

Virtual Imaging Trials in Medicine
Alliance Manchester Business School
Manchester, United Kingdom
2 - 4 June 2025

VITM 2025

PROCEEDINGS

Synthetic thoracic radiography generation for nodule detection improvement

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1. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

The use of deep learning models has become increasingly common in medical image analysis, particularly for detection, classification and segmentation tasks. To effectively train these diagnostic tools, a large database of labeled images is required to prevent overfitting and promote model generalisation [1]. Collecting these samples is a major obstacle due to the time, money, and human resources required to acquire labeled images, as well as data anonymisation requirements.

To improve the performance of these diagnostic tools, various data augmentation strategies have been developed to generate synthetic images along with their corresponding labels. The most common method is the use of generative networks [2]. However, generative networks have limitations, including the need for a large database for training and often limited generalisation capabilities [3].

The objective of this study is to evaluate the efficacy of model-based data augmentation, where a pathology is modeled on a virtual anthropomorphic model and a synthetic image is generated using a computerised scanner model [4]. The initial focus of the investigation is on the detection of pulmonary nodules on thoracic radiography and CT scans.

2. METHODS

2.1. Image generation

We used the X-ray imaging simulator gVXR [5] combined with a virtual anthropomorphic model (adapted from Z-anatomy [6]) to rapidly generate a large dataset of labeled synthetic images. Nodules shapes were either generated from the segmented CT-scan nodules of LUNA database [7], using Visualization Toolkit (VTK), or represented by a sphere of a diameter between 6 mm and 3 cm, randomly scaled in the x, y, or z axes.

To introduce variability, tissue densities were randomly adjusted within a range of 0–1%. The dimensions of the entire model were also randomly scaled within a range of 0–4%, and each lung lobe was individually scaled along the x, y, or z axis within a range of 0–4%. Each nodule was randomly assigned a Hounsfield Unit (HU) value between -174 and 300.

In order to model noise inherent to radiography [8], we modeled shot noise, movement, electronic noise, image-intensifier structure noise, and scattered radiation noise. In addition, we used quantile transformation of the pixel intensity distribution [9] to match the ones found in dataset of real data.

The synthetic dataset comprised 10,000 images, enabling us to simulate a wide range of clinical conditions.

2.2. Model training

We trained three deep learning models, on various datasets composed of: real data, synthetic data, and a mixed dataset containing both real and synthetic images. For thoracic radiography, we used YOLOv8m [10]

Figure 1. Summary of datasets used, evaluation metrics, and model performance for radiography a. Recall (for nFP=0.2) and mAP performance of YOLOv8 model. Real data come from Node21. Red line indicates recall performance of thoracic radiologists [14] b. Recall (for nFP=0.2) and mAP performance of RetinaNet model

and RetinaNet. Real training data were obtained from the NODE21 database [11]. To evaluate model performance, we used a standardized test set comprising radiographs from either the NODE21 or VinDr-CXR (VDB) datasets [12] —none of which were used during training.

For CT-scan, we used NoduleNet model [13] and LUNA16 database [7] for training and testing the model.

3. RESULTS

On 2D-Xray, YOLOv8 demonstrated the most significant performance improvement, with sensitivity increasing up to 19% and mAP increasing up to 7%.

As a baseline for further comparisons, we first trained the model exclusively on real radiographic data (1767 images from NODE21 database), resulting in a sensitivity of 73.3% for a nFP=0.2 (mAP=85.5%). Training the model solely on synthetic data (8499 images) resulted in reduced performance, with sensitivity at 49.8% (mAP=73.8%). However, training the model on a combined dataset of real (1767 images) and synthetic radiographs at real-to-synthetic ratios of 0.1:0.9 (i.e. 10% real radiographs and 90% of simulated radiographs) and 0.2:0.8 (i.e. 20% real radiographs and 80% of simulated radiographs) led to significant improvements. Sensitivity increased to 75.6% (mAP=88.5%) and 87.3% (mAP=91.5%), representing an enhancement of up to 19 % in sensitivity (Figure 1.a).

To achieve a sensitivity superior to 95%, which is necessary for a medical application, we then evaluated the RetinaNet model. The model trained solely on real data reaches a sensitivity of 96.8% for a nFP=0.2 (mAP=96.3%). However, its performance dropped significantly when tested on the external VBD dataset to a sensitivity of 52.4% and mAP of 57.9%. To address this, we trained this model solely on synthetic data, and then fine-tuning it on a subset of real data from Node21. This approach preserved its performance on the NODE21 datasets (sensitivity = 96.4% and mAP=97%), and improved its generalization, increasing sensibility by 11.3% when tested on VBD (sensitivity=58.3% and mAP = 67.8%) (Figure 1.b).

Similarly, fine-tuning NoduleNet model on a CTscan dataset composed of real-to-synthetic ratios 0.15:0.75

Figure 2. Summary of dataset used and model performance for CT-scan a. Recall (for nFP=10), AP and average DICE performance of NoduleNet model

led to an increase of 29.2% of sensitivity (at nFP=10), and 49.6% on AP50. For reference, training only on real data led to 72.6% sensitivity and 40.7%AP50, while training on the mixed dataset led to 83.3% sensitivity and 60.9%AP50. However, we observed no significant improvement in segmentation quality, with the DICE coefficient remaining at 80.5% for real data and 81.1% for the mixed dataset) (Figure 2.a).

4. CONCLUSION

This work underscores the use of synthetic data to overcome data scarcity and improve model performance and generalization in medical imaging. Our results with the RetinaNet model suggest that pretraining on a large synthetic dataset can enable the model to learn generalizable features, which can then be fine-tuned using a smaller, localized set of real data. This two-stage training approach presents a practical and scalable solution for medical domains where acquiring large volumes of annotated real data is challenging.

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Deep learning-based 4D pulmonary evaluation from 2D X-ray video: an in-silico study

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Dynamic chest radiography (DCR) is an emerging functional imaging technique that uses a flat-panel detector (FPD)¹. Approved by U.S. FDA in 2019, DCR systems have been introduced in medical facilities in Japan, the US, the UK, and Asian countries, and pulmonary function can be evaluated in a general radiography room without contrast media or radiopharmaceuticals.^{2,3} By optimizing imaging conditions, the total radiation dose can be less than two projections in conventional radiography. These features make DCR accessible for diagnosing and monitoring pulmonary function based on dynamic imaging findings, such as diaphragm motion and changes in lung density caused by respiration and blood flow (Figure 1). However, its analysis is currently limited to two dimensions (2D).

Recent advancements in generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) models have made it possible to synthesize three-dimensional (3D) images from 2D inputs.⁴ Applying this technology to DCR enables the creation of four-dimensional (4D) CT from DCR images, facilitating 3D pulmonary function analysis. However, obtaining sufficient paired 2D/3D datasets consisting of multiple respiratory phases in clinical practice is challenging. Therefore, we propose an in-silico solution: training and validating AI models using simulated datasets followed by clinical applications. This study investigates the feasibility of deep learning-based 4D pulmonary evaluation from 2D X-ray video through an in-silico approach.

Figure 1 Overview of dynamic chest radiography.

B. METHODS

Fifty-six virtual patients (age range: 0–78 years; M: F = 33:23) were generated using the extended cardiac-torso (XCAT) program.⁵ All virtual patients were designed to have an average heart rate (60 beats/min) and forced breathing (diaphragm motion: 4 cm) consisting of 150 phases in 10 s, mimicking real-world DCR.¹ Using an X-ray simulator,⁶ biplanar (posteroanterior [PA] and lateral [LA]) projections were synthesized, generating 8,400 paired chest X-ray and CT images (train:test = 6750 : 1650).

The X2CT-GAN model was trained to generate CT from single-view (PA) or multi-view (PA+LA) inputs.⁴ Training used the Adam optimizer (learning rate = 0.0002; $\beta_1 = 0.5$, $\beta_2 = 0.99$). Generated CTs were quantitatively evaluated using peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and structural similarity index (SSIM). The lung volumes were measured on generated CTs and then compared against reference lung volumes using mean absolute error (MAE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). In addition, 3D renderings were visually assessed for the reproducibility of 4D lung dynamics. Finally, the model was tested on clinical data. Since real PA and LA images are obtained in different respiratory phases as separate image sequences, only the frontal view was input into the trained GAN model for the 3D reconstruction of clinical cases.

C. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

For CT images generated from single-view X-rays, the mean PSNR/SSIM was 20.08 ± 0.66 dB / 0.578 ± 0.093 . For multi-view input, the values improved to 21.08 ± 0.76 dB / 0.626 ± 0.107 . The MAE and MAPE of left/right lung volumes for single-view reconstruction were 460/576 mL and 19.1/19.7%, respectively; multi-view reconstructions achieved 173/176 mL and 6.4/6.1%.

Multi-view reconstructions accurately reproduced 4D lung dynamics in both shape and density, while single-view results were less reliable (Figure 2). In clinical cases, although organ shape was distorted as in the single-view simulation, density changes over time were generally preserved.

These results suggest that in-silico training is an effective strategy for developing AI models—such as X2CT-GAN—when real-world training data are limited. Although clinical performance was limited with single-view input, our findings indicate that switching to synchronized multi-view input may significantly improve outcomes. We plan to match the respiratory phase of PA and LA images in clinical cases and input them into a multi-view model in our future work.

Figure 2 CT generated from X-ray images.

D. CONCLUSION

We developed the X2CT-GAN model to reproduce 4D lung dynamics from 2D X-ray images using virtual patients and evaluated it with both virtual and clinical data. While challenges remain for clinical deployment, our in-silico results demonstrate the feasibility of 4D pulmonary evaluation from 2D X-ray video.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors thank the departments of respiratory medicine, thoracic surgery, and radiology at Kanazawa University Hospital for providing the clinical data.

This research was supported in part by MEXT KAKENHI [23K18272, 21KK0286] and NIH [5P41EB028744].

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Overview of X-ray Imaging Simulation Tools for medical research: features, capabilities, and computational considerations

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ABSTRACT

X-ray simulation tools are vital for advancing medical imaging research, offering an efficient alternative to physical experiments. However, with a wide range of available platforms, selecting the right tool can be challenging, particularly for users who are not developers. This study surveyed ten prominent frameworks from academia, industry, and regulatory bodies to compare their features, performance, and accessibility. The tools support various modalities such as CT, CBCT, mammography, and fluoroscopy, and differ in programming language, computational demands, and hardware use. GPU-accelerated tools like VICTRE and DukeSim generally offer faster processing, while CPU-based frameworks like CatSim provide broader accessibility. Validation methods and public availability also vary across tools. Future enhancements aim to improve anatomical realism, computational efficiency, and support for additional imaging tasks. This overview helps researchers navigate the landscape of virtual imaging tools and choose platforms aligned with their specific needs and resources.

1. INTRODUCTION

Virtual X-ray imaging plays a key role in the development, optimization, and validation of medical imaging technologies by simulating the full imaging process in a safe, repeatable, and cost-effective way. It is especially useful for testing new system designs, evaluating algorithms, and generating datasets for machine learning. However, these simulation tools differ greatly in their computational performance. Some prioritize physical realism and detailed modeling, while others focus on speed and usability. As data requirements grow due to high-resolution phantoms and AI-driven workflows, understanding these differences becomes increasingly important. This study compares ten widely used simulation frameworks from academia, industry, and regulatory agencies, providing insights into their computational characteristics to help researchers select the most suitable tool for their specific applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

We conducted a structured survey to collect information on the computational performance and broader usage characteristics of virtual x-ray imaging frameworks. The goal was to capture key technical details, performance metrics, and development trends across tools used in research, industry, and regulatory settings. The survey consisted of five main sections:

- **General information:** Participants were asked to provide their name, affiliation, role, and email for follow-up clarification if needed.
- **Framework overview:** This section captured the name of the framework, its origin (academic, industrial, or regulatory), and the development stages it supports (e.g., design, development, evaluation, or optimization).
- **Technical specifications:** Participants detailed the imaging modalities their framework supports (e.g., CT, CBCT, mammography, radiography, fluoroscopy, tomosynthesis), input/output formats, programming language, core modules, and integration with external tools such as phantoms or reconstruction software.
- **Computational performance:** Questions addressed hardware/software requirements, average computation times, known performance limitations, and novice user onboarding time.
- **Validation, access, and future development:** Participants were asked whether their framework had been validated, published in peer-reviewed studies, or made publicly available. They were also asked about ongoing development, future improvements, training/support availability, and community or collaborative activities.

The survey was administered electronically and included multiple-choice, checkbox, and open-ended questions to ensure both structured and detailed responses. We targeted developers and primary users of virtual x-ray imaging frameworks, identified through prior publications, professional networks, and public repositories. The survey was distributed via direct email outreach. Respondents were asked to complete the survey based on their most recent version of the framework and to consult collaborators if needed for specific technical details. Follow-up questions were sent in cases where clarification or additional data was required. Responses were manually reviewed and synthesized for consistency.

3. RESULTS

A total of ten participants completed the survey, representing a mix of academic, industrial, and regulatory institutions. Respondents included framework developers, imaging scientists, and clinical collaborators actively involved in virtual imaging research and tool deployment. The surveyed frameworks were: BreastSimulator¹ and XRAYImagingSimulator² (University of Varna), CatSim³ (GE Healthcare), DRASIM⁴ (Siemens), DukeSim⁵ (Duke University), Dynamic Interactive Perlin Breast Simulation Framework⁶ (Lund University), Hybrid Tool⁷ and CBCT Tool⁸ (KU Leuven), OpenVCT⁹ (University of Pennsylvania), and VICTRE¹⁰ (FDA).

3.1 Framework scope and application

The surveyed virtual imaging frameworks were primarily developed within academic institutions (7 out of 10), with the remainder originating from industry (2 frameworks) and regulatory agencies (1 framework). This distribution highlights the predominance of academia in advancing virtual imaging trial technologies. All frameworks reported capability across the design, development, and evaluation stages of virtual imaging workflows, indicating their broad applicability across the imaging system lifecycle. Regarding optimization targets, the majority focus on image quality optimization, while a smaller subset also addresses protocol and dose optimization. Specifically, protocol optimization was implemented in four frameworks, dose optimization was reported by three frameworks, and image quality optimization was the most prevalent, reported by six frameworks. In terms of imaging modalities, the frameworks predominantly catered to breast imaging modalities such as mammography and tomosynthesis, with 70% of the tools supporting mammography simulations. Computed Tomography (CT) and Cone Beam CT (CBCT) were also frequently supported, with 50% and 60% of frameworks respectively capable of simulating these modalities. Other modalities, such as radiography (RX) and fluoroscopy, were less commonly addressed. This distribution of framework origins, application stages, optimization types, and modality support reflects a broad and evolving landscape of virtual imaging tools tailored to diverse research needs in medical imaging.

3.2 Technical characteristics

The ten surveyed virtual frameworks showed a broad range of technical features in input/output data, formats, programming languages, and modular design. Most accept detailed breast anatomy inputs—such as density, size, and shape—via digital phantoms or patient models, along with scanner settings and x-ray spectra. Some also simulate lesions using tissue characteristics and population data. Inputs vary from voxelized phantoms and DICOM to text or binary files, while outputs include projection data, reconstructed images, dose, and noise maps, commonly in DICOM or binary formats. Programming languages used include Python, C/C++, and Matlab, with CUDA used for acceleration. Frameworks feature modular components such as ray tracing, Monte Carlo simulations, finite element breast modeling, lesion insertion, and reconstruction algorithms. Some also offer post-processing and visualization tools. This technical diversity reflects the adaptability and sophistication of current breast imaging simulation tools for varied research and clinical needs.

3.3 Computational performance

The surveyed frameworks vary in computational demands, influenced by their complexity and imaging tasks. Most use multi-core CPUs or NVIDIA GPUs, with tools like VICTRE and DukeSim leveraging GPU acceleration, while others such as CatSim rely on CPUs. Simulation times range from minutes for simple tasks to several hours for complex or high-resolution models. Limitations include handling large phantoms and optimizing performance for available hardware. Some frameworks use simplifications to reduce run time. GPU tools are faster but need specialized hardware; CPU tools are more accessible but slower. Tool choice should balance speed, detail, and available resources, making computational performance a key factor in selecting the right simulation platform.

3.4 Validation

Validation is essential to ensure the reliability and realism of virtual imaging tools. Many frameworks have undergone thorough validation using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Catsim/XCIST has been extensively validated for spatial resolution¹¹, X-ray spectrum modeling¹², and dose reconstruction^{13,14}. The fidelity of VICTRE has been confirmed through clinical studies^{10,15}. OpenVCT^{9,16,17} and DukeSim¹⁸⁻²¹ have demonstrated accuracy through years of comparative studies. Tools from the University of Varna rely on Monte Carlo simulation benchmarking, evaluation of radiological properties of 3D-printed materials, and comparison with images of physical phantoms^{1,22-25}. Similarly, tools developed at Leuven incorporate technical system characteristics validated against real measurements and Monte Carlo simulations^{8,26-28}. The Dynamic Interactive Perlin Breast Simulation Framework achieves tissue realism through expert-driven parameter tuning and radiologist visual grading, built upon a validated image acquisition model⁶. These multi-level validations highlight the maturity and robustness of current virtual imaging trial platforms.

3.5 Future development

Future developments in X-ray imaging simulation tools focus on improving anatomical realism, supporting more imaging modalities, and enhancing computational performance. Several frameworks are advancing lesion modeling and tissue representation, such as VICTRE's growing lesions and DRASIM's PCCT noise simulation. Tools like CatSim and OpenVCT are refining physics models and integration with open-source software, while DukeSim expands scanner support. GPU acceleration is a key priority, with BreastSimulator and XRAYImagingSimulator adopting CUDA for faster simulations and broader applications. Overall, these updates aim to make virtual imaging tools more robust, realistic, and widely applicable in research and clinical settings.

4. DISCUSSION

This survey of ten virtual imaging frameworks highlights a field primarily led by academic institutions, supplemented by industry and regulatory contributions. Most frameworks comprehensively address the imaging workflow stages (design, development, and evaluation) with a strong emphasis on image quality optimization and breast imaging modalities, especially mammography and tomosynthesis. The inclusion of dose and protocol optimization in some tools further addresses important clinical concerns like patient safety and workflow efficiency.

The frameworks show technical diversity in input data types, output formats, and programming languages (Python, C/C++, Matlab), often leveraging GPU acceleration to balance performance with accessibility. Their modular architectures, incorporating physics-based x-ray models, lesion simulation, and reconstruction algorithms, reflect a mature ecosystem that supports detailed, customizable simulations and easy integration with other tools.

Computation times range from minutes to hours, reflecting trade-offs between simulation complexity, anatomical detail, and available resources. GPU-accelerated frameworks generally enable faster processing but require specialized hardware, while CPU-based tools offer broader accessibility at the cost of longer runtimes. Pragmatic simplifications, like pre-generated texture libraries, help manage these constraints.

Validation remains essential for trust and adoption. Frameworks such as CatSim and VICTRE are notable for extensive validation against physical systems, setting high standards for clinical relevance. Others like OpenVCT and DukeSim provide thorough component-level validation supported by publications. The variety in validation approaches and access, ranging from open-source to institution-specific, illustrates the field's collaborative but still evolving nature, highlighting the need for greater standardization and transparency.

Planned enhancements focus on improving anatomical and physical realism, expanding modality support (including emerging techniques like photon-counting CT and contrast-enhanced mammography), and boosting computational efficiency. Investments in GPU acceleration and integration of open-source reconstruction software point toward more scalable, user-friendly frameworks capable of supporting large-scale virtual trials. Collectively, these developments position virtual imaging simulations as crucial tools for regulatory science, clinical decision support, and cost-effective, ethical imaging research.

5. CONCLUSION

This survey reveals a robust and sophisticated ecosystem of virtual imaging frameworks with complementary strengths. Their continued evolution and validation will be essential to fully realize the potential of in silico trials to accelerate innovation, optimize imaging protocols, and ultimately improve patient outcomes. X-ray simulation tools vary significantly in computational performance, reflecting diverse priorities in design, from flexibility and accessibility to accuracy and scalability. As simulation becomes more central to imaging research and development, understanding the computational profiles of available tools is essential. This study offers a comparative overview to help guide the selection of frameworks based on performance, modality, and application-specific needs.

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From virtual data to real insights: an overview of simulation-based inference for scientific discovery

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

1. The Rise of Simulation-Based Learning in Science

The integration of simulations with artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative approach across scientific disciplines. Virtual data, generated through physics-based simulations, now serves as a cornerstone for training and validating machine learning (ML) models in numerous fields. In particle physics, for instance, simulation frameworks enable researchers to predict complex particle interactions in high-energy collisions ¹. In astronomy, ML models increasingly leverage high-fidelity simulations that reproduce the complexity of observations to perform highly efficient cosmological and astrophysical parameter inference through simulation-based inference (SBI) ². In medical physics, virtual patients and trials have revolutionized research methodologies. Here, simulations accelerate the development of diagnostic tools while addressing ethical concerns and logistical constraints inherent in clinical research ³. The fundamental advantage across all these domains lies in simulation's ability to provide abundant and optimal ground truth labels, rarely available with real-world data. This labeled virtual data provides a strong basis for building AI models that can uncover useful information from complex systems.

2. Bridging the Domain Gap: From Simulation to Reality

Despite their usefulness, there's an important caveat with simulation-based approaches: they rely on the assumption that simulations truly represent the real world. While significant efforts are made to create realistic simulations, computational models inevitably simplify the complexity of natural phenomena. This discrepancy creates a "domain gap" between simulated and real data, potentially undermining the performance of AI models when deployed in real-world settings ⁴. This poses a fundamental challenge for ML pipelines, which often converge on domain-specific solutions during optimization. Experimental evidence has repeatedly demonstrated performance degradation when models trained on simulated data are applied to real-world scenarios. This problem is well-recognized in computer vision, where numerous challenges have been organized specifically to address the simulation-to-reality gap ⁵. In ideal circumstances, one might train models using a mixture of simulated and real data, or fine-tune simulation-trained models with real data. However, the absence of ground truth labels in real data often prevents such straightforward solutions. Domain adaptation techniques offer promising alternatives, with domain adversarial neural networks (DANNs) emerging as a particularly effective approach for aligning features across domains without requiring labels in the target domain ⁴.

B. METHODS

We outline a general framework for leveraging simulated data and ML methods to derive insights across scientific disciplines, with emphasis on addressing the domain gap between simulation and reality and on achieving probabilistic outputs for degenerate problems.

1. Ensuring Simulation Fidelity: Metrics and Diagnostics

The effectiveness of SBI relies on the alignment between simulated and real data. Rigorous validation protocols are essential to ensure that synthetic data captures the key characteristics of real-world observations—even before applying domain adaptation techniques. For instance, noise patterns, signal-to-noise ratios, and—for vision tasks—power spectra should exhibit consistent distributions across both domains. In specific scientific domains, dedicated diagnostics can be used to assess the fidelity of simulations. In medical imaging, for instance, the distributions of radiomic features should closely match between synthetic and clinical images to ensure that insights remain transferable ⁶. These metrics not only validate simulation quality but also identify specific areas where domain adaptation may be necessary.

2. Domain Adversarial Training for Robust Transfer

DANNs address the challenge of transferring knowledge from simulated to real data. These networks consist of three key components: a feature extractor, a label predictor, and a domain classifier. The feature extractor aims to learn representations that are both informative for the primary task and invariant across domains ⁴. The innovation of DANNs lies in their training objective: the feature extractor is trained to maximize the domain classifier's confusion while minimizing the label predictor's error. This adversarial approach forces the network to

learn domain-invariant features—representations that cannot be easily identified as belonging to either the simulated or real domain. Interestingly, DANNs can be integrated with various neural architectures⁵. By aligning the distribution of embedding features across domains, these methods ensure that estimates derived from simulated data remain valid when applied to real observations. This alignment occurs without requiring labeled data in the real domain, making the approach particularly valuable for applications where ground truth is unavailable.

Figure 1 A sketch of the proposed framework for simulation-based inference using normalising flows and domain adversarial training. The embedding network extracts domain-invariant summary statistics from input data (e.g., spectra, images, datacubes), which are used by a conditional flow to perform inference with associated uncertainties.

3. Neural Posterior Estimation

Many scientific problems are inherently degenerate, meaning that different combinations of parameters can produce nearly indistinguishable observable outcomes. To address this, researchers have long relied on simulated data within Bayesian frameworks, where synthetic datasets are used as inputs to Monte Carlo methods to enable rigorous uncertainty quantification. Standard ML methods, by contrast, often fail to capture the full extent of uncertainty. SBI with normalizing flows (NFs) offers a powerful alternative^{1,7}. It combines the flexibility of neural networks with the probabilistic rigor of Bayesian inference, and its amortized nature allows fast inference after training by sampling from simple distributions to reconstruct complex posteriors. NFs work by transforming simple probability distributions (typically Gaussian) into complex, potentially multi-modal posteriors through a series of invertible transformations⁷. In conditional settings, the object of interest—such as a spectrum, image, or data cube—acts as a condition for the flow. Because these inputs are often high-dimensional, an embedding network first extracts relevant summary statistics, which are then passed to the flow to generate the conditional posterior. Importantly, the embedding network in conditional NFs can be combined with a DANN to ensure domain invariance.

C. RESULTS EXAMPLES — PRELIMINARY APPLICATIONS IN ASTRONOMY

Recent work has demonstrated the effectiveness of SBI in astronomical research. In Bracci et al.⁸, we showed that ML models trained on carefully calibrated simulations could successfully predict properties of real galaxies observed with the Very Large Telescope, classifying

with high accuracy⁹ interstellar nebulae into HII regions, planetary nebulae, and supernova remnants. Looking toward future instrumentation, in Ginolfi et al. ⁹, we highlighted the importance of simulation-based pipelines in preparing for new observational capabilities. In particular, we trained a multi-task neural network to achieve optimal performance in deriving physical properties (e.g., redshift, stellar mass and star formation rate) from simulated galaxy spectra for the upcoming MOONS instrument. In Belfiore et al. ¹⁰, we addressed the challenge of domain adaptation in galactic spectroscopy by implementing a DANN to align feature distributions between simulated and observed sets of galaxy emission lines. Our results show significant improvement (about 25%) in parameter estimation when domain adaptation is applied, compared to models trained solely on simulations. Preliminary results applying SBI with neural posterior estimation in galaxy spectroscopy are also showing promising outcomes.

D. CONCLUSION

We argue that the integration of SBI with domain adaptation represents a powerful paradigm for scientific discovery across disciplines. Domain adaptation addresses the key challenge of bridging the gap between simulated and real data, allowing models trained on synthetic inputs to generalize effectively. When combined with neural posterior estimation, this approach also enables efficient inference with rigorous uncertainty quantification. The case studies in astronomy demonstrate the practical benefits of this framework. Models trained on simulations can successfully analyze real observations, speed up preparation for new instruments, and deliver reliable uncertainty estimates for complex parameters. These capabilities are equally valuable in other fields, where similar challenges of limited labeled data and complex parameter spaces exist. As simulation capabilities continue to advance, driven by increasing computational power and more sophisticated physical models, the alignment between virtual and real data will improve. Combined with ongoing developments in domain adaptation methodology, these advances promise to further enhance the reliability and impact of SBI.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Objective and subjective validation of data-driven digital breast phantoms for in-silico replication of mammography and digital breast tomosynthesis

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Digital breast phantoms derived from 3D clinical images (data-driven) benefit from realistic tissue distribution and silhouette. On the other hand, the limited spatial resolution of the used clinical images affects definition in the generated digital phantoms and may introduce patterns and coarse structures when used for virtual clinical trials (VCT). This work aims at validating a cohort of data-driven digital breast phantoms for VCTs in mammography (DM) and digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) outlining limitation in the realisms in the generated images.

The validation is performed via an objective analysis of the breast parenchyma in simulated images and via a subjective evaluation meant to compare simulated images vs real images from an open dataset.

B. METHODS

1. The dataset of data-driven digital breast phantoms and the simulation pipeline

The dataset of the digital breast phantoms included 126 breast phantoms with voxel size ranging between 0.19 mm and 0.43 mm; they were derived from clinical breast images acquired via a dedicated breast CT scanner and by means of a tissue classification in adipose, glandular and skin tissues [1]. The compressed configuration adopted in DM and DBT was reached via a computational compression software [1]. Images were simulated via the VICTRE platform by implementing the Siemens Mammomat Inspiration apparatus [2]; DBT slices were reconstructed via TIGRE software [3]. The simulated images were analyzed either without performing any post processing or after a gaussian filtering meant to take into account the lower spatial resolution of real detector when compared with the ideal detector simulated via the Monte Carlo software, which neglects some physical phenomena that may reduce the spatial resolution [4].

2. The objective evaluation

The objective validation was performed via the evaluation of the β parameter [5], which characterizes the anatomical noise in the breast images. This is derived from the noise power spectrum (NPS) of the breast images, and it is equal to the slope of the curve represented in log-log scale in a determined frequency range [5]. In this work, a Matlab routine was developed in order to evaluate the 2D NPS over 1000 regions of interest (ROIs) randomly selected over the simulated 2D mammograms or 3D DBT stacks. In this second case, the ROIs were randomly selected over the entire 3D reconstructed volume, by excluding the 4 upper and lower slices, affected by boundary effects and the presence of the skin. The 1D NPS was derived from the 2D NPS by means of a radial averaging and the β evaluated as the slope of the 1D NPS in log-log scale in a frequency range comprised between 0.04 mm^{-1} and 0.50 mm^{-1} .

3. The subjective evaluation

The subjective analysis was based on a two-alternative forced choice (2AFC) test performed by experienced radiologists. A suitable Matlab routine with a graphical user interface was developed for supporting the radiologists in the evaluations (fig. 1). The human observers were asked to identify the simulated image ROI between a simulated and a real one, for 300 squared ROIs whose side was 150 pixels. Real mammograms were derived from an open-access database[6]. Additionally, radiologists were asked to analyze and outline noticed differences between simulated and real images.

Figure 1. Graphical user interface for the 2AFC subjective analysis. It permits to select which one between the two shown ROI is the simulated one.

C. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows a simulated DM exam (fig. 2a) and a slice from a simulated DBT image (fig. 2b). Figure 3 shows the corresponding NPS curves, in log-log scale. The linear fit outlined in red permitted to derive the β parameter as the slope of the curve.

Figure 2. Simulated a) mammogram and b) DBT slice.

Figure 3. NPS in log-log scale evaluated from the simulated images of fig. 1. The continuous red lines indicate the linear curve fit whose slope determine the β index.

Table 1 reports the average value and the standard deviation of the evaluated β parameters, these computed over the 126 simulated DM and DBT examinations.

Table 1 β parameter statistics evaluated for DM and DBT over the 126 simulated examinations.

	Mean	Std Dev
DM	2.71	0.40
DBT	3.09	0.28

From the subjective analysis of DM images, it resulted that 95% of the simulated images were correctly identified by the radiologists. Main reasons, outlined by the radiologists, were due by the absence of the microcalcification clusters in the simulated images and coarse vertical structures, that sometime appeared in the ROI from the simulated images. Additionally, thin ligaments and ducts, that are present in the real images, are not depicted with high fidelity in the simulated images. No statistical differences in the subjective evaluation are noticeable when the gaussian filtering is implemented over the images.

D. DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the suitability of a dataset of data-driven digital breast phantoms for virtual clinical trials in DM and DBT. In particular, the investigation focused on the realism of the breast parenchyma in images produced by means of the VICTRE simulation toolkit, based on a Monte Carlo approach. The first analysis focused on the evaluation of the β parameter in the simulated images, this characterizing the presence of the anatomical noise. Such a parameter is expected to be about 3 in clinical DM and DBT images [5]. In coherence with the expected value, the β parameter evaluated over the simulated images for the 126 digital breast phantoms resulted 3.09 in DBT, averaged over the cohort, with a standard deviation of 0.28. In mammography, the average value over the cohort resulted 2.71, with a standard deviation of 0.40.

On the other hand, the subjective analysis performed by means of experienced radiologists outlined that the breast parenchyma in the simulated DM images is distinguishable from that represented in real images. A 2AFC test demonstrated that the radiologist was able to correctly identify the simulated images in 95% of the cases. This resulted as a consequence of the absence of microcalcification in simulated images, of the lack of fine details as ducts and ligaments and from a coarse structure sometimes present in the simulated images, this due by the large voxel size of the digital phantoms. Same tests on DBT images are planned for the next future.

E. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that simulated DBT and DM images obtained via a cohort of data-driven digital breast phantoms produced anatomical noise, characterized by the β parameter, in line of what expected from real images. On the other hand, a subjective analysis outlined the limitation of the phantoms, in particular in depicting fine details such as microcalcifications and ligaments. However, the complexity of the anatomical noise makes still the phantom eligible for specific evaluations, in particular related to technical parameters of the scanner.

F. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interests

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Impact of patient positioning on neural network organ dose estimation in CT

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Although patient centering is a fundamental part of optimal computed tomography (CT) procedure, it is not always possible to achieve perfect centration in every clinical scenario. Patient-related factors and high workloads can lead to misalignments that affect radiation exposure¹. Previous studies have shown that patient positioning has a significant impact on the radiation dose received during CT imaging. It has been found that even minimal deviations from the center can lead to significant dose variations of up to 47 %². In clinical practice, positional shifts of about ± 4 cm in the vertical direction and ± 2 cm in the lateral direction can occur³.

Proofs-of-concept for the use of neural networks (NNs) for rapid organ dose estimation were previously described in literature^{4,5}. Since the selection of the training data set has an enormous impact on the performance of a NN, it is of utmost importance to gain knowledge about criteria that can be used to identify training data sets that lead to robust estimates.

This study aimed to investigate how a typical patient misalignment affects organ dose estimations of a NN trained solely on centered patient data. Specifically, the goal was to quantify the uncertainties introduced by excluding mispositioned cases from the training dataset and to evaluate the necessity of incorporating a more diverse and representative sample of positioning variations into the training process.

B. METHODS

A convolutional NN based on the U-Net architecture was developed to calculate 3d dose distributions in a patient's body. The network was trained using a dataset of Monte Carlo (MC) simulated CT dose distributions calculated from synthetic patient geometries (XCAT⁶). These synthetic geometries were generated by sampling height, subcutaneous fat layer thickness, and organ volumes from uniform distributions, resulting in a diverse population⁷. All training geometries were perfectly centered within the CT scanner to reflect ideal acquisition conditions. As input to the NN, electron density maps representing the spatial distribution of the tissue were generated for each geometry. In addition, a three-dimensional air kerma attenuation curve in a 32cm-water-cylinder was computed for a GE Optima CT660 scanner. This attenuation curve, specific to the scanner's radiation field, served as a physics-based input to the network. The electron density distribution and attenuation curve together formed the input channels to the U-Net, enabling it to learn the mapping between patient anatomy and absorbed dose.

After training, the model was evaluated on a test dataset consisting of laterally and vertically shifted versions of the original synthetic geometries, simulating patient mispositioning scenarios. For this, the respective input electron density maps were shifted accordingly.

Organ doses were derived from the dose distributions obtained from the NN and the MC⁸ ground truth data. To compare the NN and MC results, the organ doses for each patient geometry were summed separately for each method and the relative deviations between the results of the two methods were calculated. To see if the difference between NN (trained only on centered patient geometries) and MC changed with the patient misalignment, the mean relative deviation was then calculated over the entire test set for positional shifts of up to ± 4 cm in the vertical direction and 10 cm in the lateral direction.

C. RESULTS

Figure 1 illustrates the change in the mean relative deviation of summed doses between MC and the NN (trained only on centered patient geometries), to positional displacements, evaluated independently for lateral and vertical shifts of the patient geometries.

For lateral displacements (0 to 10 cm), increasingly positive deviations were observed. At the reference position (0 cm shift), the mean organ dose deviation was minimal (-1.01 %), serving as a baseline. A displacement of 4 cm resulted in a mean deviation of 3.32 %, which became more positive with increasing displacement: 9.24 % at 6 cm, 18.75 % at 8 cm, and 32.5 % at 10 cm. The error bars in Figure 1, representing standard deviations, also increase with the lateral shift, indicating greater sensitivity of dose assessments to the patient geometry variations.

Vertical negative shifts (e.g., -4 cm to -1 cm) resulted in increasingly positive mean relative deviations (up to +11.37 %), while positive vertical shifts (above the scanner isocenter) show negative deviations: -1.43 % at 1 cm to -2.9 % at +3 cm.

Figure 1 Mean relative deviation (%) between NN estimation and Monte Carlo simulation based on summed organ doses, in dependence of lateral (left) and vertical (right) patient displacements. Error bars represent the standard deviation over all test cases.

D. DISCUSSION

The findings of this study highlight the significant impact of patient mispositioning on the accuracy of NN based organ dose estimation in CT imaging. While the U-Net model performed well for centered patient geometries — with minimal mean summed organ dose deviations at 0 cm displacement — its performance degraded when tested on laterally and vertically shifted geometries. Vertical displacements introduced substantial overestimation of dose, with deviations exceeding 11 % at a 4 cm shift. A negative vertical displacement has shown a greater effect than a positive displacement. Lateral displacements had a smaller impact. In the clinically relevant range of 2 cm³, no significant change in dose prediction was observed.

These results show the limitation of using training datasets composed exclusively of centered patient geometries. The NN used was not exposed to positional variability during training and failed to generalize reliably to typical clinical conditions where centering errors are common. It can be assumed that the limited spatial expansion of the air kerma attenuation curve could be the reason for the failure (see Figure 2).

The increased standard deviation in organ dose deviation with larger displacement further suggests that mispositioning not only introduces bias but also a higher sensitivity to patient geometry variations.

Figure 2 Effect of displacement on dose distribution as relative deviation between NN estimation and MC results in % for three geometries from the test dataset for lateral shifts of 0 cm, 6 cm and 10 cm (left to right). *d*

E. CONCLUSION

An NN trained only on centered patient geometries showed significant deviations in organ dose estimations compared to MC results when the patient positioning was altered in realistic limits. For vertical shifts the deviations are out of the acceptable range and more extensive training datasets should be used for those cases.

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Impact of Image Restoration on Mammographic Quality: Correlating Objective Metrics with Model Observer Performance

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Keywords: Digital mammography, image processing, image quality assessment, virtual imaging trials, model observer.

1. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Although Digital Breast Tomosynthesis (DBT) has emerged as a promising tool for breast cancer screening,¹ Full-Field Digital Mammography (FFDM) is the most widely used imaging modality for this purpose.² It is well known that one of the essential requirements for medical diagnosis using mammography is good image quality.³ However, it is not possible to achieve that by reducing the exposure dose, because it leads to an increased amount of visible noise in the image. Therefore, the radiation dose used for image acquisition directly influences the quality of the mammographic image and, consequently, the performance of radiologists.⁴

In recent years, several studies have proposed ways to reduce the radiation dose in mammography while maintaining image quality suitable for diagnosis. One of the proposals is the digital image processing (restoration) of low-dose acquisitions using mathematical⁵ or data-based models.⁶ However, the image restoration process, which aims to reduce noise by estimating the noise-free signal, results in a blurring of the image details.

Many human observer studies have been conducted to assess the quality of mammography images after preprocessing steps. However, these studies are costly, time-consuming, and subject to interobserver variability. Objective metrics can automatically predict the quality perceived by human observers and are useful in real-world applications.^{7,8} However, most objective metrics were originally developed and validated to analyze “natural” images, with the goal of replacing subjective evaluation of image quality.⁹ In the case of medical images, the application of objective metrics should be done with great caution, especially when the image quality assessment is related to a specific diagnostic task.

Furthermore, although the negative impact of signal blur on mammographic image quality is well established,^{4,10} little is known about how it can be measured objectively, nor how quantitative results can be related to diagnostic values. The aim of this study is to evaluate the quality of mammograms restored by image processing and to relate the results of objective metrics to the performance of a model observer in the task of detecting microcalcifications.

2. METHODS

2.1 Image dataset

Our image dataset used in this study was first generated by simulating 10 high-resolution breast anatomies (voxel of 30 μm) and heterogeneous density using the VICTRE (Virtual Clinical Trial for Regulatory Evaluation) pipeline.¹¹ Also using the VICTRE package, the FEBio tool was used to apply a compression force to the breast volumes to achieve a thickness of 45 mm.

The phantoms were projected using a new ray tracing method based on the algorithm of Siddon.¹² This approach is useful to acquire the reference images (ground truth) needed to evaluate the objective full-reference quality metrics. Otherwise, the use of Monte Carlo simulations by VICTRE would not provide the reference

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images and, consequently, it would not be possible to calculate many of the quality metrics often used in the literature. The images were synthesized based on the parameters of the Selenia Dimensions Mammography System unit (Hologic Inc., USA), where the detector was 24 cm x 12 cm and each element was 70 μm in size. The target/filter combination considered in the simulation was W/Rh (tungsten/rhodium), with a 30 kVp spectrum and a source-detector distance of 70 cm.

Based on the proposal of a previous study,¹³ five real microcalcifications of approximately 200 μm were used to generate a simulated cluster in a 1 cm^2 region. The specific size of the lesions was defined according to the results of a recent paper,¹⁴ which showed that such structures of approximately this size are challenging in detection tasks, even after the application of restoration techniques. The computational insertion into the previously projected virtual anatomies was done with a contrast of 8%, a value considered difficult to detect small microcalcifications, according to previous studies that performed tests with human observers using a staircase protocol.^{10,15,16} In addition, the cluster was inserted into dozens of regions of high glandularity, i.e., those with at least 80% of the pixels considered dense by the LIBRA tool.¹⁷

Given the reference images and the addition of microcalcifications, the noise insertion step can be used to simulate acquisitions at different radiation doses. We used the model developed by Borges et al.,¹⁸ which takes into account both the spatial dependence of the quantum noise and the electronic noise. The model parameters were estimated using calibration images of a real polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) phantom available at the Hospital of the University of Pennsylvania.⁵ Simulations were performed using the automatic exposure control (AEC) mode as the standard full-dose (100%). A reduction to 50% and an increase to 200% of the standard dose were also simulated. To enable the calculation of some of the objective metrics, 5 noise simulations (realizations) were generated for each image.

The image restoration approach followed our previous research proposal,^{14,19} where the original noisy image is combined with the one resulting from the denoising algorithm using a weighted blending step. The weighting factor was over-adjusted based on the full-reference metric MNSE (Mean Normalized Squared Error),⁵ so that the restored images of 50% and 100% achieved approximately the same error as the original images of 100% and 200%, respectively. Five subgroups were generated for analysis: $Z_{50\%}$, $\hat{Z}_{50\% \rightarrow 100\%}$, $Z_{100\%}$, $\hat{Z}_{100\% \rightarrow 200\%}$, and $Z_{200\%}$, where Z is the original noisy image and \hat{Z} is the restored one.

The image set for quality assessment was based on regions of interest (ROIs), since the scope of this work includes a Signal-Known-Exactly (SKE) and Background-Known-Statistically (BKS) task, i.e. the signal present in the analyzed region is known, while the background is statistically modeled. Therefore, 400 ROIs (144x144 pixels) were extracted for each phantom, equally divided into the subgroups with and without lesions, resulting in a total of 4,000 regions for each of the 5 subgroups (20,000 ROIs).

2.2 Objective quality metrics

We included objective metrics frequently used in the literature^{5,15,16,20} to evaluate the quality of the images. For the full reference group, whose calculation requires a ground truth image for comparison, the following metrics were chosen: SSIM (structural similarity index measure), R^* (cross-correlation component of SSIM), PSNR (peak signal-to-noise ratio), QILV (quality index based on local variance), UIQI (universal image quality index), SNR (signal-to-noise ratio), HaarPSI (Haar wavelet-based perceptual similarity index), and MNSE with its residual noise and bias components. For the no-reference metrics, which are computed only on the evaluated image, we chose NAQI (Normalized Anisotropic Quality Index), BRISQUE (Blind Referenceless Image Spatial Quality Evaluator), PIQE (Perception based Image Quality Evaluator), NIQE (Natural Image Quality Evaluator), and Sharpness. All metrics were calculated on the aforementioned regions of the raw images, i.e. without any image processing, as well as on the restored ones. The final result for each metric was given by the mean and confidence interval of the set of regions evaluated.

2.3 Model observer

The detectability of microcalcifications in the simulated conditions was evaluated by a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) study using a Model Observer (MO), a powerful tool capable of simulating human visual behavior when performing signal detection tasks. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) was extracted from the ROC study as a figure of merit.

The model observer used in this study was the Channelized Hotelling Observer (CHO), also implemented in the VICTRE package. The CHO is a type of computational observer often used in the literature because it can incorporate frequency- or orientation-selective channels that approximate the characteristics of the human visual system.²¹ Similar to the study by Badano et al. (2018),²² five convolutional Laguerre-Gauss (LG) channels were used, with a Gaussian width adjusted to approximately match the size of the microcalcifications ($\sigma = 1.5$). In addition, to degrade the observer performance to match that of human observers in our previous studies,^{10,15,16} internal noise ($\sigma = 5.75$) was added to the model’s final decision variable, inspired by Petrov et al. (2018),²¹ such that the detectability achieved 75%-80% for the standard full-dose images.¹⁴

To train the model, 750 ROIs of negative cases (signal absent) and 250 ROIs where the signal was present (cluster) were used to build the observer template, all randomly selected in the evaluated subgroup. In the test stage, the response given by the scalar test statistic was computed on 400 ROIs from each phantom, equally divided between the two groups (signal present and signal absent). This procedure was repeated 30 times to validate the consistency of the trained model and to analyze the variation of performance in each phantom. The evaluation with the model observer considered both the original and restored images, and all parameters were fixed to evaluate the ROIs of each subgroup.

3. RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the ROIs with clusters of microcalcifications extracted from the simulated phantoms. According to Figure 1 (a), (c) and (e), the simulation of dose reduction resulted in a significant increase in visible noise, as expected. On the other hand, a comparison of Figure 1 (a-b) and (c-d) shows the potential of the applied restoration algorithm, which is reflected in the perceived reduction of noise in the image. In addition, Figure 1 (f) demonstrates the contribution of the ray tracing algorithm in producing a degradation-free image.

Figure 1: Extracted ROIs: (a) $Z_{50\%}$, (b) $\hat{Z}_{50\% \rightarrow 100\%}$, (c) $Z_{100\%}$, (d) $\hat{Z}_{100\% \rightarrow 200\%}$, (e) $Z_{200\%}$, (f) ground-truth

Table 1 shows the mean and confidence interval of the objective metrics calculated on the ROIs of each subgroup, as well as the AUC achieved by the model observer. The data were analyzed using a two-sample t-test with a significance level of 5% to assess the statistical relevance of the differences between the original and restored images ($\hat{Z}_{50\% \rightarrow 100\%}$ and $Z_{100\%} / \hat{Z}_{100\% \rightarrow 200\%}$ and $Z_{200\%}$).

The SSIM, QILV, PSNR, SNR, and NIQE metrics showed no statistically significant differences between the original and restored images, indicating a limitation in detecting changes associated with blur combined with noise in mammography images. On the other hand, NAQI, BRISQUE, PIQE, and Sharpness showed statistically different means between the groups, but did not reproduce the behavior described by the model observer, suggesting less agreement with the relevant features for microcalcification detection.

Finally, MNSE, HaarPSI, R^* and UIQI showed a closer agreement with the AUC of MO, confirming the superior image quality at higher dose levels and the positive results of the restoration framework, with statistically significant differences between all analyzed subgroups.

4. DISCUSSION

Objective metrics widely used in the literature have been developed with a focus on natural images, which may compromise their effectiveness in assessing restored medical images, as indicated by SSIM, QILV, PSNR, SNR, NIQE and Sharpness. Therefore, adopting metrics that mirror the observer’s detectability is advisable, since the clinical task is more important than the quantitative and/or perceptual quality of medical images.^{7,8}

Table 1: Mean [confidence interval] of the objective metrics and the model observer for each subgroup evaluated

Metric	$Z_{50\%}$	$\hat{Z}_{50\% \rightarrow 100\%}$	$Z_{100\%}$	$\hat{Z}_{100\% \rightarrow 200\%}$	$Z_{200\%}$
MNSE	22.00[22.00;22.01]	10.34[10.33;10.35]	10.38[10.37;10.38]	5.08[5.07;5.08]	5.03[5.03;5.04]
\mathcal{R}_N	22.00[21.99;22.01]	9.88[9.87;9.88]	10.38[10.37;10.38]	4.79[4.78;4.79]	5.03[5.03;5.04]
\mathcal{B}^2	≈ 0	0.46[0.46;0.46]	≈ 0	0.29[0.29;0.29]	≈ 0
SSIM	0.60[0.60;0.60]	0.74 [0.74;0.74]	0.74 [0.74;0.74]	0.84 [0.84;0.84]	0.84 [0.84;0.84]
QILV	0.43[0.43;0.43]	0.71 [0.70;0.71]	0.71 [0.70;0.71]	0.88 [0.88;0.88]	0.88 [0.88;0.88]
R*	0.48[0.48;0.48]	0.59[0.59;0.59]	0.60[0.60;0.60]	0.71[0.71;0.71]	0.72[0.72;0.72]
PSNR	37.23[37.21;37.26]	40.41 [40.39;40.43]	40.40 [40.38;40.43]	43.44[43.42;43.47]	43.49[43.47;43.51]
UIQI	0.54[0.54;0.54]	0.67[0.67;0.67]	0.68[0.68;0.68]	0.79[0.78;0.79]	0.79[0.79;0.79]
SNR	35.00[34.99;35.02]	38.28 [38.27;38.29]	38.27 [38.25;38.28]	41.37[41.36;41.38]	41.41[41.40;41.42]
HaarPSI	0.78[0.78;0.78]	0.81[0.81;0.81]	0.86[0.86;0.86]	0.88[0.88;0.88]	0.92[0.92;0.92]
NAQI	0.12[0.12;0.12]	0.21[0.21;0.21]	0.18[0.18;0.18]	0.26[0.26;0.26]	0.24[0.24;0.24]
BRISQUE	42.17[42.15;42.19]	38.27[38.23;38.31]	40.76[40.73;40.79]	29.47[29.36;29.58]	35.86[35.78;35.94]
PIQE	67.82[67.75;67.89]	52.31[52.16;52.45]	58.39[58.26;58.52]	34.74[34.55;34.92]	42.92[42.73;43.11]
NIQE	18.89[18.89;18.89]	18.88 [18.88;18.88]	18.88 [18.88;18.88]	18.88 [18.88;18.88]	18.88 [18.88;18.88]
<i>Sharpness</i>	96.69[96.65;96.72]	90.92[90.87;90.96]	91.96[91.91;92.00]	87.58[87.52;87.64]	88.52[88.46;88.57]
AUC-MO	0.64[0.63;0.64]	0.73[0.72;0.74]	0.77[0.76;0.79]	0.79[0.77;0.81]	0.83[0.82;0.85]

\mathcal{R}_N : Residual noise; \mathcal{B}^2 : Bias squared; **Bold**: Means with no significant differences ($p > 0.05$)

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this study highlight the need for caution when applying objective metrics to assess the quality of medical images. While the approach based on the detectability of microcalcifications showed significant differences between original and restored images, commonly used metrics such as SSIM, QILV, PSNR, SNR, and NIQE showed statistically equivalent means according to the two-sample t-test. In contrast, metrics such as MNSE, HaarPSI, R*, and UIQI behaved according to the model observer and showed significant differences between the analyzed groups. Our results suggest that these metrics have greater potential to contribute to future studies aimed at assessing the quality of mammography images restored by computer processing.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) grant #2021/12673-6.

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Impact of common artefacts on mass visibility in contrast-enhanced mammography: a virtual imaging trial

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1. Abstract

Purpose: To evaluate the impact of breast-in-breast and motion artefacts on lesion visibility in contrast-enhanced mammography (CEM) using virtual imaging trials (VITs).

Approach: Computational breast phantoms of varying densities were generated with 5 mm non-spiculated masses placed centrally and peripherally to study breast-in-breast artefacts. Motion artefacts were introduced by simulating patient movement between low-energy (LE) and high-energy (HE) acquisitions. LE and HE images were generated using Monte Carlo simulations and recombined using offline Siemens software with and without motion correction. Lesion contrast and signal-difference-to-noise ratio (SDNR) were assessed.

Results: The breast-in-breast artefact reduced contrast and SDNR by up to 76% for peripheral lesions. Higher breast density slightly improved both metrics due to the weighting factor used by the recombination algorithm. Motion artefacts decreased SDNR by up to 60% without motion correction, though the motion correction algorithm recovered image quality for minor in-plane shifts.

Conclusions: Artefacts can substantially impair lesion visibility in CEM. VITs offer a valuable platform to quantify these effects in a controlled setting.

2. Introduction

Contrast-enhanced mammography (CEM) is an advanced breast imaging modality that uses an intravenous contrast agent to show tumour angiogenesis and enhance lesion visualization. This technique involves the rapid sequential acquisition of both low-energy (LE) and high-energy (HE) images after contrast agent injection. These images are subsequently recombined to highlight contrast uptake while suppressing anatomical noise. For interpretation, radiologists assess both the LE images, which are comparable to full-field digital mammography (FFDM), and the recombined images¹. As with other modalities, CEM is prone to artefacts that may degrade image quality and hinder interpretation. These artefacts, originating from patient or system factors, may affect both LE images and recombined images. While prior literature²⁻⁶ has described their appearance and causes, few studies have assessed their impact on diagnostic performance. The impact of these artefacts depends on the imaging system, clinical task, and lesion characteristics. Virtual imaging trials (VITs) offer a controlled framework to evaluate such impacts. This study investigates how two common artefacts in recombined images, breast-in-breast artefacts and motion artefacts, affect the using contrast and signal-difference-to-noise ratio (SDNR) of 5 mm non-spiculated masses in anthropomorphic breast phantoms.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Breast density and breast-in-breast artefact

Eight computational breast phantoms representing the four BI-RADS density categories were generated using the Graff model⁷. Each phantom had the same breast volume, a compressed thickness of 50 mm, and a voxel size of 50 μm . Thirteen 5 mm diameter non-spiculated masses were placed in the fully compressed central region, while an additional 12 masses were positioned near the outer breast border, with their centres located 1 cm from the edge.

3.2 Motion artefacts

Patient motion between the LE and HE acquisitions was simulated as a linear translation (0.25-1.00 mm) of the scattered breast phantoms along the x- or y-axis. Additionally, vertical displacement was simulated by imaging the phantoms at a standard compressed thickness of 50 mm for the LE image, and 50.5 mm or 51 mm for the HE image, corresponding to paddle releases of 0.5 mm and 1.0 mm, respectively. Only centrally located masses were considered in the motion artefact analysis.

3.3 CEM image simulation and analysis

LE and HE images were simulated using MC-GPU v1.5b^{8,9}, configured to replicate a Siemens MAMMOMAT B.brilliant system. Exposure parameters were matched to clinical AEC settings based on phantom measurements. The non-spiculated masses were modelled as glandular tissue mixed with various iodine concentrations: 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 mg/cm³. Recombined images were generated using research prototype software (property of Siemens) with and without motion correction. Lesion contrast and SDNR were computed using the equations below and averaged per density group and lesion location.

$$\text{contrast} = \frac{PV_{\text{mass}} - PV_{\text{background}}}{PV_{\text{background}}}, \quad \text{SDNR} = \frac{PV_{\text{mass}} - PV_{\text{background}}}{SD_{\text{background}}}$$

4. Results

4.1 Breast density and breast-in-breast artefact

Figure 1 shows the contrast and SDNR of 0.5, 1.0, and 2.0 mg/cm³ iodine masses placed centrally and peripherally, across different breast densities. Peripheral lesions consistently exhibited lower contrast and SDNR values. For instance, a 1.0 mg/cm³ lesion showed a 76% drop in contrast and a 71% drop in SDNR compared to central placement. Peripheral masses with 0.5 mg/cm³ iodine were invisible. Contrast and SDNR slightly increased with breast density, primarily due to the weighting factor applied by the offline recombination algorithm, which is optimized for clinical rather than simulated images.

The slightly increased pixel intensity at the chest wall in Figure 2 results from the phantom generation process implemented in the VICTRE pipeline⁹, where cropping extends beyond the compression surfaces, causing thickness deviations near the chest wall edge. This artefact did not impact the results, as confirmed by tests excluding the chest wall region.

Figure 1: Contrast and SNDR values across various density categories for lesions located in the central part and at the breast border ($\pm 1SD$).

Figure 2: (left) Recombined images of four breast phantoms with varying breast density, including 2 mg/cm³ iodinated non-spiculated masses. (right) Illustration of the breast phantom with some thickness variations near the chest wall.

4.2 Motion artefacts

In cases involving left-right translational motion (Figure 3), lesion contrast remains stable with or without motion correction, but SDNR drops by up to 60% without correction. With correction, SDNR remains consistent for translations up to 1 mm, indicating effective compensation of small rigid displacements. Lesions with 0.5 mg/cm³ iodine are at the detectability threshold, suggesting that the observed variations in contrast and SDNR variations are influenced by both the iodine signal and residual background contributions.

Figure 3: Lesion contrast measured in recombined images with and without motion correction, for different degrees of left-right translational motion (± 1 SD).

In cases involving chest wall–nipple translational motion (Figure 4), lesion contrast remains stable regardless of motion correction. With motion correction, SDNR is unaffected up to 1 mm translation. Without motion correction, SDNR drops by 36–44% for 1.0 mg/cm³ lesions and 22–48% for 2.0 mg/cm³ lesions. Overall, the SDNR reduction is slightly less than in the case of left-right motion, likely due to the orientation of anatomical structures within the breast phantoms.

Figure 4: Lesion contrast and SDNR measured in recombined images with and without motion correction, for different degrees of chest wall-nipple translational motion (± 1 SD).

Paddle release (Figure 5) reduces SDNR even with motion correction. Without motion correction, SDNR drops up to 49% for 1 mg/cm³ lesions and 44% for 2 mg/cm³ lesions; with motion correction, reductions are limited to 5% and 9%. As shown in Figure 6, residual artefacts persist after motion correction in paddle release cases, indicating that non-rigid motion presents a greater challenge for the algorithm to fully compensate than rigid in-plane motion.

Figure 5: Lesion contrast and SDNR measured in recombined images with and without motion correction, for different degrees of paddle release (± 1 SD).

Figure 6: Recombined images with and without motion correction of a scattered breast phantom with 1 mg/cm³ iodinated masses. Patient motion is induced by a 0.5 mm translation in the left-right direction and chest wall-nipple direction, as well as a 0.5 mm paddle release.

5. Discussion

This study examined breast-in-breast and motion artefacts in CEM images, focusing on their impact on the contrast and SDNR of 5 mm non-spiculated masses. Although no visible breast-in-breast artefact was observed, peripheral lesions showed significant reductions in contrast and SDNR, indicating potential image quality degradation and the importance of accounting for non-uniform breast thickness. Motion artefacts significantly impact lesion visibility if not corrected. Motion correction in the recombination algorithm maintained stable contrast and SDNR, highlighting the importance of effective motion correction for maintaining image quality.

While contrast and SDNR are useful metrics for assessing lesion visibility, they do not fully capture all aspects of image interpretation. CEM artefacts can also influence lesion characterization, reading time, and reader confidence. The impact of CEM artefacts depends on the imaging system and recombination algorithm, the clinical task, and lesion characteristics such as type, size, and contrast uptake. This study explored only a limited subset of these variables. Other limitations include the simplified modelling of patient motion and minor discrepancies between simulated and real-world acquisitions potentially influencing recombination performance.

6. Conclusion

This simulation study using structured backgrounds demonstrates that breast-in-breast artefact and patient motion can significantly degrade lesion contrast and SDNR in contrast-enhanced mammography, particularly for lesions located in the breast periphery and in the absence of motion correction. Virtual imaging trials proved to be a valuable tool for systematically assessing the impact of CEM artefacts, providing insights that are challenging to achieve through clinical studies or physical phantom experiments.

Acknowledgments

We gratefully acknowledge Siemens Healthineers for providing access to the offline recombination algorithm. In particular, we extend our sincere thanks to Ferdinand Lueck, Marcel Beister, Ralf Nanke, Pilar Beatriz Garcia-Allende, and Steffen Kappler for their valuable discussions and technical support.

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3D image quality and dose distribution in breast CT imaging by a GPU-accelerated virtual imaging trial

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Clinical imaging trials are adopted worldwide with the aim of testing the diagnostic power of new X-ray imaging techniques. To overcome the huge burden on time, cost and person involvement of these trials, virtual imaging trials (VITs) have been established recently, including breast imaging, as *in silico* reproductions of diagnostic exams carried out with computational methods. In this field, our group is developing the VIT-BREAST platform, a GPU-based Monte Carlo (MC) tool for breast imaging VITs. In this work we aim to realize a virtual imaging evaluation of three different breast CT (BCT) scanners in terms of image quality with glandular dose assessment.

B. METHODS

1. Simulation platform

Within the VIT-Breast platform, a GPU-based MC code, gCTD¹, was developed for replicating the geometry and X-ray spectra adopted respectively in two research (scanner 1 and 2) and one commercial (scanner 3) dedicated BCT scanners, whose main characteristics are shown in Table 1. The gCTD code, developed by the team of prof. X. Jia at Johns Hopkins University, runs under CUDA 11.6 and was executed on an NVIDIA V100 32GB graphics card. The overall processing speed was 4.3×10^8 photon histories/s.

Table 1. System parameters of simulated cone-beam BCT scanner.²

	Scanner 1	Scanner 2	Scanner 3
Focal spot size (mm)	0.4	0.3	0.3
Tube voltage (kV)	80	60	49
Added filtration	0.2 mm Cu	0.2 mm Cu	1.76 mm Al
HVL (mm Al)	5.74	1.5	1.41
Detector scintillator layer	600 μ m CsI:Tl	450 μ m CsI:Tl	600 μ m CsI:Tl
Detector pixel pitch (mm)	0.194	0.150	0.194
Detector pixel array matrix	2000 \times 1500	1933 \times 1533	2000 \times 1500
Projections per scan	350	300	300
Source-Isocenter Distance (mm)	458	458	650
Isocenter-Detector Distance (mm)	449	179	273

The gCTD code records the deposited energy in the phantom and the number of photons reaching the detector plane. The flat-panel detectors simulated include Paxscan 4030CB (Varian)³ for scanner 1 and 3, and the DEXELA 2923MAM^{4,5} for scanner 2.

2. Patient Population

Our cohort of virtual breasts included 20 anthropomorphic voxelized breast phantoms from a publicly available dataset (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4529852>)⁶. All are realistic representations of the breast anatomy, derived from patient BCT scans performed at UC Davis Medical Center after a segmentation process⁷. In 8 of these phantoms, a simulated spiculated tumor mass - obtained from the MAXIMA project dataset - was inserted computationally, using a software procedure. To simulate tumor as a radio-dense tissue, it was given the same photon interaction coefficients as glandular tissue, but with a mass density 12% higher than glandular tissue.

3. Dose Evaluation

For each simulated study, we derived the 3D map of the absorbed dose in the glandular tissue (D_g), as well as the dose in the skin (D_s), the fat (D_f) and in the whole breast (D_b). From these dose distributions we derived their mean value and the standard deviation (σ_g) for each virtual patient.

4. Image Evaluation

To achieve realistic imaging performance, we considered detector spatial resolution and efficiency, via post-processing corrections applied to the 2D photon distribution incident on the detector plane. The spatial resolution of each scanner was replicated by applying a smoothing Gaussian filter with a sigma chosen to replicate the radial MTF of the scanners, evaluated by simulating the scan of a highly absorbing thin wire. Additionally, a correction for detector efficiency was applied. From the mass attenuation coefficient of CsI derived from NIST XCOM database, we calculated the energy dependent attenuation in the detector, for each 2 keV energy bin. Moreover, the CT numbers were derived by reconstructing a simulated phantom with known inserts. These were then compared with the reference values to calibrate the three scanners. The contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) was measured in adipose and glandular tissue, to assess the impact of scatter on image quality.

C. RESULTS

1. Dose Evaluation

Figure 1a shows an example of dose histograms for Fat, Skin, Glandular and Total tissues for phantom 3 imaged with scanner 1, with 1.16×10^{10} photons/projection. We calculated the appropriate number of photons needed to simulate a scan with an MGD of 5 mGy. The average values of these distributions for each phantom were reported in fig. 1b as a function of the breast mass glandular fraction.

Fig.1: a) Fat, Skin, Glandular and Total Dose histograms for phantom 3 with Scanner 1, simulating 10^{10} photons/projection. b) Average Total, Glandular, Fat and Skin doses as a function of mass glandular fraction of the breast phantoms.

Fig. 2: Line profiles of a) Primary, and b) Primary+Scatter attenuation (I/I_0), and c) SPR, measured along a ROI at the centre of the simulated detector for Scanner 1, 2 and 3, for phantom no. 3.

2. 2D Image quality evaluation

The gCTD code permits to evaluate the contribution of primary and secondary (Compton, Rayleigh and multiple scattered) photons to image formation. As an example, for phantom 3, fig. 2 shows the attenuation (I/I_0) (fig. 2a-b) and the scatter-to-primary ratio (SPR) (fig. 2c), measured along a central ROI at the centre of the simulated detector in Scanner 1, 2 and 3. Fig. 3a-c shows the total scatter profiles along the same ROI and the contribution of the different components (Compton, Rayleigh, multiple scatter).

Fig. 3: Profiles of Total, Compton, Rayleigh and Multi scatter components measured along a central ROI at the centre of the simulated detector in Scanner 1, 2 and 3, for phantom no. 3.

2. 3D Image Evaluation

To evaluate the overall image quality, we selected phantom 3 – which includes a tumor detail – to run the simulations for the three simulated scanners. Image reconstructions were performed using the ASTRA toolbox in MATLAB. Three reconstruction scenarios were compared: using only the primary photon (fig. 4a), primary + scatter contributions (fig. 4b) and with detector MTF correction (fig. 4c). Profiles across the simulated phantom 3 in fig. 4c are shown in fig. 5.

Fig. 4: 3D image reconstruction of Phantom 3 using: a) primary photons only, or b) primary + scattered photons, or c) after applying the MTF correction procedure.

Fig. 5: Profiles across the simulated phantom 3 for scanner 1,2 and 3.

Measured tumor-glandular CNR and tumor-adipose CNR were 0.6, 0.4, and 1.3, and 1.9, 0.7, and 3.1, for scanners 1, 2, and 3, respectively.

C. DISCUSSION

The results show the capability of our proposed simulation platform to study deeply the influence of scanner characteristics on the dose and image performance. In particular, we note that the application of post-processing corrections is essential for bridging the gap between ideal simulations and clinically realistic imaging performance in BCT systems. The use of a GPU platform allowed to obtain a complete imaging and dosimetric virtual study, launching as many primary photons as to deliver an average glandular dose of about 5 mGy, in about 5 h.

D. CONCLUSION

In this work, using VIT-BREAST platform, we realized an evaluation of dose and image quality of three different breast CT scanners, using a virtual patient population of 20 health patients and 8 patients with tumor. The patient population will eventually include 50 patients.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported by Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), via the research project VITA.

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VIT-MBRT, a GPU-based virtual imaging platform dedicated to minibeam radiation therapy for preclinical research

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

X-ray minibeam radiotherapy (x-MBRT) is a preclinical radiotherapy technique that uses kilovoltage photon beams for research on spatially fractionated radiotherapy in small animals. MBRT (with photon or particle irradiation). It is characterized by a succession of high-dose (peaks) and low-dose regions (valleys). Literature evidence shows that increasing the peak-to-valley dose ratio (PVDR), can improve the therapeutic window, allowing for more effective tumor control while preserving normal tissue integrity. Other parameters playing a role in MBRT efficacy are the valley dose, peak dose, beamlet width and spacing. The potential benefits of MBRT are currently being explored in various preclinical studies. As part of a proof-of-concept Next Generation EU funded project, we are investigating geometrical and beam dosimetry parameters for MBRT in mice. We are studying different x-MBRT collimators and irradiation geometries, to determine the most effective approaches for targeting tumors. To this aim, we developed a Monte Carlo (MC) GPU-based platform (called VIT-MBRT) to reduce the simulation time with respect to CPU-based MC codes, hence providing real-time capabilities. A validation of this code is reported here.

B. METHODS

1. GPU-based code

The GPU-based dose calculation code is called gCTD^{1,2} and it is a MC code developed by the team of Prof. Xun Jia, (Johns Hopkins University). In gCTD photons are tracked through the Woodcock method³. gCTD does not simulate electron transport, but the electron kinetic energy is deposited locally at the interaction site when a secondary electron is generated after a Compton scattering or a photoelectric event. While this may not represent a major drawback for gCTD simulations when the electron range is less than the voxel size, care is due at x-MBRT energies with sub-millimeter beamlets and primary photon energies up to, e.g., 250 keV, whose electron range in water is 0.637 mm. In this work, the code (written with the CUDA toolkit) was run on a GPU card type NVIDIA GEFORCE RTX 3090Ti.

2. TOPAS code

The validation was carried out by comparing the results of tests with gCTD code and with a TOPAS (<http://topasmc.org>) version 3.9 MC code (Geant4 toolbox version 10.5.p01), previously validated⁴.

3. Setup description

We simulated the small animal irradiator X-RAD225Cx SmART (PXI, North Branford, CT, USA), operated at 225 kVp with 2 mm Be inherent and 0.3 mm Cu additional filtration, and 3.5 mm focal spot. Doses were scored in a cubic water box (2 cm)³ or in a mouse phantom, located at 25.7 cm from the source. The voxel size was 0.1 mm³. For open beam irradiation, an upstream collimator defined a field size of 1.5×1.5 cm²; for x-MBRT irradiation, a downstream tungsten multi-slit collimator, positioned at 23.3 cm from the source, determined the fractionated pattern with varied beamlet width, at a fixed center-to-center (c-t-c) distance of 1 mm between beamlets. The peak and valley doses, as well as the PVDR, were evaluated at different depths in water. The dose distribution was simulated in the following cases:

- *Open beam:* The dose distribution in the water phantom was simulated in the absence of the upstream field collimator. We compared the estimated Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) curve with the two codes, by launching 10¹¹ primary photons, resulting in a statistical uncertainty of 0.03%.
- *Multi-slit collimator:* The collimator was a 5-mm-thick W slab of 4×4 cm² with parallel slits oriented perpendicular to beam axis, with a slit width set in a range from 0.1 mm to 0.5 mm in 0.1 mm step. In this case, 2×10¹⁰ primary photons were launched, resulting in a statistical uncertainty of 0.05%.
- *Mouse phantom:* we created a voxelized mouse phantom, by segmenting the lung, skin, body, bone, and heart organs of a tumor-bearing mouse from a CT scan with our X-RAD225Cx irradiator; the phantom was incorporated into the gCTD geometry, hence deriving absorbed dose maps in the tumor and the surrounding healthy tissues.

Figure 1: Plot of central-axis PDD in the water phantom, calculated with TOPAS and gCTD codes (a), and their relative percentage difference (b).

C. RESULTS

1. Open field

For open field geometry, fig. 1 shows the PDD, measured in a 50×50 voxel region of interest (ROI) at the centre of the water phantom, for gCTD and TOPAS simulations (fig. 1a); corresponding relative differences between the datasets (fig.1b) show a mean deviation of 0.06% and a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.00148.

2. Multi-slit collimator

The dose distribution in water was estimated using the x-MBRT collimator with varied slit width and fixed c-t-c distance. Dose values in peaks and valleys were calculated with gCTD and with TOPAS, tracking a 2 × 80 pixel ROI at the centre of the phantom (Fig. 2).

3. Mouse *x*-MBRT irradiation

Figure 3 shows the gCTD simulation for the mouse model irradiated with an open beam geometry (Fig. 3a) or with a multi-slit collimator with a beamlet aperture of 0.5 mm (Fig. 3b). In both cases, 10^{11} photons were simulated; the dose absorbed in the tumor was evaluated in a spherical ROI closely embedding the tumor volume as determined from the pre-irradiation CT scan.

Figure 2: (a) Comparison of the PVDR vs. depth in water using a 5-mm thick tungsten multi-slit collimator with beam widths from 0.1 mm to 0.5 mm and *c-t-c* distance 1 mm, for TOPAS (black line) and gCTD (red line) codes; (b) corresponding relative percentage differences.

D. DISCUSSION

We introduced a new simulation platform based on gCTD^{1,2}, a GPU based Monte Carlo simulation code, to reduce the simulation time for *x*-MBRT virtual irradiations. The comparison with analogous simulations in TOPAS showed a good agreement (0.03%–5%) in PDD calculation, but with significant computational time differences (Table 1).

Figure 3: Absorbed dose maps (color coded) simulated using gCTD code, overlaid on the segmented CT image (in b/w) of the mouse phantom, in a central slice through the tumor volume (circled in white), calculated in the open beam configuration (a) and in MBRT configuration with beamlets width 0.5 mm and c-t-c distance 1 mm (b).

Table 1: Summary of the simulation setup used for the two codes, showing differences in overall computation time with varied number of primary photons.

Simulation code	Computer hardware	Computing time (s)			Ratio of computing times		
		10^9 photons	10^{10} photons	10^{11} photons	10^9 phot.	10^{10} phot.	10^{11} phot.
TOPAS	2 x AMD EPYC 7281, 2.2 GHz, 32-Core Processors, 256 GB RAM	4512.11	46050.00	305037.00	288	333	298
gCTD	NVIDIA GeForce RTX™ 3090Ti	15.66	138.20	1025.01			

E. CONCLUSION

Within the VIT-MBRT platform, we validated the GPU-based MC simulation code gCTD against TOPAS simulations, for virtual irradiations in minibeam kilovoltage radiotherapy. We showed that, compared to a TOPAS CPU based code, the gCTD code may reduce the overall computing time by a factor of up to about 300, with statistical uncertainty of 0.05%.

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1022-Horizon scanning of virtual clinical trial platforms and digital twins in Italy

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The AIFM4VCT working group of the Italian Association of Medical Physics (AIFM) was established to foster networking and advance the development and application of in-silico frameworks and digital twins in Virtual Imaging Trials (VITs) in medicine. We conducted a horizon scanning of the state of the art in the implementation of VITs in Italy. The review specifically focuses on the development of virtual platforms and digital twins, and their role in VITs, highlighting their application fields: diagnostic radiology, nuclear medicine, and radiotherapy.

A literature search including the last 5 years was carried out by independent researchers from the AIFM4VCT group. Specific keywords (Italy as affiliation/digital phantom/computer-generated model/simulated phantom/in-silico medicine/virtual imaging/computational twin) were employed in freely available literature databases. The selected research topics covered: analysis of diagnostic and screening modalities; therapies and personalized medicine; development and implementation of 3D digital phantoms (e.g., for single organs, anatomical districts, and pathologies); related application of artificial intelligence tools.

About 80 original papers were collected, including research and conference papers, reviews, and technical notes. The papers were stratified based on the anatomical district (breast, abdomen, chest, etc.) and application. The studies were analyzed and discussed in terms of strengths and weaknesses across all application fields. The review underlined a growing interest of the medical physics community in the development of VIT platforms and their potential impact in clinical settings. However, especially in nuclear medicine, VITs are still in their early stages, but hold significant potential in revolutionizing personalized medicine, improving patient outcomes, and transforming healthcare delivery. The need for stakeholders, validation, and standardization approaches is evident, as well as the need to engage legislative bodies in the adoption of in-silico tests supporting medical device development and clinical decisions.

VITA: The Italian AIFM, INFN, and ISS scientific collaboration towards a national center for virtual imaging trials

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

The development of Virtual Imaging Trials (VITs) is gaining importance due to their potential benefits, leveraging the increasing availability of massive hardware and software computing power. Several international initiatives have emerged, primarily in the USA. Examples are the VICTRE (Virtual Imaging Clinical Trials for Regulatory Evaluation) project¹, which compares the performance of digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) against digital mammography (DM) for breasts with different anatomical characteristics, and the Center for Virtual Imaging Trials at Duke University² aiming to accelerate and enhance the evaluation and optimization of imaging technologies, promoting precise design and effective use of imaging in patient-centred care.

In Italy, various research groups are working on VIT topics. The Italian Association of Medical Physics (AIFM) has established a working group on VITs to promote collaboration among hospital initiatives; the INFN (National Institute for Nuclear Physics) community is participating in Spoke 8 "In Silico Medicine and Omics Data" within the PNRR ICSC National Center for HPC, Big Data, and Quantum Computing project, aiming to provide high computing and storage capacities for biomedical solutions. Moreover, through such Next Generation EU funding, INFN is laying the foundations for a future National Computing Center with a special focus on medical applications such as Virtual Imaging Trials.

Based on these activities, the new three-year VITA project, funded by INFN, aims to unify various independent research efforts by INFN, AIFM, and ISS, laying the groundwork for a future National Centre dedicated to VITs in Italy. We present here the design and first results of this project.

B. VITA Infrastructure

Figure 1b shows the design of the VITA infrastructure. A central node is in Bologna at INFN CNAF where the INFN deployed an open-source, highly secure, GDPR-compliant, ISO/IEC 27001-certified cloud computing platform for Big Data management and AI in all research fields requiring sensitive data management. The platform, named EPIC (Enhanced Privacy and Compliance) Cloud is being extended to include by the end of 2025 two further INFN datacenters located in

Bari and Catania. The IaaS level allows access to a broad pool of resources including CPUs, GPUs, HPC clusters and several storage types to address different needs and trade-off between speed and costs. This structure will be accessible to clinical users and software developers through XNAT software platform (xnat.org). XNAT (fig.1a) is an open-source imaging informatics platform developed by Neuroinformatics Research Group at Washington University, dedicated to managing importing, archiving, processing and securely distributing imaging and related study data. At moment, 6 operating nodes are planned on the VITA infrastructure

Figure 1: a) Operating diagram of XNAT imaging software platform and b) schema of VITA infrastructure.

C. VITA NODES

Operating node 1 – INFN Napoli Medical Physics group (Napoli)

The INFN Naples Medical Physics group developed the VIT-BREAST platform for 2D and 3D imaging and dosimetry in breast cancer diagnosis, using Monte Carlo (MC) simulations. The platform is based on a Geant4 MC code³, for simulation of DM, DBT, and BCT imaging exams, also providing 3D maps of glandular dose distribution⁴ (fig. 2a,b). The group is now developing a new platform, called VIT-OSTEO, for virtual high-resolution cone-beam CT exams of the knee and other skeletal districts, and for bone densitometry scans, including dosimetry estimates, in the framework of radiological osteoporosis diagnosis (fig. 2c,d).

Figure 2: Examples of (a) CT imaging, and (b) corresponding dose distribution map of a female breast with the VIT-BREAST platform, and with the VIT-OSTEO platform for (c) CT imaging, and (d) dose map in a bone densitometry virtual scan.

Operating node 2 – Center for Oncologic Research (Aviano)

CRO Aviano performs simulation of radiotherapy hypofractionation trials by rescaling of CT-calculated dose distribution among patient cohorts and applying NTCP and TCP models in order to choose optimal fractionation scheme. In silico simulation of radiotherapy techniques in order to select best treatment approach, eg. deep inspiration breath-hold against free breathing breast cancer radiotherapy, are conducted. An ongoing study in collaboration with the Machine Learning and Perception Lab of the Udine University is evaluating the generation of synthetic images for radiotherapy dose calculation.

Operating node 3 – Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria Città della Salute e della Scienza (Torino)

The Medical Physics group of the AOU Città della Salute e della Scienza in Turin has significant experience in the optimization of CT protocols and in quantitative and radiomic analysis of diagnostic images. This university hospital has contributed to the creation of a public database called “unitochest”⁵ in which more than 10k pulmonary nodules of 623 different patients are segmented in CT images.

Operating node 4 – Istituto Superiore di Sanità (Roma)

At the ISS-National Center for Radiation Protection and Computational Physics, in-silico medicine activities are conducted using Monte Carlo techniques for medical applications. The ISS is involved in the "Developing a Metrological Framework

for Assessment of Image-Based Artificial Intelligence Systems for Disease Detection" project, which evaluates AI techniques for breast cancer diagnosis⁶.

Operating node 5 – Azienda Provinciale per i Servizi Sanitari (Trento)

At the APSS, two main research lines are active. The first involves vascular surgery within the TANGO project, in collaboration with the University of Trento, where a database of pre- and post-operative CT scans of patients undergoing surgical treatment for abdominal aortic aneurysm correction is being collected. Based on these data researchers at APSS in Trento developed AI-based tools for AAA surgical planning⁷.

The second line focuses on neurosurgery, supporting surgeons in brain tumor interventions, both for preoperative planning and intraoperative guidance. A database of pre-analyzed T1, fMRI, and DWI MRI images is available. AI-based tools for pediatric MRI brain tissue segmentation, focusing on malformations, were also developed⁸.

Operating node 6 – Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria Integrata (Verona), Medical Physics Unit

The Medical Physics unit of AOUI in Verona has a strong experience in the use of AI applied in particular to Breast MRI⁹⁻¹¹. Two artificial intelligence algorithms were developed to support the complete workflow for predicting response to neoadjuvant therapy in breast cancer patients, starting from baseline MRI acquired with (Dynamic Contrast Enhanced) DCE technique.

Figure 3: This is the caption of a figure, should be central below the figure.

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1024-Model free atlas An efficient learnable atlas construction scheme

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Deformable templates (atlas), which utilize geometric deformations to align images within a dataset, play a pivotal role in medical image analysis and computational anatomy. Traditional atlas creation involves iterative pairwise 3D image registration, a process that demands significant computational resources. In contrast, deep learning-based approaches accelerate template generation by leveraging neural networks to learn data distributions, yet they often suffer from uncertainties in feature abstraction and potential model biases. To address these challenges, we propose an iterative optimization framework for learnable atlas construction. Our approach begins with an efficient registration scheme that relies solely on learnable parameters: by using gradient descent to optimize deformation fields, we achieve effective registration between the atlas and samples without resorting to neural network-based feature extraction. Although gradient descent methods are inherently limited by batch size constraints, we overcome this limitation by iteratively updating the atlas—refining it in each iteration by averaging the optimally warped images computed over the entire dataset. Additionally, we incorporate a novel unbiased activation function that ensures template neutrality by constraining the average deformation field to zero, thereby eliminating the need for explicit unbiasedness optimization in the loss function.

A validated Monte Carlo platform for virtual imaging with a CdTe compact gamma camera

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Compact, small field of view (SFOV) gamma cameras (GCs) are compact, handheld nuclear medicine gamma-ray imaging devices used for pre-, intra-operative, and diagnostic imaging clinical procedures, such as sentinel lymph node (SLN) biopsy or thyroid scintigraphy, and radio-guided surgery¹. ^{99m}Tc is commonly used also in SLN imaging in oncologic surgery, with injected activity ranging from 3.7 MBq (melanoma) to 370 MBq (breast cancer)². Detectors in SFOV GCs are based on either a semiconductor sensor (such as CdTe or CdZnTe) or a scintillator crystal. Metal collimators commonly adopted include parallel hole or pinhole geometry, but also diverging collimators and coded aperture (CA) masks have been employed. Reportedly¹, extrinsic sensitivity of SFOV GCs at collimator surface can be in the order of hundreds of cps/MBq, with extrinsic lateral spatial resolution in the order of a few mm and field of view (FOV) in the order of 50 mm by side.

In past years, the University & INFN Napoli group developed the MediPROBE2 SFOV GC, equipped with a coded aperture (CA) or pinhole collimator, based on a 1-mm-thick semiconductor CdTe sensor, read out by a Medipix2 (photon counting) or Timepix2 (photon counting and energy sensitive) CMOS readout ASICs³. That group is now developing a new SFOV GC, called MediPROBE4⁴, based on the recently released Timepix4 ASIC⁵ (<https://medipix.web.cern.ch/medipix4>) and a 2-mm-thick CdTe pixel detector. In this work, we report on the development of a digital twin of MediPROBE4 SFOV GC equipped with a CA or pinhole collimator, based on a Monte Carlo (MC) simulator, useful for device performance assessment and virtual imaging trials in nuclear medicine tasks with SFOV GCs. Here we tested the extension of the simulation code gCTD, originally developed for radiology and radiotherapy applications, to virtual imaging trials (VITs) in specific gamma-ray imaging tasks with CGCs.

B. METHODS

We computationally reproduced the MediPROBE4 SFOV GC by creating a model of the CA collimator and the detector (a 2-mm-thick CdTe pixel detector). Such an assembly was tested virtually for imaging of point-like and extended radioactive sources. Monte Carlo (MC) simulations of the detector response were carried out using the GEANT4 toolkit (physics list low energy opt4). Then, MC simulations of gamma-ray acquisitions with MediPROBE4 were carried out using the graphical processing unit (GPU) accelerated gCTD code⁶. GPU-based simulations were run on an NVIDIA RTX 3090Ti graphics card.

The simulated CA mask is a modified uniformly redundant array (MURA), no two holes touching (NTHT) mask of rank-31, which we realized physically by electrodischarge machining of as many as 1920 round apertures of 0.25 mm diameter. The digital model of this collimator contains square (not round) apertures. We created a voxelized tissue phantom of 8 cm × 8 cm × 10.1 cm size, containing a 6-cm-thick water slab, a 4-cm-thick air slab, and the 1-mm-thick CA collimator. The Timepix4 detector was modeled as a 2-mm-thick CdTe pixelated sensor of 448 × 512 pixels with a pixel pitch of 0.055 mm. We simulated the CdTe detector response with Geant4 since, at variance with the gCTD code, it tracks electrons and generates fluorescence photons in the detector. The electronic readout chip was not included in the simulations. Once the CdTe detector response (spatial resolution, energy sensitivity, intrinsic detection efficiency) was modeled from CPU-based GEANT4 MC simulations, we used the gCTD MC code to propagate the gamma-rays from the source to the detector.

Figure 1 a) Physical CA mask. b) Timepix4 assembly. c) Geometric configuration for virtual tests of the MediPROBE4 CGC.

Raw images were fed to a reconstruction code written in MATLAB for CA decoding via autocorrelation. We virtually tested the collimator-detector assembly for several geometries of the ^{99m}Tc source(s), emitting 140.5 keV photons isotropically. *In silico* monoenergetic sources were positioned in a water phantom (Figure 1), with the following geometries (SCD = source to collimator-face distance):

- i) Point-like source centered in the FOV, SCD = 8 cm, 4 cm depth in water (2.1 MBq),
- ii) Cubic source of 10-mm-side centered in the FOV, SCD = 8 cm, 4 cm depth in water (2.1 MBq),
- iii) Cubic source of 7-mm-side placed laterally 1 cm off center, SCD = 6 cm (6 MBq),
- iv) Cubic source of 8-mm-side placed laterally 0.5 cm off center, SCD = 7 cm (10 MBq)
- v) Superposition of two extended sources in the FOV, obtained as the sum of raw images from *iii*) and *iv*)

We quantified image quality by computing the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), as the ratio of the mean value of the signal (μ) in a small region of interest around the source image, to the standard deviation (σ) of the background.

C. RESULTS

Reconstructed images in configurations *i*) and *ii*) showed high SNR values (Figure 2a,b). For configuration *v*) we observed two well-separated sources with $\text{SNR} > 7$ (Figure 2c). While the size and planar location (x - y plane) of all sources were correctly reconstructed, roughly at the expected distance from the source. Each simulation required 5–200 s to run (GPU-time < 3 s, plus file saving time), from 10^7 to 10^9 primary photons. Image reconstruction required < 20 ms per image. The total time required to obtain a decoded image was therefore below 4 minutes, not including the time needed to simulate the detector response in Geant4, only performed once.

D. DISCUSSION

The analysis of decoded images showed an SNR adequate for the localization of extended 3D sources of up to 10 mm linear size. In every reconstruction, the source was clearly distinguished from the background and correctly located in the x - y plane. The size of reconstructed sources matched their actual dimension. Results showed a lateral spatial resolution adequate for localizing two extended sources placed 2 cm apart. Apart from an observed fixed offset to be investigated further, the axial position of the source was reconstructed with a longitudinal resolution less than 10 mm.

The virtual imaging tests of the MediPROBE4 CGC here presented, show the capability to correctly reconstruct in 3D an image of a 2.1 MBq source with a virtual acquisition time of 1 s, at 6-cm depth in water and SCD = 8 cm.

The gCTD GPU-based Monte Carlo code was used here for the first time for simulating nuclear imaging tests with CGCs. This tool produced a simulation of the MediPROBE4 CGC in real time, showing dramatically improved time performance compared to a previously developed MC platform based on GEANT4⁴ (which required 5–7 h computing time to obtain a raw image for the same simulated source).

Figure 2 Decoded simulated images of ^{99m}Tc sources in different geometrical configurations (a,b) immersed in a water phantom, with the CA mask at 2 cm from the water surface. In c), we simulated two sources of different activity, size, and depth in water; the system sensitivity (380 cps/MBq) was calculated after background subtraction and accounting for the 2-mm-thick CdTe intrinsic detection efficiency of 55% at 140.5 keV.

E. CONCLUSION

We presented a tool (VIT-CGC) for virtual imaging trials for CGCs, which contains the first application of the gCTD GPU-based simulation code to nuclear medicine CGC imaging. Integrating this tool with a Geant4-based simulation of the CdTe sensor, we developed a comprehensive MC simulation platform. VIT-CGC can be adopted for the performance assessment and optimization of the detector and collimator setup. We are implementing VIT-CGC with a dataset of test objects and anthropomorphic phantoms for nuclear medicine tasks with CGC.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work contributes to the activities of the two projects VITA (Virtual Imaging TriAls) and MEDIPIX4, funded by INFN, Italy. The authors do not have any conflicts of interest to disclose.

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VIT-OSTEO: a GPU-based imaging and dosimetry simulation platform for HR-pQCT and DXA virtual scans in bone health diagnosis

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

In diagnostic radiology, virtual models are available for mammography, breast tomosynthesis, angiography and computed tomography (CT) including breast CT¹. In this framework, in addition to breast imaging² and nuclear medicine imaging³, our group has been developing virtual imaging trial (VIT) tools for bone imaging, including the digital twinning of dual energy X-Ray absorptiometry (DXA) and high resolution peripheral quantitative CT (HR-pQCT) scanners⁴. DXA and HR-pQCT are two modalities dedicated to musculoskeletal imaging. DXA is used for bone densitometry as it measures areal bone mineral density, aBMD, in osteoporosis diagnosis. HR-pQCT is a CT technique to assess volumetric bone mineral density (vBMD) and bone microarchitecture in the epiphysis of long bones (e.g., the distal tibia and the radius). This work complements the companion VIT tools for breast imaging² (VIT-BREAST) and for CGC imaging (VIT-CGC), with a new tool for bone imaging (called VIT-OSTEO). Here we present virtual twins for a DXA and a HR-pQCT clinical scanner, representing first implementations for this platform, and related anthropomorphic voxelized digital phantoms.

B. METHODS

VIT-OSTEO is based on GPU-accelerated Monte Carlo (MC) simulations with voxelized phantoms, using geometrical, spectral and irradiation parameters adopted in two commercial scanners: a DXA and an HR-pQCT scanner. The MC code is a dedicated version of the validated gCTD code. Simulations provide both imaging projections and 3D absorbed dose maps, then processed for aBMD assessment (DXA) and HR-pQCT dataset reconstruction. A graphical user interface (under development) inputs the scan parameters to gCTD to simulate the scanner of choice. Detector response (energy-integrating for HR-pQCT, and photon-counting mode for DXA) was assessed with separate GEANT4 based MC simulations, providing a model of the detector response used to convert the simulated incident photon fluence map onto the detector surface, into the imaging detector’s response. The number of photon histories in each virtual scan ($3\text{-}5 \times 10^{11}$ histories) produces an incident photon fluence matched to that measured in a clinical scan, hence producing realistic quantum noise in the image and organ doses, with a statistical uncertainty $< 1\%$ and a GPU computational speed exceeding 10^9 histories per second.

We created a digital twin of the GE Healthcare Lunar iDXA scanner by reproducing its raster scanning geometry (transversal scan from left to right, followed by a longitudinal translation in the head-to-toe direction, see Figure 1a,b), a narrow cone beam (4.5° aperture) and a photon counting CdTe detector (64×2 pixels, 1-mm-thick sensor). We used a 100 kVp spectrum (Figure 1c) with filtration 1.89 mm Aluminum and 0.200 mm Samarium (K-edge, 46.83 keV). We realized a voxelized version of the QRM DXA Spine QA phantom, 3HA (QRM, Germany). We also developed an anthropomorphic computational phantom of the lumbar spine, derived from segmented whole-body CT images⁵. We obtained a digital twin of the XtremeCT II HR-pQCT scanner (Scanco Medical AG, Switzerland) by replicating its scanning geometry (Figure 1d) (202° scan angle, 1011 projections, narrow cone beam irradiation, single rotation with no axial translation), its detector

(0.088-mm thick CsI:Tl detector, 221×19 mm, 0.048 mm pixel pitch) and its 68 kVp X-ray spectrum (68 kVp, inherent filtration 1 mm Al, added filtration 0.2 mm Cu and 0.3 mm Be, reproduced with SpekPy⁶, Figure 1e). Voxelized phantoms of the distal tibia and radius were obtained by segmenting original HR-pQCT scans. Simulations were performed using the GPU-based code, gCTD³. This MC code was run on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 graphic card embedded in a DELL Aurora R11 desktop computer (Intel i9-10900KF, 3.70 GHz, 128 GB RAM). With these virtual scanners, we simulated a DXA examination of the lumbar spine and an HR-pQCT scan of the tibia and radius.

Figure 1 a) and b) show the raster geometry used by the GE Lunar iDXA scanner. c) X-Ray spectrum inserted in the MC simulation (100 kVp, filtration of 2.5 mm Al, 0.2 mm Sm for k-edge filtration). d) Irradiation geometry used by the HR-pQCT scanner. e) X-Ray spectrum for HR-pQCT simulations.

C. RESULTS

We digitally reproduced the DXA scan of the QA Lumbar Spine phantom, obtaining the 3D map of absorbed dose in the phantom (Figure 2a) from which we derived the mean absorbed dose in the vertebrae (1.6 ± 0.9 mGy) and in the soft tissue (0.85 ± 0.25 mGy). We also obtained projection images in two energy channels (Figure 2b), from which the aBMD can be computed. From MC simulation of HR-pQCT we obtained a 3D absorbed dose distribution within the phantom (Figure 3a), used for calculating mean absorbed dose in tissues (bone, fat, muscle, skin and bone marrow) and effective dose for the HR-pQCT scan. This was about 2 μ Sv for the tibia and 1.5 μ Sv for the radius, with an overall uncertainty of 40%. Simulated image projections were binned (2×2) and filtered back projection CT reconstruction (Figure 3b). No bone-specific reconstruction kernel was used for reconstruction.

D. DISCUSSION

Effective dose estimates for the HR-pQCT scans were lower than reported in the literature (3–5 μ Sv). Raw CT reconstructions from the VIT-OSTEO platform shows lower spatial resolution compared to clinical HR-pQCT images. The VIT-OSTEO platform will also be adopted for device design specification and virtual performance assessment of a compact DXA unit for distal tibia scans with photon counting detectors (DXA4A), dedicated to astronauts' bone health imaging during spaceflights, currently under development⁷.

E. CONCLUSION

We presented a new research tool for VITs for bone imaging, called VIT-OSTEO, capable of replicating computationally the clinical units for HR-pQCT and DXA patient scans. The tool is based on a GPU-accelerated MC code with real-time performance, delivering imaging datasets and organ absorbed dose maps. Digital twins of the XtremeCT II HR-pQCT and GE Lunar iDXA scanners have been developed, coupled to voxelized phantoms of anatomical and quality assurance test objects.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work contributes to the activities of the projects VITA and MEDIPIX4, funded by INFN, Italy. The authors acknowledge Jan Dudak (IEAP CTU, Prague, Czech Republic) for providing the CT reconstruction image using the VGSTUDIO MAX software. The authors do not have any conflicts of interest to disclose. HR-pQCT scan of a volunteer used for this work was approved by the University of Calgary Health Ethics Board within the CaBHS study.

DXA scan MC simulation

Figure 2 a) Orthogonal views of the 3D absorbed dose map (mGy) in the QRM QA Lumbar Spine phantom (4.9×10^{11} primaries). b) DXA image obtained by raster geometry scanning with a digital twin of the GE Lunar iDXA; high- and low-energy photons were separated at the detector. c) Coronal and axial views of the 3D absorbed dose map (μGy) in the anthropomorphic phantom (3×10^{11} primaries). d) Coronal and axial views of the voxelized anthropomorphic phantom.

HR-pQCT MC simulation

Figure 3 a) Orthogonal views of the 3D absorbed dose map (in mGy) in a central slice of the left tibia, for a virtual HR-pQCT scan (XtremeCT, Scanco Medical). b) Corresponding CT reconstructed slices obtained from 1011 simulated projections over 202° scan angle, obtained via filtered back projection. The dose map shows the high absorption in compact and trabecular bone, and the different absorbed dose between fat, muscle and skin tissues. Simulated photon histories exceeding 10^{11} .

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Synthetic Computed Tomography Pulmonary Nodule Generation: a New Methodology Based on Technical and Clinical Domain Knowledge

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Reliable diagnosis and clinical management of pulmonary nodules (PN) in patients is paramount for potential lung cancer patients.¹ X-ray Computed tomography (CT) is a standard imaging technique used to detect and classify PN.² Recently, various deep learning techniques have been proposed to automate PN classification based on CT imaging.^{3,4} These methods require a substantial amount of images, annotated by clinicians, in order to train neural networks. However, especially for PN and their various morphologies, training datasets might at times be scarce, ambiguously annotated, or difficult to obtain in the clinics.

In this paper, we introduce a new methodology to generate synthetic CT PN data, which generates realistic artificial images based on a 3D tissue modeling and CT scan simulation pipeline, wherein permutations of modeled PN features can be parametrized. The resulting CT images, stored in Dicom files, can be representative at pixel-level, and also richly annotated at scale. Domain knowledge is explicitly used to underpin our data generators, resulting if needed also in synthetic data for rare edge cases with reliable feature annotations, which can in turn be used to enhance the training of machine learning PN classifiers.

We use as real-images reference the LIDC-IDRI database,⁵ which contains expert radiologist annotations of a) accurate border segmentation of nodules, and b) 9 labels per nodule (7 quantifying morphological shape and texture features of the nodule, and 2 considered clinically interpretive). To compare the CT image data between real and synthetic nodules, we currently focus on the “spiculation” morphology feature, which we use as a label to train an ResNet18 deep network. Our current focus on spiculation is due to it being one of the main signs of malignancy for lung nodules.⁶ However, our methodology procedurally generates the synthetic PN CT data based on parametrizing the full set of seven morphological features: lobulation, spiculation, sphericity, texture, margin, internal structure and calcification.

B. METHODS

At the core of our synthetic CT PN generation pipeline is the ability to parametrically define 3D geometries. The parametric interface to our nodule generator employs all 7 morphological features from the LIDC-IDRI dataset as well as a size and volume input. Each feature is programmatically defined. For spiculation, this means we can drive the morphology of the 3D structure to generate increasingly irregular surfaces. Our generators are pseudo-random models: by changing a seed value, a new permutation of a nodule is generated while maintaining all input features (figure 1).

An in-house developed CT solver ingests the generated 3D geometry and produces the synthetic Dicom slices. We are focusing the generation pipeline on nodule morphology, and not yet on the surrounding tissue, at this stage. Iterative development to increase the quality of the synthetic PN images is done also thanks to the feedback from a radiology domain expert.

Figure 1 - Left: a nodule from the LIDC-IDRI database. Right: permutations of synthetic CT pulmonary nodules generated with our methodology, using the same input features as the real nodule annotations, but changing seed value.

To compare our synthetic dataset to the LIDC-IDRI dataset, we use a ResNet18 model to process pixel-data from 2D cropped nodules: 80x80mm in the slice with the largest nodule section area. We augmented the dataset by rotating and flipping the cropped nodules. Additional inputs for the classifier were also nodule sizes and volumes. ResNet was chosen as network architecture due to its widespread use in similar tasks.³ We trained the ResNet18 (Huber loss) on pixel data of 840 real LIDC-IDRI unique nodules, relying on human annotations for spiculation as ground truth. The trained ResNet18 model was then used as a regression model to infer the spiculation values of 102 synthetically generated nodules, cropped within the central 2D slice of each PN. In this way we get non-integer estimates for spiculation as output, which allow us to quantify precisely the actual model-output deviation from the discrete and ordinal ground truth.

C. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the estimates for spiculation on synthetic CT PN images by the ResNet18 model trained on real-image data. The ground truth in this case is represented by the spiculation values that were imposed as inputs in the synthetic generation pipeline.

Figure 2 - Spiculation regression for synthetic data. ResNet18 trained on real LIDC-IDRI nodules, then inferring on synthetic data. On the horizontal axis, spiculation values used as input parameters to the synthetic pipeline.

D. DISCUSSION

We have hereby presented our methodology for generating and analyzing synthetic PN data. The results show how the regressed and pre-determined spiculation values correlate fairly well for the synthetic nodules we generated. Deviation in estimated spiculation can still be noticed though, which might be related to the fact that the real images we used to train the ResNet18 model contain noise and tissue structures external to the nodule that we don't yet fully simulate in our pipeline. In addition, the spiculation feature was not represented in a balanced way within the LIDC-IDRI dataset. In the future, we plan to extend the capabilities of our simulation pipeline also to more precisely represent the tissues surrounding the nodules. This will in turn allow us to improve the realism of our data generation. Furthermore, as already mentioned, the current focus of this paper is on spiculation. However, in future works, we could extend real-vs-synthetic PN comparisons to various other nodule features as well. And on the CT imaging simulation side, we also could extend our CT solver to integrate detailed information from various scanner vendors regarding imaging system specifications.

E. CONCLUSION

Our methodology introduces a new deterministic, expert-informed synthetic data generation pipeline that can enhance machine learning applications in medical imaging, paving the way for new, explainable diagnostic tools. This controllable, explainable pipeline can generate wide variations of anatomies and pulmonary nodules, resulting in representative, richly annotated synthetic CT datasets at scale. Therefore, offering a solution to overcome possible data scarcity in clinical applications by means of the engineering of a synthetic dataset that could capture rare edge cases whenever needed. This is possible thanks to the fact that permutations of nodule morphological features can be fully parametrized at the data generation stage. In addition, rich annotations, including pixel/voxel precise segmentation of PN boundaries, are natively available from the synthetic datasets.

Our methodology can also enable the development of more explainable AI models. Further directions could also entail extending the scope of this work to other PN morphological features, and even to PN malignancy scores. Moreover, generation of specific histological subtypes of nodules such as adenocarcinomas, sarcoidosis, lymphoma, and more, could also be planned. Which in turn could further enhance the training options for deep learning algorithms.

It is worth noting that, in addition to CT pulmonary nodules, our synthetic data generation methodology can be extended to a plethora of diverse organ, pathology, and medical imaging combinations. For instance, given adequate input parameters or features, vascular structures and pathologies imaged with magnetic resonance scanners could also be generated synthetically. This is one of the main benefits of a deterministic approach for synthetic data production based on technical and clinical domain-knowledge.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

No conflict of interest to declare.

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Development of a Model Observer for CT Protocol Optimization based on a Virtual Phantom

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

The study of the applicability of virtual phantoms for CT protocol optimization procedures gains increasing interest. Traditionally, such procedures involve the use of physical phantoms to evaluate CT image quality as a function of dose by means of the receiving operator characteristic (ROC) analysis. Recently, algorithmic approaches, such as model observers (MO) based on Artificial Intelligence, have been developed to substitute human observers (i.e. experienced radiologists to evaluate a large number of images).

The aim of this work is a preliminary investigation on the potential replacement of physical phantoms with virtual phantoms by comparing the present results with those obtained in a previous study of ours based on an appropriate physical phantom and a MO developed by means of a UNet neural network [1,2].

To this purpose a virtual twin of the physical phantom was realized. The DukeSim [3] software was adopted to simulate the actual CT scanner as well as the acquisition protocol in order to set up a virtual images dataset as close as possible to the real one previously acquired.

B. METHODS

1. Physical phantom

An elliptical (31x21x10cm) PMMA phantom containing 10 cylindrical inserts with diameters 3,4,5,6 and 7 mm was designed and manufactured. Inserts were filled with iodinated contrast media at specific concentrations in order to obtain -45HU and -55HU contrasts with respect to PMMA background at 120 kV.

2. Source domain and Model observer

A dataset of 30,000 images including 8 volumetric CT Dose Index settings (CTDI) was collected with a 128 slice CT scanner (Somatom Definition Flash, Siemens Healthcare) using an abdomen protocol (120 kVp, AEC on, helical mode, pitch=1, beam collimation=38.4 mm, slice thickness=2 mm). Filtered back projection reconstruction was performed with B41s kernel and 5x5cm² FoV (512x512pixel) [1,2].

The characteristics of the MO adopted to reproduce the performances of human observers in detecting low contrast objects in CT phantom images are described in [1,2].

MO performances were addressed in terms of the Area Under the Localization-ROC Curve (L-AUC) as a function of CTDI [1,2].

3. Virtual phantom

The virtual twin of our previous PMMA phantom was designed in a voxelized version (0.25x0.25x0.25mm voxels) [3]. The inserts contrast of the real phantom was reproduced in the virtual one simply by assigning to the virtual PMMA material an appropriate density within the inserts (i.e. 1.1395g/cm³ for a -45 HU contrast).

4. Virtual images dataset

The adopted approach consisted in evaluating the performances of the previously trained MO on a test dataset of virtual images that are possibly exact twins of the real images used in our previous work.

Therefore, DukeSim was set to reproduce the same scanner and acquisition protocol used for the real images.

DukeSim tube current and current modulation parameters [4] were optimized to obtain, for each of the 8 CTDI values, an equivalent noise (i.e. a difference of the noise standard deviation <1HU) as well as a consistent 2-D noise spectrum (i.e. structural similarity index between noise spectra ≥ 0.5 , Fig. 1). In Fig. 2 a large FoV image of the real phantom compared with the virtual one is shown.

Figure 1. Noise spectra of real and virtual images

Figure 2 Example of a large FoV image of the real phantom (left) and of the virtual one (right).

The Siemens reconstruction software ReconCT, previously used for the real images, was also used for the virtual images in order to properly replicate reconstruction kernel, image size, reconstruction FoV and slice thickness. The FoV center coordinates were calculated from the DICOM metadata of the twin real images.

A dataset of ~4400 images of 5x5cm² FoV for the 8 CTDI values was obtained, ~2800 of them containing the 4mm or the 7mm insert, and ~1600 containing only bulk PMMA (background).

C. RESULTS

In Fig. 3 L-AUC is reported as a function of CTDI for real and virtual phantom images for both 4mm and 7mm inserts (orange and green curves). A comparison of the histograms of the real and virtual images (not reported here), showing in many cases a clear displacement of the virtual images average due to a few outlier pixels with high HU

values, suggested the introduction of an image preprocessing, consisting in rescaling pixel values so that their mean and 5-95 percentile interval matched those of the twin real images. A 3x3pixel smoothing was also added before the input to the MO (purple curve).

L-AUC curves computed for human observers are also reported for reference (dashed blue curves) [1,2].

Figure 3. L-AUC vs. CTDI for the images subsets containing the 4mm and 7mm inserts (left and right panels respectively)

D. DISCUSSION

L-AUC curves show that MO had different output statistics between virtual and real images. It is worth noting that the drop in performance when the MO is trained on real images (source domain) and tested on virtual ones (target domain) is a well-known issue in machine learning, referred to as domain gap. This problem arises because neural networks tend to converge on domain-specific solutions and it becomes particularly critical when the target domain is unlabeled or sparsely labeled. In other words, a UNet-based MO could be highly sensitive to the differences between real and virtual images. In Fig. 4 some examples are shown in which the MO correctly detected the insert in the real image but failed in the virtual twin.

Figure 4. Examples of images in which the MO correctly detected the insert in the real image but failed in the virtual twin.

Even though virtual images were closely resembling the real ones as for noise standard deviation, noise spectrum and inserts contrast, the MO is unveiling subtle differences in the structure/noise pattern of virtual images, as it can

be noticed by the differences evident in Fig. 3. More in-depth investigations such as radiomic analysis could surely help in understanding the aspects that affect the MO performances and the quality of the virtual dataset. On the other hand, the increase of L-AUCs when adding the extra preprocessing step tell us that this extremely simple domain adaptation can significantly improve the MO performances. Finally, it is important to observe that, despite the yet poor predictive performances, the L-AUC curves reveal that MO is able to distinguish between different doses and insert diameters and ultimately between CT protocols. Domain adaptation techniques, such as domain adversarial training, which promotes the extraction of domain-invariant features, could be employed to improve the MO performances.

E. CONCLUSION

Preliminary results suggest that the output statistics of an AI-based MO trained on real phantom images are adversely affected when tested on virtual images, though generated using state-of-the-art CT image simulation software. This finding indicates that the MO may be sensitive to subtle differences in image characteristics between real and simulated datasets. Further investigation through advanced radiomic analyses may help to elucidate the nature and impact of these discrepancies. Future work will include additional image quality assessment techniques, such as the evaluation of the detectability index and annotation of virtual datasets by trained human observers. These steps will be essential to enhance our understanding of the capabilities of AI-based MOs in CT protocol optimization and to identify necessary improvements in simulation methodologies. Nevertheless, the ability to distinguish between doses and insert diameters tells us that the use of AI-based MO together with virtual images for CT protocol optimization is still promising.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the NIH, P41EB028744 through the collaboration between our group and CVIT. The authors declare no other conflict of interest.

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From photon interactions to patient image: an in-silico pipeline for designing and optimising new clinical photon counting computed tomography systems

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Photon counting (PC) is an x-ray imaging technique which works by counting the number of photons interacting with a sensor material. This is done by measuring the signal from the detector in real time and counting the number of times the signal rises above a threshold (set significantly above the noise floor). PC has advantages over conventional x-ray imaging, such as weighting x-rays equally regardless of energy, and not integrating electronic noise into images. PC thus produces medical images with several advantages[1] including superior soft tissue contrast and higher spatial resolutions, at lower patient doses. Further, by using N different thresholds, N different energy bins can be defined, allowing spectral data to be measured in one acquisition. When a single threshold is used the technique is usually called photon counting computed tomography (PCCT), whereas with multiple thresholds the term spectral PCCT (SPCCT) is more common.

The many advantages of PC come at a cost of significantly increased complexity, as well as susceptibility to two physical phenomena: charge sharing (where one x-ray shares its charge across more than one pixel) and pulse-pileup (where x-rays arrive too close together for the counting circuitry to distinguish them). The effects of these phenomena can be significant, so hardware based correction have been proposed to deal with each: charge sharing correction algorithms (CSCAs) for charge sharing and alternative count triggering schemes (ACTS) for pulse-pileup.

Due to the high cost of prototyping and testing physical PC chips, and due to ACTS being relatively newly proposed, CSCAs and ACTS have not been deployed in parallel or compared against each other yet. Whilst each has been shown to have significant impacts on detector performance as assessed by physical metrics (detection efficiency and spectral efficiency), their implications for imaging applications are less well studied. This work aims to fill this gap in the literature by comparing the impacts of CSCAs and ACTS on image quality.

B. METHODS

1. Simulation framework

We have previously published on our unique, in-house simulation pipeline, known as CoGI, which we used to optimise a variety of detector design parameters for spectral PC imaging[2]. These studies used individual pixel metrics such as detection efficiency and spectral efficiency, rather than image quality metrics. Recently CoGI has been extended to simulate full PCCT acquisitions, as shown in Figure 1. CoGI works as follows:

- 1). The source spectrum, in 1keV increments, is calculated using SpekCalc, based on tube voltage, anode material and beam filtration.
- 2). A Monte Carlo is performed in GATE[3] to simulate photon-matter interactions through the phantom/patient and in the detector. The Livermore low-energy physics library is used, with atomic deexcitation on, to enable fluorescence x-rays from any contrast agents or semiconductor sensor materials to be included. A .txt file is thus generated,

containing the x, y, z and time coordinates for each event which deposits energy in the sensor material, along with the energy deposited.

3). A finite element model in COMSOL is used to solve the Prettyman equation[4] for each pixel geometry. This allows a 4D map of charge induction efficiency (CIE) to be calculated, which represents the efficiency with which a unit of charge can induce a signal at the collecting anode, as a function of time and the charge's location within the crystal.

4). The interactions file from GATE and the CIE map from COMSOL are combined to generate the pulse trains experienced by each pixel of the detector. The events are shaped so that signal pulses can now interact and overlap with each other, and electronic noise can be added at this stage. This work is performed in MATLAB.

5). The pixel level data can then be processed in MATLAB using a range of signal processing schemes, either intrapixel (ACTS) or interpixel (CSCAs). The output is a sinogram corresponding to the simulated acquisition.

6). The Core Imaging Library[5] is then used to reconstruct the sinogram into an image.

Figure 1. Work flow for the spectral photon counting computed tomography simulation framework, CoGI. Step number is given in the top row and corresponds to the description in the main text. Programs used to implement each stage are listed in the middle line (rectangles) and the processes simulated are given in the bottom row (rectangles with arrows at top).

2. Simulation set-up

The parameters used for the current simulations are shown in Table 1. Where multiple values are listed, every possible combination was modelled, i.e. for each flux, each pixel pitch was assessed with each processing scheme. The phantom imaged is shown in Figure 2.

Table 1. List of simulation parameters used with CoGI in the current experiment.

Step	Parameter	Value
<u>1: Source simulation</u>	Tube voltage	120 kVp
	Filtration	None
	Flux at the detector	10^6 , 10^7 and 10^8 photons $\text{mm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
<u>2: Monte Carlo</u>	Sensor material	CdTe
	Pixel pitch	100 to 400 μm , in 50 μm steps
	Sensor thickness	1.5 mm
	Number of projections	2000
	Acquisition duration	1 s
<u>3: Finite element</u>	Sensor material	CdTe
	Pixel pitch	100 to 400 μm , in 50 μm steps
	Sensor thickness	1.5 mm
	Maximum charge collection time	35 ns
<u>4: Signal interactions</u>	Noise	None added
	Pulse decay shape	Exponential (falls to 10% in 100 ns)
<u>5: Signal processing</u>	Pulse processing scheme	Standard, 5 ACTS and 12 CSCAs
<u>6: Image reconstruction</u>	Reconstruction approach	Filtered back projection

Figure 2. Test phantom imaged in this study. Calcium, iodine inserts were all varied in concentration to produce HU values in the range 100 – 800. Mixed iodine-calcium inserts used differing ratios of iodine and calcium to achieve a consistent 800 HU.

C. RESULTS

Figure 3 shows the contrast-to-noise ratio for high-flux exposures using both the standard (STD) and ACTS signal processing schemes.

Figure 4 shows how calcium linearity varies as a function of pixel pitch for STD, as well as the two best performing ACTS (DLR and SR algorithms) and for the best additive (Add2x2St) and subtractive (Sub2x2Dy) CSCAs. This is shown for both low (left) and high (right) x-ray fluxes.

Figure 3. CNR produced by the standard counting scheme and the specialized ACTS counting schemes. DLR and SR performed equally well, so only one data line is visible. CNR was assessed for the central insert at 10^8 photons $\text{mm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at the detector.

D. DISCUSSION

This work represents the first comparison of ACTS, STD and CSCA signal processing schemes in the imaging domain. The results obtained are extensive, so only representative images can be shown here. Figure 3 shows that at high fluxes where pileup is common, ACTS provide significant advantages over STD, improving CNR by almost a factor of 2. Though not shown, CSCAs performed similarly to the STD approach, making ACTS the best option for contrast preservation at high fluxes. Similarly, Figure 4 shows that whilst all approaches provide similar contrast linearity at low x-ray fluxes, at higher fluxes pulse-pileup degrades the linearity of the detector response for STD

Figure 4. Plots showing linearity of signal intensity with calcium concentration for the multiple inserts at low (10^6 photons $\text{mm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and high (10^8 photons $\text{mm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) fluxes.

and CSCA approaches, but ACTS maintain consistently high linearity scores. The drop and recovery in linearity of the CSCAs in particular was shown to be due to a PC specific imaging artefact.

This work underscores the potential impact of using ACTS in PCCT applications, and underscores the potential impact these newly proposed algorithms can have both on image quality and spectral content. These results will have implications for future PCCT system designs.

E. CONCLUSION

A fully *in silico* pipeline was used to assess image quality and spectral information content as x-ray flux, pixel pitch and signal processing schemes were systematically varied. A representative subset of results were presented. Results showed that ACTS outperform CSCAs and STD signal processing schemes in terms of CNR and calcium linearity, as well as that they were less prone to imaging artefacts.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors thank the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) for funding the work and report no conflicts of interest.

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1030-Development and application of a scanner specific cone beam CT simulation framework for image guided radiotherapy

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Purpose: To develop and validate a scanner-specific cone beam CT (CBCT) simulation framework and apply it to assess the performance of radiomics features in image guided radiotherapy and stereotactic radiation surgery.

Methods: A previously validated X-ray simulation framework (DukeSim) was adapted to replicate the specific acquisition geometry and physical attributes of a clinical CBCT scanner (TrueBeam onboard imager, Varian). The CBCT simulator was validated against experimental measurements using a standard phantom (Model 062MA, SunNuclear) imaged with a clinical scanner (TrueBeam onboard imager, Varian). Simulated and experimental measurements were quantitatively compared in terms of image quality, following the recommendations of AAPM TG 179 and TG 142. Using the validated simulation framework, CBCT images of human models with brain cancer (varying lesions shapes, size, and positions) were generated to assess the reproducibility and repeatability of radiomics features in CBCT.

Results: The CBCT simulator was successfully implemented. The validation results demonstrated close concordance between the simulations and experimental measurements, with all image quality parameters meeting the AAPM TG 179 and TG 142 recommendations, i.e., HU uniformity was below 50 HU and geometric distortion was measured at 0.2 mm for lesions smaller than 2 mm, suggesting that the modeled CBCT scanner is a viable tool for stereotactic radiation surgery applications.

Conclusions: This study demonstrates the potential use of virtual imaging trials for quantitative CBCT studies in radiation therapy. The simulation framework showed strong agreement with experimental results in terms of image quality, uniformity, and geometrical artifact. Ongoing work includes evaluating the accuracy of morphological radiomics features across different reconstruction techniques, such as Feldkamp-Davis-Kress (FDK) and the simultaneous algebraic reconstruction technique (SART).

1031-Simulation and modelling in assessing performance of AI enabled medical devices

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There is rapid growth in the number of artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML) enabled medical devices on the market: more than 1000 have marketing authorizations from the FDA, mainly for radiology.

Regulators have become increasingly aware that AI/ML medical devices pose new risks compared to traditional algorithms. There are many risks around data quality and bias that can need to be suitably mitigated. If the training data may contain an unrepresentative group of patients or pathology, or doesn't capture the variability in collected data (scanner manufacturers or acquisition setting) then real world performance of those devices can be significantly worse than published, values, especially where cross-validated methods are used.

Modelling and simulation can be used to create data that can augment clinical data, and increase anatomical variability, instrument-induced variability (noise, contrast, distortion etc), and pathological variability, and confounds. The use of simulated data to augment clinical data in training and validating of AI/ML enabled medical devices might enable data from 100 participants and 5 centres to capture the variability in anatomy, pathology and data acquisition that might otherwise need to have been gathered from 1000s of patients and 100s of hospitals.

The increasing regulatory acceptance of simulated data is illustrated by the definition of FDA medical device product code QIH: Automated radiological image processing and analysis tools. Software implementing artificial intelligence including non-adaptive machine learning algorithms trained with clinical and/or artificial data".

There is a need for a consensus on appropriate validation of models used to generate simulated data, and for sharing of good practice and of models.

Scatter-to-primary ratio in contrast-enhanced mammography for different grid ratios – A Monte Carlo study

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Contrast-enhanced mammography (CEM) is an emerging imaging modality for breast imaging^{1,2}. Since the same system is used for both digital mammography (DM) and CEM, they use the same anti-scatter grid. Due to the use of different spectra in CEM, the spatial distribution of scatter across the projected breast surface may differ between both images, which was already reasoned to be the cause of artifacts².

For the high-energy (HE) image, the currently used grids might have reduced scatter absorption properties due to stronger penetration and reduced scattering angles for HE photons³. One possibility to increase the absorption efficiency for such photons is an increase of the grid ratio $r = h/D$. Since a decrease in the septa separation D could negatively affect primary transmission, this study aimed at investigating the impact of grid ratio increase on the scatter-to-primary ratio (SPR) in CEM by increasing the septa height h .

B. METHODS

1. Monte Carlo simulations

Four realistically shaped compressed breast phantoms of average shape in the cranio-caudal view were generated⁴ with thicknesses (t) of 30 mm, 50 mm, 70 mm, and 90 mm. The phantoms were defined as a homogeneous mix of 15 % glandular and 85 % adipose tissue⁵.

A digital twin of a *Siemens Mammomat Revelation* system was created with a previously validated Geant4-based⁶ (version 10.7.4, Sept. 2022) Monte Carlo (MC) breast imaging simulation program⁷. The modelled system had a source-to-imager distance (SID) of 655.5 mm and consisted of a 3 mm thick PET compression paddle, an air gap of 12.6 mm that included the 2 mm thick carbon fiber breast support table and the grid, a 1.0 mm carbon fiber and 3.4 mm air detector cover, and an a-Se direct conversion layer (239.36x304.64x0.2 mm³, pixel size 1.36x1.36 mm²) (see fig. 1). Focused stationary anti-scatter grids of four different geometries were simulated (see table 1). One simulation without grid was performed for each phantom. Each simulation resulted in two images of energy deposited by primary and scattered radiation. Two spectra were applied per phantom and grid condition: low-energy (LE): W/Rh 0.05 mm at 27 kV, 29 kV, 31 kV, and 32 kV for the 30 mm to 90 mm thick phantoms, respectively; and HE: W/Ti 1.0 mm at 49 kV (independent of breast thickness). The source was modelled⁸ as a point source emitting diverging X rays electronically collimated to the detector including the heel effect. The number of histories per simulation condition varied between 4.0×10^9 and 4.6×10^9 to result in a statistical uncertainty of $\sigma < 1$ % per image.

Table 1

Grid parameter	Unit	Value			
Grid ratio r	-	5 (standard)	10	15	20
Septa thickness d	mm		0.0215		
Septa separation D	mm		0.285		
Septa height h	mm	1.5	2.85	4.275	5.7
Position above detector p_z	mm	9.7	9.025	8.3125	7.6
Septa material	-		Pb		
Interspace material	-		Cellulose		

Figure 1 Schematic of Monte Carlo geometry. (a) Side view, showing x-ray beam extent. (b) Front view, showing grid structure and geometry.

2. Analysis

From the obtained LE primary images without grid, binary masks of the projected breast area were obtained for each phantom through flat-field correction and thresholding using Otsu's method⁹. Additionally, the center of mass (COM) was computed from the binary images. At the COM of each phantom, a region of interest (ROI) of 7×7 px ($\approx 1 \times 1$ cm²) was placed for analysis. The mean scatter-to-primary ratio (SPR) inside this ROI was then calculated as

$$SPR = \frac{S}{P}$$

with P and S being the energies absorbed by the detector from primary and scattered photons, respectively. Additionally, average profiles over a width of 7 px were obtained across the projected breast area in perpendicular directions through the COM to evaluate the spatial distribution of SPR.

C. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows SPR decrease with increasing grid ratio (a) and differences in SPR between HE and LE ($dSPR$) (b). The standard grid ($r = 5$) reduced SPR at the COM by 68 % - 76 % (LE) and 66 % - 74 % (HE). While a grid with $r = 10$ brought an additional SPR reduction of 8 % - 9 %, further increase of r had only minor effects. SPR increased with increasing breast thickness for LE and HE images. This increase was reduced when increasing r . For $r \geq 10$, differences between HE and LE images at the COM neither changed with r nor with t .

Differences in SPR between the two spectra were also reduced across the entire projected breast surface with the standard grid. However, figure 3 shows the shapes of the SPR profiles assimilating even further when increasing r to 10 for a 50 mm thick phantom. However, this increase in SPR homogeneity affected only the inner part of the projected breast area and not the breast edge.

D. DISCUSSION

The standard grid is only slightly less effective at reducing scatter under HE conditions compared to the LE range. However, increasing r to around 10 further reduces SPR within the breast and the effect of breast thickness on scatter in both DM and CEM. More importantly, it improves SPR homogeneity across LE and HE images, potentially minimizing rim artifacts in CEM. Unlike the LE image, the HE image is not affected by the SPR increase near the inner breast edge caused by the compression paddle⁷. This results in marked differences between HE and LE scatter distributions in that region, seen in fig. 3 as a negative $dSPR$ and sign reversal. Greater similarity of SPR profiles between LE and HE images might contribute to less noticeable artifacts.

Simulation results without a grid align well with previous data in the LE-range¹⁰ and HE experimental measurements¹¹. Although relative deviations with the standard grid are larger, absolute differences remain small (< 0.25) due to overall low SPR values when using a grid.

Figure 2 Mean SPR for LE and HE images (a) and difference of mean SPR between HE and LE (b) inside a 7x7 px ROI at the COM for all grid conditions and breast thicknesses. Error bars indicate 95% coverage intervals.

Figure 3 Differences in SPR between HE and LE for different grid ratios across the projected breast surface for the 50 mm phantom case. Black vertical lines indicate the COM. Error bands show 95% coverage intervals.

This study is limited to a single mammography system. Therefore, results may differ slightly for manufacturers with different setups. Additionally, the projected breast area of the phantoms increases with thickness, which may confound the effects of breast size and thickness on SPR. Nevertheless, the simulations reflect SPR behavior for average-shaped breasts at each thickness level, as observed in the general population.

E. CONCLUSION

Virtual imaging trials using MC simulations can effectively demonstrate optimization potential in medical imaging. For CEM, an increased grid ratio close to $r = 10$ could be beneficial due to reduced SPR at the COM and increased SPR homogeneity across the projected breast surface. Furthermore, the influence of breast thickness on SPR would be reduced both in DM and CEM. It would be interesting to see how this reduction in SPR through an increased grid ratio affects image quality.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

I. Sechopoulos has research agreements with Canon Medical Systems, Siemens Healthcare, Sectra Benelux, ScreenPoint Medical, Volpara Health, and Lunit.

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Virtual patient populations of breast cancer from a biology-based mathematical model and quantitative MRI data

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Clinical trials in oncology can only evaluate a few therapeutic interventions in a small number of patients to determine safety, efficacy, and dosing. The limited patient numbers inevitably fail to capture the heterogeneity of tumor characteristics. Virtual clinical trials are a potential solution to evaluate many therapeutic interventions in representative and sufficiently heterogeneous patient populations. To generate a virtual patient population, we use our biology-based, mathematical model of tumor growth and treatment response¹ to characterize key biological properties for triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) patients. The model is a mechanically coupled system of differential equations that explicitly accounts for biological characteristics including cell proliferation and death due to treatment. By fitting the model to patient-specific magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data, we generate patient-specific estimates of these parameters. Thus, for n patients in a dataset, we generate n pairs of tumor cell proliferation and drug efficacy values. We then fit a joint probability distribution to these parameter estimates and sample to generate new “virtual patient” parameters, repeating the process m times to generate an explainable, biology-based virtual population (of m patients) that is appropriate for simulating, for example, novel interventional strategies.

B. METHODS

1. Patient population and image processing

Data from 27 TNBC patients in the I-SPY2 trial² were used in this study. Patients underwent diffusion-weighted MRI (DW-MRI) and dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (DCE-MRI) before (V1), after three weekly cycles (V2), and after twelve weekly cycles (V3) of neoadjuvant chemotherapy. Intra- and intervisit image registration was performed to align all images from all visits (V1-V3) for each patient. DCE-MRI scans were used to identify the tumor region of interest, estimate spatiotemporal drug concentration maps $C(x,t)$, and segment breast tissue types (adipose, fibroglandular) using established methods^{1,9}. DW-MRI scans were used to calculate apparent diffusion coefficient maps $ADC(x,t)$ from which tumor cellularity (i.e., cell number) maps, $N(x,t)$ were calculated¹ (Figure 1A).

2. Biology-based mathematical model

Our biology-based mathematical model characterizes the spatiotemporal change in the number of tumor cells, $N(x, t)$, as a

function of the diffusion of cells, logistic proliferation, and treatment-induced death¹:

$$\frac{\partial N(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot D (\nabla N(\mathbf{x}, t)) + kN(\mathbf{x}, t) \left(1 - \frac{N(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\theta}\right) - \alpha C(\mathbf{x}, t)e^{-\beta t}, \quad [1]$$

where D is the tumor cell diffusion coefficient (s/mm^2), k is the tumor cell proliferation rate (day^{-1}), θ is the carrying capacity, α is the efficacy rate of the treatment (day^{-1}), and β is the decay rate of treatment efficacy (day^{-1}). The diffusion of tumor cells, D , is damped by the mechanical forces on the tumor from surrounding tissue³ as given by

$$D(\mathbf{x}, t) = D_0 e^{-\gamma \sigma_{vm}(\mathbf{x}, t)}, \quad [2]$$

subject to mechanical equilibrium

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma(\mathbf{x}, t) - \lambda \cdot \nabla N(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0, \quad [3]$$

where D_0 is the diffusion coefficient of unstressed tumor cells, λ and γ are mechanical coupling constants, and $\sigma_{vm}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the von Mises stress obtained from the Cauchy stress tensor, σ .

3. Model calibration

For each patient, global values (i.e., one value per patient) for D , k , and α were estimated by calibrating Eqs. [1]-[3] to the MRI data from all visits (V1-V3) via Levenberg-Marquardt. Using these calibrated values, the parametrized model was run forward in time from V1 to predict patient-specific tumor response at V3; this created the model patient population from which the virtual populations are to be generated¹.

4. Generating the virtual patient population

Sensitivity analyses (data not shown) indicate k and α parameters have the greatest influence on the temporal tumor cellularity changes. Thus, combinations of these two parameters were used to generate unique virtual patients. To capture the heterogeneity of the model population, a Gaussian mixture model⁵ (GMM) was used to estimate the joint distribution of (k, α) (Figure 1B) via the Expectation-Maximization algorithm. To generate a virtual patient, the model is first furnished with an initial tumor cellularity map, $N(\mathbf{x}, t=V1)$ and its corresponding θ , $C(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and D . Then, the model is assigned a sampled k and α from the fitted GMM and is run forward to predict virtual patient tumor response at V3 (Figure 1C). This process is repeated using 100 samples from the fitted GMM and combined with the 27 initial tumor cellularity maps (and corresponding θ , $C(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and D), to yield 2700 virtual patients.

5. Expanding heterogeneity within the virtual patient population

To increase the heterogeneity of treatment response in a virtual population, the covariance matrices of the best-fit GMM were scaled by a factor of 2, 3, 4, and 5. We drew 100 (k, α) pairs from each of the scaled GMMs and generated virtual populations as described in the previous section.

6. Statistical Analysis

Virtual patients are first constructed to capture the statistical relationships present in the original data⁵. To preserve the relationship between k and α , we chose the best-fit GMM using the Bayesian Information Criterion⁷. We quantified the agreement between virtual and model patient population response to treatment via the 2-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test⁷ applied to the percent change in tumor cellularity from V1 to V3.

C. RESULTS

The best-fit GMM for the set of calibrated k and α from the model patients has two components with weights of 0.93 and 0.07. Figure 3 depicts the distribution of change in tumor cellularity from V1 to V3 (i.e., the change from $(N(\mathbf{x}, t=V1))$ to $N(\mathbf{x}, t=V3)$) for the model patients and each virtual patient population. As the covariance scale factor increases, the distribution of the responses increasingly deviates from that of the model population. Decreasing KS test p -values quantify this trend; covariance scale factors greater than 4 result in virtual patient populations whose response to treatment is significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from that of the model population. Thus, we can generate populations whose response matches that of the original population, as well as populations that differ from the response distribution of the original population in a controlled and explainable way.

Figure 1. (A) Patient tumor cellularity maps, $N(\mathbf{x}, t)$, at times $V1$ - $V3$ were used to calibrate global values for k and α , resulting in one (k, α) pair for each of the 27 patients. A GMM estimates the joint distribution of the two parameters. (B) To generate a virtual patient, the model is furnished with initial tumor cellularity, $N(\mathbf{x}, t=V1)$, carrying capacity θ , drug concentration $C(\mathbf{x}, t)$, diffusion coefficient D , and a sampled (k, α) pair from the GMM. (C) The model is run forward in time to make predictions for the virtual patient.

D. DISCUSSION

We presented virtual patient populations with increasing heterogeneity of tumor characteristics and treatment responses compared to the original dataset. The importance and practicality of using a biology-based, mathematical model is clear; its interpretability allows us to generate virtual patients with specific, known characteristics that possess a controllable degree of heterogeneity. However, there remain several opportunities for improvement. The version of the mathematical model used in this study does not account for intra-tumor heterogeneity as we calibrated k and α globally. In other manifestations of this model, we calibrated for spatially varying $k(\mathbf{x})$ to capture intra-tumor heterogeneity⁸. We are currently working to generate realistic, unique tumor geometries using spherical harmonics-based decomposition⁹. Lastly, the level of disease heterogeneity captured is limited by the small number of model patients used to inform the GMM.

E. CONCLUSION

We are developing a framework for generating virtual populations of TNBC patients using an immediately interpretable biology-based mathematical model that allows tuning of tumor characteristic heterogeneity to construct patients with features not captured in the original patient cohort. This framework is applicable to any solid tumor for which the necessary MRI data is available.

Figure 3. (A) Change in cellularity from V1 to V3 in model patients using patient-specific calibrated parameters. (B) Change in cellularity from V1 to V3 in virtual patients generated from the best-fit GMM has a similar distribution as that of the model patients shown in (A). (C-F) Change in cellularity from V1 to V3 in the virtual patient populations generated by scaling the covariance matrix of the best-fit GMM demonstrates the increasing heterogeneity of response to treatment with increasing scale factor. Decreasing two-sample KS test p -values shows that increasing scale factors decrease the similarity between virtual patient and model patient treatment response.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

NSF DMS 2436499, NSF DMS 2309782, NSF CISE-IIS 2312746, CPRIT RP220225

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation Graduate Research Fellowship under Grant No. DE2137420

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1034-Enabling in silico trials at population scales a pilot CT virtual imaging trial using ORNL supercomputing resources

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Purpose:

Virtual imaging trials (VITs) require extensive computational resources to simulate the heterogeneity of clinical populations and image acquisition protocols. As simulation scope expands to cover larger parameter spaces, traditional computing systems are unable to meet demand. By harnessing high-performance computing (HPC) capabilities at Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL), this project aims to develop a scalable computational framework for CT VITs.

Methods:

Simulations were performed using DukeSim, a validated CT simulation platform that uses CPU- and GPU-driven processes. The study utilized 297 virtual XCAT phantoms representing diverse conditions, specifically lung lesions (107 adult and 57 pediatric), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD, 67 adult), and liver lesions (66 adult). Simulations accounted for dynamic variations in disease progression, respiratory motion, and scan protocols. These computationally intensive simulations were executed on Summit, an ORNL supercomputer featuring 4600 compute nodes, each equipped with dual IBM POWER9 processors and six NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs.

Results:

A total of 10,140 simulations were performed, generating over 125 TB of CT projection data and reconstructed images. Each cohort accounted for a range of acquisition conditions (3-30), variations in disease states (1-2), and repetitions with variable anatomy (1-3). Simulations ran on individual compute nodes in 35-100 minutes (average 45 minutes) compared to an estimated 317 days on a single node. Leveraging ORNL's HPC resources, the VIT was completed in two weeks – an unprecedented efficiency compared to previous simulation studies or clinical trials of smaller scale.

Conclusion:

By leveraging the capabilities of supercomputing resources, we successfully conducted a population scale VIT, generating over 10,000 CT simulations. This enables the evaluation of diverse patients and conditions, including the ability repeated CT scans of the same patient to address a wide variety of questions on CT variability. This study advances AI-driven simulation frameworks and sets a new standard for computational research in complex scientific domains.

Dataset	Adult Lung Lesions	Pediatric Lung Lesions			AAPM Challenge phantoms		
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Data subset		80 kV	100 kV	120 kV	Lung Lesions	COPD	Liver Lesions
# patients	40	57			67	67	66
Total # of phantoms	120	171			67	67	66
Scanner type	EID, PCCT	EID	EID, PCCT	EID	EID		
Parameter variations	30	3	8	5	12		
Simulation count	4320	684	1710	1026	804	804	792
Total	4320	3420			2400		
Final total	10140						

1036-Virtual Imaging Trials with Generic Engine for Modular Software Task Orchestration and Negotiation (VIT GEMSTONE)

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A virtual imaging trial requires interdependent workings of software for virtual patient creation, virtual imaging, and virtual perception of images. Efficient execution of such a virtual trial requires an integrated system consisting of multiple software modules running in sequence. However, inconsistencies in file formats, heterogeneous environments, and complex execution dependencies undermine such integration. Outputs from one module may not align with the expected inputs of the next, and variations in command-line options, parameter handling, and environment settings further complicate automation. Errors in parameter specification often surface late in execution, wasting time and resources. Many pipeline architectures address these challenges with tightly coupled wrapper scripts, but this approach makes modifications complex and creates barriers to integrating new components.

GEMSTONE is a generic orchestration engine designed to fully decouple processing modules from the engine, allowing software components to be added, removed, or modified without changes to the core system. GEMSTONE addresses three persistent challenges in multi-stage workflows. Path management and parameter validation are built-in and centrally managed. Developers configure parameter and path names, types, and constraints without writing parsing or validation code. GEMSTONE enforces type safety, default values, range limits, and directory existence checks upon launch, to catch errors early. File format compatibility is addressed through structured documentation and validation mechanisms that guide module developers through negotiation to explicitly-defined agreements, that are automatically enforced at runtime.

By allowing modules to evolve without requiring changes to the core engine, GEMSTONE accelerates integration. Centralized parameter validation reduces debugging time, centralized path management reduces confusion and improves portability, and structured format agreements ensure compatibility across diverse software components. The scalable design supports large workflows and allows module-level parallelization. A pilot deployment at CVIT is currently evaluating GEMSTONE's effectiveness in integrating virtual patient creation, virtual CT scanning, and virtual radiologist tasks into an end-to-end workflow.

1037-An Automated CCTA Ischemic Myocardial Segmentation Network Using 3D Symmetry and Sparse Annotation

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Myocardial dysfunction serves as a direct trigger for the occurrence of future Major Adverse Cardiovascular Events (MACE). Clinically, analysis of left ventricular myocardial function in different perfusion regions is commonly conducted. However, due to the lack of rapid segmentation and analysis algorithms for ischemic myocardial segmentation in the short-axis view of Coronary Computed Tomography Angiography (CCTA), there are challenges in performing myocardial analysis in imaging studies. To address the aforementioned challenges, this paper implements an automated segmentation method for ischemic myocardial based on CCTA images. Our method consists of three main components: myocardium segmentation, short-axis rigid transformation, and ischemic myocardial segmentation. Specifically, we are the first to design a longitudinal localization algorithm for myocardium segmentation. This algorithm precisely calculates the spatial position of the longitudinal axis and employs a longitudinal axis-based transformation method to resample the original CCTA scans into short-axis orientation. Additionally, we devise a partitioning algorithm based on symbolic distance to generate key points and a voxel-level 17-segment model from the myocardium. The ischemic myocardial segmentation aligns with FFR values, enabling an accurate correspondence. Through the aforementioned steps, this paper ultimately realizes an algorithmic workflow for identifying cardiac functional regions based on CCTA, with coronary artery perfusion as a reference. This work automates the clinical task of left ventricular segment partitioning, providing physicians with intelligent diagnostic assistance and contributing to the advancement of medical practice.

1038-Multimodal Driven Gene Expression Prediction from Pathology Images of Gastrointestinal Tumors

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Rectal cancer is a common and heterogeneous malignant tumor that requires precise genetic analysis for better understanding and treatment. With the development of deep learning and the emergence of pathology foundation models, significant progress has been made in pathology-based pan-cancer gene prediction, but research on specific cancer types remains insufficient. In this study, we constructed a comprehensive gastrointestinal adenocarcinoma dataset and developed a multi-stage deep learning framework. By leveraging pathology foundation models to generate pathology reports, the model's ability to extract disease-specific features was enhanced. An image feature retrieval mechanism was incorporated to utilize similar samples, and a Transformer-based architecture was applied for gene prediction, optimized with a hybrid loss function to capture both global patterns and local variations. The model demonstrated excellent performance on two independent pathology datasets. Furthermore, a colorectal cancer spatial transcriptomics dataset was constructed to validate the model's ability to predict spatially resolved gene expression and decode intratumoral regional heterogeneity.

1039-Consensus recommendations on reliable development and use of Virtual Imaging Trials Updates from the AAPM Task Group 387

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Over the recent year, the concepts and methods underlying virtual imaging trials (VITs) have significantly matured. These advancements include the ongoing development of diverse models of human anatomy and diseases, as well as scanner-specific simulations of various imaging devices. Given the remarkable progress and demonstrated benefits of VITs across multiple imaging modalities and applications, it is crucial to establish robust frameworks that facilitate their widespread adoption within the medical imaging research community. To advance this goal, we have formed an AAPM Task Group to consolidate consensus recommendations for the reliable development and application of VITs. This presentation will outline these recommendations, focusing on three essential pillars: credibility, reproducibility, and accessibility. 1) Credibility – Patient and imaging device models must undergo rigorous verification and validation to ensure a sufficient level of realism and diversity for their intended use in imaging trials. 2) Reproducibility – Virtual resources and documentation should be designed to enable seamless replication of data and findings from previous trials. 3) Accessibility – VITs should be user-friendly and widely accessible, requiring streamlined coding practices, effective data management schemes, standardized input/output formats with appropriate headers and identifiers, and intuitive software tools. To achieve these objectives, we have developed consensus recommendations that promote collaboration, data sharing, and interoperability of VIT components across diverse imaging applications, including X-ray imaging, nuclear medicine, MRI, and ultrasound. These recommendations will be presented alongside examples of specific VIT tools. Additionally, we will discuss existing challenges and propose potential solutions to further establish virtual imaging trials as a powerful resource in medical imaging research and practice.

Retinal Digital Twins: From Imaging to Personalized Predictions

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Digital twins are increasingly gaining traction in healthcare. These twins are simulations of parts of the human body that directly relate back to an individual. Using such twins, we are able to optimize patient interventions and personalize patient predictions. In the field of vascular digital twins, prior work has primarily dealt with twinning major vessels such as the aorta¹, major cerebral vessels², or heart chambers such as the atrium³. These are relatively easy to image and extract patient structure from. However, there have been far fewer microvascular digital twins.

The retina, at the back of the eye, is an ideal system to create a microvascular digital twin. It is simple to image, with colour fundus photograph or optical coherence tomography being non-invasive and quick, and it is connected to the brain providing a window to general cerebro and cardiovascular health⁴. Crucially for a digital twin, it is simple and cheap to repeatedly image, allowing for longitudinal models of health to be built up.

Besides being a window to microvascular health, the retina has a plethora of diseases such as age-related macular degeneration, central serous retinopathy, and diabetic retinopathy, for which early treatment is essential to preserve vision. Therefore, being able to develop digital twins of the retina will allow us to better understand retinal and vascular disease and help us to improve treatment options and outcomes for individuals.

Prior work has developed mathematical models of the retina, as well as generative digital twins of the retinal vasculature^{5,6}. Here we go beyond these works by firstly developing a virtual population pipeline to generate synthetic retinal vasculatures. We then develop a personalized digital twin pipeline of the retinal vasculature introducing a way to simulate the deep capillary layers that are currently difficult to segment.

B. METHODS

Virtual Populations

A statistical shape model is used to generate the four major temporal arcades. Constrained constructive optimization (CCO) is then used to grow the branching tree network in two stages. The first stage ensures spread of flow across the temporal region of the retina. The second stage creates smaller arterioles that perfuse the macula, mimicking an angiogenic process biased towards the avascular zone.

The final stage generates the capillary bed. CCO is not useful in this instance as the capillary bed is a mesh-like structure distributed in depth across three layers – the superficial, intermediate and deep capillary plexi. As a result, Voronoi tessellation was used to generate the capillary plexi in the macular region. The superficial network was connected to the branching tree through the pre-capillary arterioles/post-capillary venules. The layers of the capillary network were connected through vessels at 90 degrees to the layers distributed with a density of 11/mm² as observed in histology samples.

Functional simulations included blood flow through the network using a lumped parameter model with a terminal resistance for arterioles and venules that terminated outside of the macula.

Once the pipeline is setup, all that is required to simulate a synthetic individual is blood pressure, central retinal artery diameter, central retinal artery flow velocity, and intraocular pressure⁷.

Digital Twins

The digital twin pipeline uses colour fundus images with overlaid optical coherence tomography angiography (OCTA) to segment the retinal vascular network for an individual. This was semi-automated with two datasets used – an in-house dataset collected from the Liverpool Royal Hospital⁸ and the DRIVE dataset⁹. Six individuals had their vasculature segmented.

The capillary bed was again dealt with using Voronoi tessellation due to the inability to segment a connected network at that resolution. Each individual had 20 capillary networks generated due to this with averages taken across those 20 networks. Blood flow was again simulated, but now with the addition of a plasma skimming model¹⁰ from which mean transit times (MTT) and capillary transit time heterogeneity (CTH) could be computed.

Diabetic retinopathy was simulated in these individuals to see how differing retinal vasculatures may be impacted by modifications in disease. Diabetic retinopathy was simulated through a progressive decline in vessel density.

C. RESULTS

Virtual populations of 200 synthetic individuals were generated (example can be seen in Fig 1a-c). These networks were validated against morphometric quantities such as vascular area density and fractal dimension, as well as functional quantities like retinal blood flow (Fig 1d). These all showed good agreement with experimental data.

Figure 1 (A) A visualisation of one generated individual vasculature. Vessels are coloured according to their type: capillary, artery or vein. (B) Zoomed in view of the dense macular region from (A), colour-coded by vascular plexus. Length on each axis is in centimetres. (C) En-face view of the SVC in the temporal region and the macula (zoomed-in inset). (D) Validation of blood flow simulations against experimental data across diameters. Adapted from Hernandez et al.⁷ SVC: superficial vascular complex.

Six individuals were selected from which digital twins of the retinal vasculature were developed (Fig 2). As we did not have individual measures of flow and pressure, we used literature values which showed good overall agreement. The different datasets had different fidelities and hence the segmentations were not as detailed in the in-house dataset. This proved to have a large effect on flow conditions. Simulations of MTT and CTH also agreed with the literature, with an increase from 5s and 6s respectively to 7s and 10s when diabetic retinopathy was simulated.

Figure 2 Example of generated digital twins. The graph of the vasculature is shown next to the generated vascular graph. Arteries (in red) and veins (in orange) are digitised from the segmentation. Capillaries (in blue) are randomly generated.

D. DISCUSSION

In this work we demonstrated two pipelines for developing retinal vascular simulations. The first generates synthetic virtual populations for use in *in silico* clinical trials¹¹. The second segments and simulates blood flow and plasma skimming in individual retinal vasculatures. This opens up the possibility of patient-specific retinal digital twins.

The patient-specific digital twin simulations were only specific up to the capillary level. At the capillary scale, the imaging is not good enough to discern the capillary network in full. As such, we had to use synthetically generated capillary beds simulated using Voronoi tessellation. Due to this, the retinal twin is not fully representative of an individual at this scale. We attempted to overcome this issue by generating 20 different capillary beds for each retinal vasculature to give us error bounds on the impact of the capillary plexi.

Furthermore, a limitation with generating digital twins of the microvasculature is the difficulty with validation, particularly functional validation. We did not have patient-specific flow measurements in the retina, although this is possible with an invasive fundus fluorescein angiogram.

We also demonstrated the impact of diabetic retinopathy on mean transit time of red blood cells, showing a 40% increase in transit time. This is an interesting result and motivates further investigation as an *in silico* biomarker of retinal disease.

E. CONCLUSION

Digital twin technology is rapidly advancing in multiple areas of health. Here we demonstrate that this can be extended to the microcirculation through the easily imageable retinal vasculature. Further work is required to understand how to validate patient-specific simulations and incorporate longitudinal data as repeat scans become more common.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

RJH was funded by an EPSRC Doctoral Training Network in AI and Future Digital Health studentship.

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Validation of frictional interactions in mechanical thrombectomy using in vitro and in silico models

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BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Mechanical thrombectomy (MT) is a widely adopted technique for treating acute ischemic stroke (AIS); however, the mechanical interactions between the clot, vessel wall, and stent retriever (SR) remain insufficiently quantified.¹ One critical aspect of MT is the friction between the clot, vessel, and SR. While clot-vessel friction has been extensively studied, fibrin-rich clots - those with low red blood cell (RBC) content exhibit higher friction than RBC-rich clots.² Clinical trials have similarly observed that the increased friction of fibrin-rich clots complicates retrieval. Previous studies calculated the static friction coefficient between the clot and vessel, assuming dynamic friction to be negligible. However, a recent study quantified dynamic friction for clot-vessel, stent-vessel, and stent-clot interactions for the first time.³ The results showed lower dynamic friction values for clot-vessel and clot-stent interactions but significantly higher dynamic friction between the stent and vessel. Past in silico MT studies neglected stent-vessel friction, assuming its dynamic friction was minimal. This study aims to validate and better understand stent-vessel friction through in silico and in vitro experiments.

METHODS

A realistic vascular model was used to perform thrombectomy procedures (without a clot) under controlled conditions in the in vitro setup.⁴ The experimental setup consisted of a fluid reservoir, a pump, a silicone phantom, and a stent retriever (SR) (Solitaire X, Medtronic) positioned within a Phenom 21 microcatheter (Medtronic), as illustrated in Fig. 1. The purpose of the *in vitro* studies was to investigate the influence of SR-vessel friction on SR behavior, particularly in curved vessel regions. SR retrieval procedures were recorded for each test to analyze SR dynamics and enable comparison with *in silico* studies.

For the *in silico* setup, a 3D model was reconstructed from CT scans of the experimental silicone phantom. A similar configuration to the *in vitro* setup was replicated using LS-DYNA, and a sensitivity analysis of friction was performed through multiple simulations. The friction coefficient

value was validated by iterating and achieving similar stent behavior to the in vitro model in a curved vessel. Additionally, blood clots were incorporated into the in silico studies to investigate the effect of friction and decay ratio on mechanical thrombectomy (MT) outcomes. Finite element simulations were conducted in LS-DYNA to carry out the *in silico* experiments.^{5,6}

Fig. 1. Schematic of the pipeline used in the in silico and in vitro setup for validating stent-vessel friction and sensitivity analysis of MT using in silico models.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Clinical practice and *in vitro* experiments have demonstrated that acute vessel curvature correlates with poorer mechanical thrombectomy (MT) outcomes and higher failure rates. These adverse outcomes have been attributed to stent retriever (SR) compression, which may cause clot disengagement and subsequent MT failure. Using *in vitro* and *in silico* models, we investigated SR compression and its relationship with the SR-vessel friction coefficient. Our findings indicate that higher SR-vessel friction leads to increased stent compression and wire-like deformation. Notably, validated SR-vessel friction coefficients are currently absent from the literature. To address this gap, we quantified these values through *in vitro* SR retrieval experiments, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2. MT outcomes for varying decay coefficient (DC) for fibrin-rich clot. Friction coefficients for clot-vessel (FS = 0.46, FD = 0.23), clot-stent (FS = 0.1, FD = 0.03), and stent-vessel (FS = FD = 0.2) were kept constant for both cases. FS: Static friction and FD: dynamic friction

We calculated the experimental friction coefficient between the stent retriever (SR) and vessel wall, obtaining values of approximately 0.73 with saline solution and 0.5 with soap solution. When replicating these retrievals *in silico* using the 0.73 friction coefficient, we observed a significant discrepancy in stent behavior compared to *in vitro* results, with excessive compression in simulations. This mismatch likely stems from differences in contact area representation between physical experiments and numerical modeling. Through iterative adjustments, we matched the stent compression ratio (compressed length to vessel diameter) to *in vitro* observations by reducing the friction coefficient to 0.3 for saline and 0.2 for soap solution. This validated coefficient (F=0.2) was subsequently used for all remaining simulations to predict thrombectomy outcomes. Notably, SR compression persisted even at F=0.1, leading to: (i) Fibrin-rich clots disengaging from SR struts in curved regions, and (ii) RBC-rich clots fragmenting in curved regions. This aligns with clinical and *in vitro* findings reported in the literature.⁷

We further investigated fibrin-rich clots by simulating mechanical thrombectomy (MT) with varying decay ratios (governing static-to-dynamic friction transition), as shown in Fig. 2. At lower decay ratios, fibrin-rich clots disengaged earlier than at higher ratios—a phenomenon observed numerically but requiring experimental validation.

CONCLUSIONS

The comparison revealed strong agreement between experimental and numerical results, validating the predictive capability of *in silico* models in thrombectomy research. The stent behavior in curved vessels and its relation to failure in thrombectomy are thoroughly investigated. The higher SR-vessel friction values contribute to SR compression in curved vessels. The effect of decay ratio

on fibrin-rich clot has been investigated, and we found that a lower decay ratio contributes to early disengagement in comparison with a higher decay ratio. These findings contribute to the optimization of thrombectomy devices and procedural strategies, ultimately enhancing treatment outcomes for patients with ischemic stroke. The effect of decay coefficient (DC) in numerical simulations shows significant variation in MT outcomes, and it needs to be validated with in vitro studies. The clot behavior and disengagement in the curved vessels need further thorough investigation and validation.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

FUNDING

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101104493.

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Stereotactic ablative body radiotherapy (SABR) is a modern form of radiotherapy that delivers a high radiation dose to the tumour, with minimal irradiation of the surrounding tissue and is used to treat early stage lung cancer. However, even in such cancers, microscopic disease outside the tumour increases the risk of local-regional failure. In this research, a model of microscopic disease is fitted to clinical imaging, dose and outcome data for 257 lung cancer patients. The model is then used to investigate modified treatments prescribing a low dose level to a larger second target volume. We seek to determine whether such a prescription reduces the risk of failure without overexposure of the lung.

We employ simulations that calculate a tumour control probability (TCP) using patient planning CT scans, modelled geometric uncertainties, planned dose distributions, and a model of microscopic disease. The microscopic disease probability scales linearly with the size of the tumour and decreases exponentially from the tumour edge (Fig.1).

In the virtual clinical trial, patient delivered doses are modified to include a margin around the tumour receiving 25% of the maximum dose to the tumour. The set of predicted TCPs using the modified dose distributions is compared to the set obtained with the original dose distributions to determine the effectiveness of the margin.

It was found that a 2.3cm margin covers microscopic disease in 90% of patients. This is significantly larger than the current consensus from pathology studies. The results of the virtual trial suggest that applying this margin during the SABR planning process reduces the rate of local-regional recurrence by $(2.10 \pm 0.08)\%$ whilst only increasing the mean lung dose by 0.02%. In conclusion, our virtual trial suggests that a modified dose prescription can improve tumour control with negligible increase in toxicity. This is possible due to overlap with the existing dose spill (Fig.1).

Fig.1: The method used in this research. Patient imaging, dose and outcome data are used to fit a model of microscopic disease. A virtual trial is then conducted using Monte Carlo simulations, and the effectiveness of a modified dose is compared to the original dose.

A virtual study of soft tissue spectral information in unenhanced photon-counting CT

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

The next major leap in detector technology for computed tomography (CT) is the introduction of photon-counting detectors.^{1,2} As opposed to conventional integrating x-ray detectors, which detect the number of photons that have interacted in the detector during a period of time, photon-counting detectors register single photons along with their energies. Photon-counting detectors have the potential to significantly improve spectral and spatial resolution compared to current detectors, thereby enhancing, or enabling, a range of clinical applications.

The high energy resolution offered by photon-counting CT (PCCT) has been shown to improve contrast-enhanced imaging,¹ but may also benefit unenhanced imaging without a contrast agent, such as gray-white matter differentiation, which is an important and frequent soft-tissue imaging task in brain CT to detect early signs of infarction.³ However, gray-white matter differentiation is also one of the most challenging CT imaging tasks because the contrast between gray and white matter is typically less than 10 HU.⁴

The purpose of the present study is to quantify the improvement offered by PCCT in unenhanced soft-tissue imaging, specifically for gray-white matter differentiation, comparing spectral PCCT, non-spectral PCCT, and conventional energy-integrating (EID) CT, where all other factors except the energy information are equal. As opposed to previous studies that were using cadmium-based PCCT detectors,^{3,5} we have investigated the potential benefit of deep-silicon detectors with relatively high energy resolution. It is a virtual study, which will be used to guide future phantom experiments and clinical trials.

B. METHODS

B1. A deep-silicon photon-counting detector

GE HealthCare has developed a prototype wide-coverage PCCT system based on silicon detectors.⁶ To reach a sufficient photon stopping power in the diagnostic energy range despite the relatively low atomic number of silicon, the silicon wafers are oriented in an edge-on geometry.¹ This sensor arrangement, several centimeters thick, is referred to as a deep-silicon sensor. When a photon interacts in the detector material, charge is released, which drifts as electron-hole pairs and is collected by electrodes on the sides of the sensors. The drift distance corresponds to the thickness of the sensor (not to the depth) and is therefore short, which minimizes spreading of the charge cloud. The collected charge generates a pulse with a height that is proportional to the energy of the photon, and comparators, implemented in an application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC), sort the detected pulses into eight energy bins.

Silicon is a non-toxic material with minimal impact on the environment, and silicon sensors can be produced from high-purity and high-quality elemental crystals using well-established manufacturing processes. In terms of energy resolution, silicon has several advantages, including high charge-collection efficiency, no K-fluorescence in the relevant energy range, and high intrinsic energy resolution. In addition, the relatively long interaction trajectories inherent to the deep-silicon design enables splitting of the electrodes into depth segments. Since each of these segments is connected to an independent ASIC channel, the count rate per channel is substantially reduced and the deep-silicon design therefore alleviates the need to shrink the pixel size below optimal levels to reach sufficiently low count-rate levels; for all photon-counting detectors, too small pixels result in increased pixel cross talk, which causes artefacts and reduced energy resolution.⁷ Tungsten foils

between the sensors block charge sharing and detector scatter, in addition to blocking object scatter, hence reducing cross talk further.

B2. A deep-silicon digital twin

We are developing a framework for digital twins of deep-silicon photon-counting detectors. The framework has been integrated into the CatSim platform, a detailed CT and x-ray simulation environment that has been developed at GE HealthCare over the last two decades.^{8,9} CatSim provides mechanics for simulating photon generation and filtration, a CT geometry with gantry rotation and patient table translation, and photon transport using ray tracing through a variety of software phantoms. A generic two-dimensional filtered-back-projection algorithm with a standard kernel was used for the single-slice reconstructions in this study. All imaging was at 120 kV and 300 mAs.

Detection in the framework is simulated by propagating the signal on the detector through an interaction efficiency matrix of the deep-silicon detector that has been generated using Monte-Carlo methods (GEANT4). The model simulates loss of energy to detector scatter, but it does not yet include energy loss to charge sharing, or pixel correlations, i.e. cross talk, caused by detector scatter or charge sharing. The framework contains a pileup model,¹⁰ but the effect was not included in this study.

A basic photon-counting image chain has been implemented in the framework, including a data-driven material-decomposition (MD) algorithm,¹¹ calibrated on a range of polyethylene (PE) and polyvinylchloride (PVC) slabs in combinations spanning the density and effective atomic numbers of the imaging objects.

B3. Simulated images and analysis

A digital twin of the deep-silicon photon-counting detector presented in Sec. B1 based on the framework from Sec. B2 was employed to image the two software phantoms shown in Figure 1: A 20-cm water phantom, and a skull phantom, each with two 2.8-cm diameter cylindrical inserts. The skull phantom was segmented from a spectral image of a physical skull phantom to make it spatially and spectrally accurate. Virtual monochromatic images (VMIs) of the phantoms were generated at a range of energies.

Figure 1: Images of the two software phantoms, each with gray and white matter inserts, that were used in this study. Window width / Window level = 100 HU / 40 HU.

Three imaging cases were considered: 1) Spectral PCCT, 2) non-spectral PCCT, and 3) conventional EID CT. To investigate brain matter differentiation, the two inserts in the software phantoms were, respectively, filled with gray and white brain matter, based on the elemental composition reported in Ref. 12. The contrast-to-noise ratio (CNR) between the two inserts were used as a figure of merit. To ensure comparability, the same simulated data set was used to generate images corresponding to all three imaging cases by selecting the appropriate VMI according to the following:

- 1) In spectral PCCT, the energy can be selected freely and the VMI that maximized the CNR between the two inserts was therefore chosen.
- 2) In non-spectral PCCT, all photons are weighted equally, which is optimal for density tasks without any spectral information, but non-optimal for any case with spectral information. To determine the appropriate VMI for this case, a pure density task was defined by filling the inserts of the water phantom with artificial water at two different densities, 1000 mg/ml and 1005 mg/ml. The VMI that maximized the CNR between the two inserts was selected.
- 3) In EID CT, higher-energy photons are assigned a higher weight because the detector signal is proportional to the photon energy. This intrinsic weighting scheme is generally non-optimal for soft-tissue imaging cases. A typical energy-integrating system was simulated using standard tools in the

CatSim platform and the VMI was selected that matched the contrast between the gray and white matter inserts in the EID image.

To validate the results presented here, we propose a phantom measurement with inserts that exhibit the correct linear attenuation as a function of energy. We propose to use a mixture of sodium chloride and glycol dissolved in water for the inserts. A mixture of these three easily obtainable materials is, in principle, sufficient to simulate the attenuation and density of any other material. The appropriate proportions were determined by a least-square fit of the linear attenuation of the mixture to that of gray and white matter in the energy range 20-120 keV.

C. RESULTS

The CNR of the density task was maximized at 61 keV, which corresponds to equal weighting of all photons and consequently determined the VMI for non-spectral PCCT. The contrast between the gray and white matter inserts matched the EID system at 66 keV and 68 keV for the water and skull phantoms, which determined the VMIs for conventional EID CT.

Table 1 lists the CNR values for 100 pixels measured between the gray and white matter inserts for the investigated imaging cases. In the water phantom, the CNR of brain matter was maximized at 55 keV, which is the optimal VMI for spectral PCCT with an increase in CNR of 17% relative to non-spectral PCCT and 59% compared to EID CT. Higher energies were preferred in the skull phantom because of filtration in bone, resulting in a maximum CNR at 58 keV. In this case, the CNR benefits of spectral PCCT compared to non-spectral PCCT and EID CT were 3% and 42%, respectively.

Figure 2 shows the linear attenuation of the mixtures proposed to mimic gray and white matter. The volumetric proportions of the phantom materials are listed in the figure legends. The differences in attenuation of the mixtures compared to gray and white matter were within 0.1% in the range 20-120 keV.

Table 1: The CNR of 100 pixels between the inserts with gray and white matter in the water and skull phantoms for the imaging cases considered in this study.

	Spectral PCCT		Non-spectral PCCT		EID CT	
	VMI	CNR	VMI	CNR	VMI	CNR
Water phantom	55 keV	2.31	61 keV	1.97	66 keV	1.45
Skull phantom	58 keV	2.28	61 keV	2.22	68 keV	1.60

Figure 2: Linear attenuation of the mixtures proposed for validating the results of this study, compared to brain matter. Logarithmic scales enhance the minute attenuation differences.

D. DISCUSSION

The results presented here were obtained without any image processing for reducing noise across the range of VMIs, which is otherwise a common procedure and would likely further improve the results for spectral PCCT.¹³ The pileup effect, which was not included in the simulation, will reduce the CNR of PCCT to some extent,¹⁰ but the cases investigated here are not high-pileup cases and we expect the impact of this simplification to be relatively small. Pixel cross talk was also not simulated and can be expected to reduce the CNR for all cases, PCCT and EID,¹ but since this investigation is mainly concerned with image areas that are larger than the typical range of cross talk, we expect the impact of excluding this effect to be limited.

Pourmorteza et al reported a 33% gray-white matter CNR improvement for non-spectral PCCT vs. EID.³ This benefit is only slightly lower than what we measured for the skull phantom, and the discrepancy appears reasonable given the differences between the studies. The study also noted that the CNR was higher in the low energy bin than in the high energy bin. It was therefore concluded that spectral information could improve the results, but no further analysis was carried out on that topic. However, Michael et al found that non-spectral PCCT (so-called polyenergetic reconstructions) outperformed spectral PCCT in terms of gray-white matter CNR.⁵ This result contradicts our findings; even though the benefit of spectral vs. non-spectral PCCT was small in the skull phantom, it was still positive. In fact, several other studies have shown that optimal energy weighting is expected to improve the CNR,² which leads us to believe that the results of Michael et al could be the consequence of non-linear image processing.

Artifacts, particularly in the skull base, is another challenge for neuro CT that could potentially be improved by spectral PCCT, which eliminates beam hardening artifacts.² That effect will be a topic of future studies.

E. CONCLUSIONS

We conclude that deep-silicon spectral PCCT has the potential to improve the CNR of unenhanced imaging of brain tissue by up to 59% compared to conventional techniques. Brain matter was simulated well with a mixture of three other easily obtainable materials, which will be used in a future phantom experiment to validate the results.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

E.F is an employee of GE HealthCare. M.P. has received funding from GE HealthCare. This work was partially funded by the Swedish Foundation for Strategic Research (grant number APR20-0012) and GE HealthCare.

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Beyond Registration Constraints: Simplicial Mesh Jump Diffusion for Virtual Aneurysm Population Synthesis

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

The rising cost of medical device development has placed a significant financial burden on healthcare systems and medical device companies [1]. A major factor causing such cost increase is the high failure rate in late-phase clinical trials, where many devices fail to reach the market after years of costly research and development [2]. In-silico trials, i.e., computer simulations that evaluate medical device performance on virtual patients [3], offer a promising solution [4]. By reducing reliance on animal and human testing, these trials can shorten study durations, lower costs, and minimise ethical concerns.

In-silico trials have successfully replicated the findings of conventional clinical trials for intracranial aneurysms treatment, and have provided new insights into treatment failures using virtual populations produced by segmentation and reconstruction of medical images [5]. Intracranial aneurysms are abnormal bulges in brain arteries that pose significant health risks due to the possibility to rupture, causing life-threatening hemorrhages. However, a major limitation of In-silico trials on digital twins [5] is the lack of anatomical diversity, as it is constrained by the high costs of imaging and post-processing. Consequently, clinically significant but rare cases, such as multiple intracranial aneurysms, remain under-represented. Recent advances in generative models have allowed for creating significantly larger and more diverse virtual populations by learning anatomical distributions from existing datasets [6]. Although techniques such as variational autoencoders [6], GANs [7], and diffusion models [8] can effectively synthesize organs in the form of template registered meshes (e.g., lungs, hearts, and livers) [9], the generation of organs with significantly large variation in shape and size remains challenging. This is because the aforementioned-methods [6,7,8] assume point-wise correspondence between subjects. However, in applications such as aneurysm and cerebral vessel generation, high inter-subject variability makes mesh registration infeasible, and requiring such point-wise correspondence limits the generating diversity when needing to learn from diverse datasets hard to register.

In this work, we propose Simplicial Mesh Jump Diffusion (SiMJD), which is a novel generative model for surface meshes. It is based on a diffusion process that allows transitions between different spatial dimensional states. Specifically, SiMJD proposes a dedicated jump process to improve the conventional diffusion model [10], enabling the synthesis of diverse anatomies without template registration. As a result, this improves in-silico trials by enabling more inclusive and representative evaluations of medical devices.

B. METHODS

1. Simplicial Mesh Jump Diffusion Model

Simplicial Mesh Jump Diffusion (SiMJD) proposes a jump mechanism that enables transitions between meshes of different graph structures, improving over the conventional diffusion frameworks that are more suitable for vector generation without explicit structures. Here, a surface mesh is modeled as a simplicial complex, i.e., a specialized graph that consists of nodes, edges, and faces [11]. A graph structure refers to connections between vertices, which is represented by an adjacency matrix.

Figure 1 Architecture of the proposed simplicial mesh jump diffusion model.

In the forward process, SiMJJD continuously applies a two-step transition to convert an aneurysm mesh to a simplified noise (Figure 1). Within each transition, first, a jump step simplifies the graph structure of an aneurysm through an edge-collapse operation, selectively merging vertices and edges within the aneurysm region while preserving the graph structure of the feeding vasculature (Figure 2). Then, a diffusion step follows to introduce Gaussian noise to vertex coordinates, gradually collapsing the geometric detail while maintaining the current graph structure. After applying a sufficient number of transitions to an aneurysm mesh, the graph structure collapses to a single vertex, while the vertex coordinates collapse to a normal distribution.

The backward process reverses the forward transitions, simultaneously denoising the vertex coordinates and reconstructing the graph structure. A denoising neural network is used to predict the noise component. A backward jump mechanism is used to up-sample the mesh and restore the original graph structure through conducting an edge-split and an edge-flip operations. The goal is to ensure that the reconstructed aneurysm meshes remain anatomically plausible and capable of capturing real-world variations.

The forward and backward jump process within each transition (as illustrated in the grey box of Figure 1) is regulated by a jump ratio $\bar{\lambda}_t \in [0, 1]$. At each step, a random number is drawn from a uniform distribution over $[0, 1]$, if the value exceeds $\bar{\lambda}_t$, a jump occurs. An edge mask predicts which edges are eligible for the collapse, split, and flip operations. The forward jump ratio $\bar{\lambda}_t(n_0)$ is formulated as a function of the initial vertex number n_0 . The function is designed to enable larger meshes to receive higher jump ratios to facilitate more aggressive downsampling. The backward jump ratio is defined to be proportional to the forward jump ratio, i.e., $\bar{\lambda}_t(\hat{n}_0) = \gamma_t \bar{\lambda}_t(\hat{n}_0)$, where \hat{n}_0 is the predicted vertex number of the restored graph, i.e., vertex number at time 0, and γ_t quantifies the ratio between two conditional probabilities of $P_t(n_t + 1 | \hat{n}_0)$ and $P_t(n_t | \hat{n}_0)$, formulated as $\frac{P_t(n_t + 1 | \hat{n}_0)}{P_t(n_t | \hat{n}_0)}$.

Figure 2 An illustration of the forward and backward jump processes.

2. Implementation

Loss function: SiMJD is trained using three key loss components, including a mean-squared error loss to ensure accurate vertex denoising, a binary cross-entropy loss to guide edge selection during mesh up-sampling, and another mean-squared error loss to predict the vertex number in the final generated mesh.

Backbone network: We exploit different features for characterising each simplex dimension: (1) coordinates, Gaussian curvature, and mean curvature for vertices; (2) Euclidean distances and dihedral angles for edges; and (3) outward normal vectors and face areas for faces. The backbone of the backward predictor is a Hodge-Laplacian heterogeneous graph attention network (HL-HGAT) [11], extended with a UNet-like [12] structure for enhanced mesh reconstruction. This allows SiMJD to generate high-quality, anatomically realistic aneurysm meshes with diverse topologies, significantly advancing the generation quality of synthetic virtual patient populations for in-silico trials.

Dataset: The AneuX morphology database is an open-access, multi-center repository containing 3D geometric models of 750 intracranial aneurysms [13]. Curated during the AneuX project, it integrates data from three sources: AneuX, Aneurist, and Aneurisk. It offers various mesh resolutions and cut configurations, along with clinical parameters and pre-computed morphometric indices for each aneurysm dome. It serves as a valuable resource for morphological analysis and computational studies of intracranial aneurysms.

C. RESULTS

After training the SiMJD, we apply its forward process to 100 aneurysm samples from the AneuX datasets, which are excluded from the training process. Each sample is collapsed to a noise by iteratively applying the edge collapse operation until the aneurysm dome reaches a single vertex. Starting from this vertex noise, we generate a new aneurysm by applying the trained backward process of SiMJD. The results are shown below:

Figure 3 Example aneurysm surface meshes generated from feeding systems sampled from the testing set.

D. DISCUSSION

Existing template-based methods, such as variational autoencoders (VAEs), generate new anatomies by predicting vertex coordinates or their deformations based on a pre-defined template [6,8]. However, in applications lacking a well-defined template, it is essential to generate not only the vertex coordinates but also

the graph structure. The proposed method addresses this challenge through a jump process that autoregressively up-samples the graph. Although the results have been qualitatively validated, this study currently lacks quantitative evaluations to assess the diversity and plausibility of the generated virtual population. Furthermore, because the proposed method preserves topology and is applicable to surface mesh generation in a general sense, there is potential to demonstrate its effectiveness by validating on a broader range of datasets.

E. CONCLUSION

This study proposes an effective generative model SiMJD, enabling to generate synthetic aneurysm meshes without relying on any template registration. Qualitative results show that our method can successfully synthesize aneurysms conditioned on a given feeding system. This approach addresses the longstanding challenge of generating organ anatomies without clear point-wise correspondence between samples.

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1046-Foundational Model For Source Agnostic Cerebral Vessel Segmentation

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Cerebral vessel segmentation models perform well when trained and tested within the same modality or institution. However, their performance significantly degrades when deployed across different data sources due to domain shifts.

To address this, we propose a domain-agnostic foundational segmentation framework that enables robust vessel segmentation across diverse imaging datasets without requiring domain-specific fine-tuning. Our method integrates labelled and unlabelled data from different modalities, leveraging transwarp contrastive learning and gradient alignment techniques to bridge the distribution gap between domains. By learning a source-agnostic representation, the model generalizes effectively across multiple unseen target domains. Our method highlights the potential of source-agnostic medical image segmentation, providing a more generalizable and scalable solution for multi-centre and multi-modal cerebral vessel applications. This research contributes to the development of robust deep-learning models that can be effectively deployed in real-world clinical settings, enhancing the reliability of creating digital twins for insilico trials.

Developing an *in silico* pipeline for ventilation MRI-based modelling of particle deposition in the lungs of people with cystic fibrosis

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Computational models of inhaled particle deposition are increasingly used for optimising drug delivery. However, existing approaches are often unsuitable in the presence of significant ventilation heterogeneity, which occurs due to airway blockage and inflammation in cystic fibrosis (CF) lung disease. Inhaled therapies for CF such as antibiotics and emerging genetic therapies act locally at the deposition site, so it is important to understand how individual ventilation distribution and disease pathophysiology affect regional particle deposition. We outline a novel approach to incorporate multi-modal MRI data into a reduced-order whole-lung deposition model, which we test by simulating aerosol bolus dispersion (ABD) experiments, imposing acinar ventilation rates with synthetic ventilation MRI data. We then simulate the effects of CF pathophysiology by imposing airway constrictions, comparing to experimental results in the literature to identify necessary improvements.

B. METHODS

1. Lung networks

1H lung images were collected by the POLARIS group at the University of Sheffield. ITK-SNAP was used to segment left and right lung masks, and the airway tree down to the lobar airways, from which airway centrelines were extracted using the Vascular Modelling Toolkit in 3D Slicer. A space-filling branching algorithm was used to generate the remaining airways within the segmented lung masks [1].

2. Ventilation and particle deposition model

The ventilation and deposition model are substantially the same as [2]. The airway tree is modelled as a network of coupled cylindrical pipes, where edges represent the airways and nodes the junctions between them. We assume a linear relationship between the pressure drop and flow rate along each edge

$$\mathbf{Np} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{r})\mathbf{q},$$

where \mathbf{N} is the incidence matrix of the network, \mathbf{p} is the vector of node pressures, \mathbf{r} is the vector of edge resistances (given by Poiseuille's law) and \mathbf{q} is the vector of edge fluxes. Flow rates throughout the network can be computed given boundary conditions on the terminal node (i.e. those with no child nodes) pressures \mathbf{p}_{term} , by modelling the acini as independent linear elastic bags subject to a uniform pleural pressure $P_{\text{pl}}(t)$

Figure 1 a) Left - 1D lung network generated from a 1H UTE MRI image. b) Right - 2D slices through 3D synthetic ventilation maps with varying ventilation heterogeneity (VH) and defect size (λ_d).

$$R \frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{v}_{\text{term}} + K \mathbf{v}_{\text{term}} = \mathbf{p}_{\text{term}} - \mathbf{1}_{\text{term}} P_{\text{pl}}(t),$$

where R and K are the resistance and elastance of the bags respectively, assumed equal for all acini, and \mathbf{v}_{term} and $\mathbf{1}_{\text{term}}$ are vectors of acinar volumes and ones respectively. The flow rates are then used to calculate the transport and deposition of inhaled particles. The original network is rediscritised by replacing each edge by a series of finite volume elements representing cylindrical slices along the airway. The acinar airways are modelled as symmetric trees appended to the original terminal nodes, with a constant inner volume representing the acinar ducts, and a time-dependent outer volume representing the alveolar space, over which the acinar volume \mathbf{v}_{term} is distributed. Particle transport is approximated using the 1D advection-dispersion-reaction (ADR) equation

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = D_{\text{eff}} \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} - S(c)$$

where x is the distance along the airway, $c(x, t)$ is the cross-sectional average particle concentration, u is the mean flow velocity, D_{eff} is the effective dispersion coefficient, and S is a sink term representing the local particle deposition rate. Empirical formulae are used for the effective diffusivities in the conducting and acinar airways and the deposition loss terms as in [2]. A semi-Lagrangian finite volume numerical scheme is used to solve the AR and D processes separately in each simulation timestep. The AR process is solved first in a Lagrangian step where volumes are moved through the network and particle deposition calculated accordingly. Volumes traversing bifurcations are either split or merged (assuming instant well-mixing) depending on the local flow conditions. The D process is then solved on the updated network of finite volumes using the numerical Green's function method described in [3].

3. Synthetic 129Xe ventilation maps

Synthetic 129Xe ventilation maps are used to thoroughly test the image-to-model pipeline while data collection is ongoing, though future studies will incorporate real 129Xe ventilation images from the MAGNIFY study. These are generated by defining a scalar field of Perlin noise $\phi(\mathbf{x}, \lambda_d)$ over the bounding volume of the lung network with length scale λ_d , as shown in figure 1b) [4]. The ventilation calculation is modified to impose the terminal fluxes $\mathbf{q}_{\text{term}} = \frac{q_1}{N_{\text{term}}} \hat{\Phi}_{\text{term}}$, where q_1 is the flux at the mouth, N_{term} is the number of terminal nodes, and $\hat{\Phi}_{\text{term}} = \exp(VH \cdot \phi(\mathbf{x}_{\text{term}}, \lambda_d))$ is the vector of values of ϕ at the terminal node positions \mathbf{x}_{term} , transformed to be lognormally distributed with scale parameter VH , which controls the contrast between poorly- and well-ventilated regions, as shown in figure 1b).

4. Simulated aerosol bolus dispersion experiments

In silico ABD experiments were performed approximating the protocol of [5], with a 1L inspiration from FRC (2.1L) at a constant flow rate of 0.5L/s, followed by a 2L expiration at the same flow rate. 100ml boluses of 3 μ m monodisperse particles were injected into the tidal volume at penetration volumes $V_p = 150\text{ml}$, 500ml and 800ml,

defined as the volume between the bolus midpoint and the end of inhalation. The returning bolus concentration was measured during exhalation, as shown in figure 2. The bolus deposition fraction D , dispersion H and mode shift MS were calculated as follows:

$$D = 1 - \frac{A_{ex}}{A_{in}}, \quad H = \sqrt{H_{ex}^2 - H_{in}^2}, \quad MS = M_{ex} - V_p,$$

where $A_{in/ex}$ are the areas under the in/exhaled concentration curves; $H_{in/ex}$ are the FWHM of the in/exhaled concentration curves; and M_{ex} is the volume between the start of exhalation and the exhaled bolus mode.

Figure 2 – Particle concentration measured at the mouth for 3 ABD runs, illustrating how the returning bolus concentration profiles change with respect to penetration volume.

ABD experiments were repeated for small and large ventilation defects, firstly using ventilation maps ($\lambda_d = 20\text{mm}$, 100mm), and then by applying distal (Horsfield order 0-5) and intermediate (Horsfield order 6-11) airway constrictions, with uniform random severity of 0-90% reduction in lumen radius. To give physiologically relevant values for ventilation defect percentage (VDP), defined as the number of acini with a ventilation rate < 0.3 of the mean, VH was varied from 0.7-1.3 for the ventilation maps, and the fraction of airways in the selected generations constricted was varied from 0.2-0.6.

C. RESULTS

Figure 3 shows the ABD results at $V_p = 800\text{ml}$. Deposition increases with VDP for both methods, as expected, although this effect is more pronounced for the case where constrictions are applied. The predicted dispersion values unexpectedly decrease with VDP, though this likely reflects that the FWHM is a poor measure of the skewed bolus when deposition is high. When airway constrictions are applied, the expected negative bolus mode shift is observed, but is significantly underestimated when ventilation maps are applied (c.f. [5]).

Figure 3 – Exhaled bolus parameters wrt. VDP at $V_p = 800\text{ml}$, where ventilation defects have been applied separately using ventilation maps and airway constrictions.

D. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated methods for incorporating structural and functional lung MRI data into a path-based particle deposition model to perform ABD experiments *in silico*. We have shown that ventilation asynchrony and heterogeneity are both necessary to explain experimental results. These results suggest that while this model pipeline is a feasible way to predict overall particle deposition in healthy lungs, it does not accurately capture aerosol dynamics for people with obstructive lung conditions. Well-established CT-based methods use the assumption of synchronous ventilation [6], however, these results suggest that more disease-specific approaches to interpret imaging data are required to accurately capture the dynamics [7]. This will be the focus of our next steps in pipeline development.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This study "MAGNIFY SRC: Pulmonary Magnetic Resonance Imaging for Cystic Fibrosis" is funded by the CF Trust and CF Foundation. C.A.W. and A.H. are supported by the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Manchester Biomedical Research Centre (BRC) (NIHR203308). A.H. and C.A.W. are supported by the EPSRC Network Plus 'BIOREME' (EP/W000490/1). The views expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the CF Trust, the CF Foundation, the NIHR, or the EPSRC. We declare no competing interests.

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1048-VIT for MVP the role of virtual imaging in healthcare startup ecosystem

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Academic research in applied sciences is a cornerstone of innovative scientific discovery, yet commercialization in healthcare remains challenging due to heavy regulatory pathways, lengthy testing through clinical trials, significant R&D and market penetration costs. This significantly hampers the creation and survival of new health-tech providers (startups), ultimately denying potential benefits for patients. Funding for clinical translation is often a “chicken and egg” type of situation. From one side, venture capital firms (investors) seek investment de-risking activities, such as development of a minimal viable product (MVP) tested in clinical settings with a defined regulatory path. On the other side, MVP development, particularly for AI-based healthcare solutions, relies heavily on medical data access, which is often restricted, outdated, or over-processed.

Virtual imaging platforms, such as the one developed at the Center for Virtual Imaging Trials at Duke University, USA, were primarily designed for the task of optimization and clinical testing of new medical imaging technology. Fast and cheap data generation with access to ground truth makes them also valuable for commercial AI development and validation.

A case study of an early-stage startup developing an AI-based medical imaging software showed that using the DukeSim platform, data generation costs were reduced by 90% compared to acquiring hospital-provided data. Virtual imaging costs are mostly related to the costs of GPU-accelerated computing on cloud-based platforms, while the costs of a traditional approach are related to the administrative and legal fees required to design a compliant data transfer. Generating a correct virtual CT scan in-house took 22 days, with subsequent scans completed in hours, compared to 11 months for clinical data acquisition.

While diversity of anthropomorphic patients limits the full application of AI algorithms in clinical settings, hybrid approaches combining clinical and simulated data and further development of imaging simulators are expected to bridge this gap.

Physiological Parameter-Driven Echocardiography Synthesis: Towards Pre-Training of Foundation Models for Cardiac Disease Diagnosis

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1. Background and purpose

Echocardiography has been widely used for cardiac assessment due to its real-time and non-invasive feature. However, acquiring large-scale, high-quality, dynamic ultrasound images with labeling is time-consuming and laborious, which severely restricts the development of deep learning-based cardiac diagnostic foundation models^[1]. In recent years, Statistical Shape Models (SSM), which is capable of generating deformable cardiac models with anatomical information of real cardiac MRI sequences, has provided new possibilities for describing the heart^[2].

Recently, several label map-based synthesis has been developed to generate pseudo medial images. For example, paired CT-MRI conversion can be done using stable diffusion^[3]. Researchers have also controlled cardiac ultrasound video generation with multimodal inputs (sketches, label maps and text) derived from original scans^[4]. However, such paired data are often difficult to obtain in echocardiography tasks. While label-to-image translation techniques on unpaired data such as CycleGAN have shown promise in medical image synthesis^[5, 6], their outputs often suffer from structural distortion or texture artifacts.

This work introduces a novel synthetic pipeline that addresses these challenges through two main contributions:

1. A physiology-driven Statistical Shape Model (SSM) is used for echocardiography synthesis to enable controllable variation in anatomical and motion parameters, such as chamber volume, ventricle wall thickness, ejection fraction, and percentage of systolic phase.
2. An enhanced Rectified Flow model with inverse ordinary differential equation (ODE) supervision—unlike the original Rectified Flow method^[7], we explicitly supervise the reverse generation process, guiding the backward trajectory to preserve structural consistency while synthesizing realistic ultrasound textures.

2. Method

Our proposed synthetic pipeline consists of four main stages, as illustrated in Figure. 1. First, SSM generation creates anatomical label maps based on physiological parameters. These are then transformed into pseudo-ultrasound images using CycleGAN-based synthesis. A VAE verification step ensures stable encoding by minimizing the reconstruction error of the generated images. Finally, Rectified Flow with inverse supervision refines textures and preserves structural fidelity.

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed four-stage synthetic pipeline.

2.1 Statistical Shape Model and Label Map Generation

We adopt a dynamic statistical cardiac atlas proposed in previous work, which was constructed from real cardiac Computed Tomography Angiography (CTA) sequences. The atlas is based on a statistical spatiotemporal model of whole heart shape and motion pattern, allowing flexible adjustment of both morphological and temporal parameters, such as ventricle volumes, ventricle wall thickness, cardiac cycle, ejection fraction, etc.^[2]

Figure 2: Shape changes corresponding to the variations of four deformation parameters in the Statistical Shape Model.

Using this model, we generate a set of 141 distinct 3D cardiac structures that span the entire cardiac cycle. These volumetric models are sliced into 2D planes to generate cross-sectional label maps containing anatomical regions of interest (e.g., ventricular chambers, interventricular septum). Each label map is paired with associated physiological parameters (e.g., chamber volume, ejection fraction, wall thickness), providing semantically meaningful inputs for image synthesis.

All label maps are preprocessed with noise injection and grayscale normalization to ensure input consistency across the pipeline.

2.2 CycleGAN-Based Pseudo Image Generation

We employ an unpaired image-to-image translation framework based on CycleGAN to map label maps (domain X) to pseudo-ultrasound-like grayscale images (domain Y). The framework includes two generators $G: X \rightarrow Y, F: Y \rightarrow X$ and two discriminators D_X and D_Y , optimized using adversarial and cycle-consistency losses.

The output $y_{pseudo} = G(x)$ contains preliminary texture characteristics of ultrasound images, albeit with noticeable artifacts or unrealistic features.

2.3 VAE-Based Reconstruction

We train a variational autoencoder (VAE) on real echocardiography frames and observe that CycleGAN’s coarse pseudo-ultrasound images yield low ℓ_2 reconstruction loss, while raw anatomical label maps—lacking speckle texture—produce high loss and distorted outputs. By retaining only those samples with sufficiently low reconstruction error, our VAE verification guarantees that inputs to the subsequent diffusion-based style transfer possess both coherent anatomy and plausible ultrasound textures.

2.4 Style Transfer with Rectified Flow

To convert pseudo grayscale images into realistic echocardiographic textures, we used a diffusion-based method inspired by Rectified Flow. However, the original Rectified Flow method does not guarantee structural fidelity in the output image, likely due to the lack of supervision in the reverse generation path. We addressed this by adding backward reconstruction supervision during training, enforcing cycle consistency between forward and reverse processes. This helped to maintain anatomical structure and improved texture realism. In this way, our improved method produced clearer boundaries and more realistic speckle noise, providing a foundation for downstream tasks like parameter regression and foundation model training.

3 Result

We evaluated our proposed method on a synthetic dataset, focusing on image quality, structural fidelity. A total of 96 pairs of synthetic grayscale and real echocardiography images were used, and we employed Fréchet Inception Distance (FID)^[8], introduced by Heusel et al., for quantitative assessment.

In quantitative evaluation, the baseline CycleGAN model yielded a high FID score of 193.88 on 96 paired samples, indicating a large discrepancy in grayscale and texture distribution compared to real echocardiography. With our Rectified Flow style transfer method, the FID further improved to 149.81, demonstrating closer alignment with real ultrasound speckle patterns and anatomical structures. Through visual inspection, the modified Rectified Flow-generated single frames preserved clear myocardial boundaries and ventricular contours while exhibiting realistic speckle noise, markedly outperforming the CycleGAN-only outputs.

Overall, the proposed pipeline achieves better realism and structure preservation than conventional methods, offering a reliable foundation for large-scale synthetic echocardiography dataset generation.

Figure 3. Exemplar synthesis results. Each row corresponds to one echocardiographic view: apex (APEX), apical four-chamber (A4C), and parasternal long-axis (PLAX). The four columns are Label: Semantic label map generated by the statistical shape model, indicating ventricular chambers, septum, etc.; Noise injection: Label map with noise injection and grayscale conversion used as input to CycleGAN; CycleGAN: Pseudo ultrasound-style output from the baseline CycleGAN, showing notable discrepancies in grayscale and texture; Ours: Results of our Rectified Flow-based style transfer, exhibiting both structural fidelity and realistic speckle patterns.

4 Discussion

The SSM built from real MRI provides accurate anatomical priors, greatly improving structural fidelity and downstream model generalization. Inverse supervision addresses the lack of cycle consistency in standard diffusion models by imposing reconstruction constraints during the reverse pass, leading to higher-quality, structure-preserving style transfers. However, a key limitation of the current approach is that it is limited to the generation of static images. Future work will focus on leveraging the temporal parameters of the SSM within a conditional diffusion framework to generate full-cycle cardiac videos with physiological coherence and cycle consistency.

5 Conclusion

We presented a synthesis pipeline for echocardiographic image generation: from SSM-based anatomical modeling and CycleGAN pseudo-ultrasound synthesis, to VAE verification for texture consistency, and finally Rectified Flow with inverse supervision for realistic style transfer. Our method outperforms traditional approaches in anatomical consistency and ultrasound texture realism. Future research will investigate end-to-end temporal generation, and will fine-tune downstream cardiac diagnosis models to evaluate the clinical utility of the synthetic data.

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Predictive Quality of Body Size Measurands for Radiation Risk Estimation Across CT Protocols

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Computed tomography (CT) plays a central role in modern healthcare, highly affecting how clinicians diagnose and treat diseases.¹ Diagnostic performances are strictly related to the quality of the radiological images which is dictated by the radiation output of the device. A fundamental determinant of both image quality and radiation dose is patient size.² Different patients require different radiation levels to achieve comparable image quality, depending on their body habitus. According to the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), effective dose from a CT scan can vary by a factor of ten or more, depending on patient size, demographics, scan region, and scanner operation.³ Despite this known variability, it remains unclear which size metric should be used and how that influences scanner output and risk across patient populations. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the predictive potential of different patient size metrics for estimating CT radiation risk using virtual imaging trials (VITs) framework.

B. METHODS

A total of six virtual adult patients were selected from the XCAT phantom library (Duke University) to represent a diverse range of body habitus.^{4,5} The cohort included one female and five males, with ages ranging from 26 to 63 years, heights from 162.7 to 190.0 cm, and weights from 63.7 to 94.2 kg, covering body mass index (BMI) classifications from normal to obese. To expand body shape diversity while maintaining consistent height, two phantoms were derived from an existing model by adding adipose tissue to the chest, abdomen, and pelvis regions, resulting in larger body diameter while preserving internal anatomy.

CT scans were simulated using DukeSim, a validated scanner-specific simulator configured to replicate the physical and geometric characteristics of a typical SOMATOM Definition Flash system (Siemens Healthineers).^{4,5} Four anatomical regions including head, neck, head and neck (HN), and chest regions were simulated using both fixed tube current and tube current modulation (TCM). TCM simulations were performed using two strength settings – average and strong. Each condition was simulated with ten exposure levels (50, 70, 90, 120, 170, 220, 300, 400, 550, and 750 mA) to evaluate a wide range of mA values, including those beyond typical clinical levels.

Organ doses were calculated for each scan and used to compute two radiation risk metrics: effective dose (E) and Risk Index (RI). E was determined based on tissue-weighted organ doses following the ICRP Publication 103 definition.⁶ RI was calculated using BEIR VII tissue risk coefficients to reflect patient-specific radiation sensitivity.^{7,8}

Patient size was characterized using weight and BMI. Moreover, effective diameter (D_E) and water-equivalent diameter (D_W) were calculated for each slice and reported as average ($D_{Eaverage}$, $D_{Waverage}$), median ($D_{Emedian}$, $D_{Wmedian}$), and center ($D_{Ecenter}$, $D_{Wcenter}$) values across the imaging volume.

To assess the predictive quality of each metric, exponential regression models were fitted between radiation risk estimates (E and RI) and each size metric. Model performance was evaluated across anatomical region and exposure condition (fixed mA, TCM-average, TCM-strong), using normalized root mean square error (nRMSE).

C. RESULTS

The performance of patient size metrics in predicting effective dose (E) and risk index (RI) varied across anatomical regions and TCM settings. As shown in Figures 1, all size metrics performed similarly in predicting E in the chest region. However, for RI prediction, D_W metrics yielded the lowest errors. In the HN region (Figure 2), average and median metrics of D_W and D_E provided the best predictions for E, while BMI and $D_{E_{average}}$ showed the lowest nRMSE values for RI. In the head region (Figure 3), E and RI exhibited similar trends across size metrics, although the magnitude of prediction error slightly differed. Center-based metrics ($D_{E_{center}}$, $D_{W_{center}}$) showed the highest prediction error for both E and RI. In contrast, the neck region (Figure 4) demonstrated a different pattern. BMI showed the highest error for E prediction, while center-based metrics were among the most predictive for RI, with the lowest nRMSE values.

Figure 1. nRMSE distribution for E and RI in the chest region across size metrics, mA levels, and TCM strength.

Figure 2. nRMSE distribution for E and RI in the HN region across size metrics, mA levels, and TCM strength.

Figure 3. nRMSE distribution for E and RI in the head region across size metrics, mA levels, and TCM strength.

Figure 4. nRMSE distribution for E and RI in the neck region across size metrics, mA levels, and TCM strength.

D. DISCUSSION

This study shows that the ability of patient size metrics to predict radiation risk varies by anatomical region and TCM setting; no single metric performs consistently well in all scenarios. D_E and D_W generally outperform weight and BMI, but their predictive accuracy differs depending on the body region and risk metric. Importantly, RI often captures differences in patient-specific sensitivity that are not evident in E, highlighting its added value for individualized risk assessment. In this study, VITs offer a realistic representation of patient sizes and shapes, providing valuable insights on assessing the predictive qualities of patient size metrics related to radiation risk estimates.

E. CONCLUSION

CT radiation risk predictability varies even within the same size metric and is dependent upon anatomical region, protocol, and TCM settings. Individualized methods offer the most accurate risk estimates and should be prioritized when feasible. When individualization is not possible, selecting the appropriate size metric is crucial for risk prediction optimality. Finally, VITs enable the evaluation of TCM performance to inform prospective individualized risk assessment.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT AND CONFLICT OF INTREST

This work was supported by the National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering of the National Institutes of Health under award number P41-EB028744 and R44EB031658.

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4D Patient-Specific Whole-Heart Mesh Reconstruction with Myocardial Weak Incompressibility from Cardiac Time-Series CTA Images

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain the leading cause of death globally, with mortality rates consistently ranking at the top¹. Reconstructing patient-specific cardiac geometric models is clinically helpful for CVDs diagnosis and treatment². The traditional multi-stage approach to reconstruct cardiac geometric models is usually labor-intensive and time-consuming. Although recent advances in graph convolutional network (GCN) have demonstrated significant potential for reconstructing whole-heart models from medical images³, research on 4D whole-heart mesh reconstruction remains limited.

In this paper, we proposed a 4D patient-specific whole-heart mesh reconstruction network (RecNet4D) that generates dynamic heart models from time-series CTA images. Our proposed method uses a 3D convolutional neural network (CNN) to encode image features, and uses multiple template iterative deformation modules (TIDMs) to deform the mesh template into the patient-specific mesh. On this basis, utilizing the weak incompressible property of myocardial tissue, we constrain the myocardial volume variance to ensure the consistency throughout the cardiac cycle.

B. METHODS

The pipeline of our RecNet4D is shown in Figure 1(a). As shown, a 3D CNN is used to encode the input time-series CTA images into global features $F_{1\sim n}^g$ and local features $F_{1\sim n}^l$, and then $(k+n-1)$ TIDMs with the same parameters are employed to deform the mesh template into patient-specific mesh $V_{k\sim k+n-1}^{pred}$. Except for the first frame mesh V_k^{pred} , which is predicted by using k TIDMs ($k=3$ in our experiments), the meshes V_i^{pred} are obtained by deforming the previous predicted mesh V_{i-1}^{pred} using one TIDM. Therefore, we can modify our RecNet4D into a 3D version (RecNet3D) easily, and thus pre-train our RecNet4D using 3D images. The RecNet3D is shown in Figure 1(b), which consists of one 3D CNN and k TIDMs.

As shown in Figure 1(c), our TIDM uses a sampler to trilinear interpolate the global and local features, and then concatenates these features with a 384-dimensional Fourier feature⁴ F^f as the final GCN node features. As shown, our TIDM consists of 3 down-sampling GCN⁵ layers and 2 nested graph residual blocks (GResBlocks), which comprise 2 GCNs with skip connections⁶. The output channels from 3 GCN layers are 256, 64, and 3, respectively. We use *biharmonic coordinates*⁷ to compute the linear mapping W between the control points QV^{tmp} and the template vertices V^{tmp} to avoid unreasonable deformations³. Therefore, the predicted vertex can be computed by $V_n^{pred} = WQ(V_{n-1}^{pred} + \Delta X)$ during the training process. Here, Q is a binary selector matrix indicating the rows of the control points within the template vertices, and ΔX represents the predicted displacement.

The loss function during the pre-training stage can be expressed as $L_{pre-training} = L_{seg} + L_{geo}(V_k^{gcn}, G) + L_{geo}(V_k^{pred}, G) + \|(V_k^{gcn} - V_k^{pred})\|_2^2$, where $L_{geo}(V_k^{gcn}, G)$ and $L_{geo}(V_k^{pred}, G)$ is the geometric loss between the

GCN output mesh vertices $V_k^{gcn} = V_k^{tmp} + \Delta X$ and the shape deformation mesh vertices V_k^{pred} by control points, and the ground-truth mesh vertices G , respectively. Here, the geometric loss is composed of the Chamfer distance loss L_{cd} and the normal loss L_{nm} , i.e. $L_{geo}(V, G) = L_{cd}^{\lambda_1}(V, G) + L_{nm}^{\lambda_2}(V, G)$, segmentation loss L_{seg} is the sum of cross-entropy and Dice loss. During the fine-tuning stage, the 3D CNN was frozen and the fine-tuning loss can be expressed as $L_{fine-tuning} = \sum_{i=1}^{k+n-1} (L_{geo}(V_i^{gcn}, G) + L_{geo}(V_i^{pred}, G) + \|(V_i^{gcn} - V_i^{pred})\|_2^2) + \lambda_3 \sum_{i=1}^n (V_i - \bar{V})$, where V_i denotes the myocardium (Myo) volume by a differentiable volume formula⁸ and \bar{V} denotes the average over the entire cardiac cycle. The hyperparameters $\lambda_{1\sim 3}$ in our experiments are set to 0.3, 0.46 and 0.001, respectively.

Figure 1. Overview of our proposed 4D patient-specific whole-heart mesh reconstruction network (RecNet4D). (a) The overall architecture of RecNet4D. (b) The 3D version of our ResNet4D (RecNet3D). (c) The structure of our Template Iterative Deformation Module (TIDM).

C. EXPERIMENTS

1. Dataset and Preprocessing

We used 20 CTA images from the MMWHS⁹ training dataset with expert-annotated labels for seven cardiac structures: left ventricle (LV), Myo, right ventricle (RV), left atrium (LA), right atrium (RA), aorta (AO), and pulmonary artery (PA). Additionally, we employed 42 time-series (dynamic) CTA images (20 frames each) from healthy subjects. All the dynamic CTA images were de-identified and previously collected for other purposes. For RecNet3D, 16 images from MMWHS and 26 dynamic images were used for pre-training, and 4 images from MMWHS and 8 dynamic images were used for validation, respectively. For RecNet4D, only dynamic images were used for fine-tuning and validation. Each image from the MMWHS was augmented to generate 60 images using the same augmentation methods described in ³. All images were intensity-normalized to $[-1,1]$ and were resized to $128 \times 128 \times 128$ using trilinear interpolation before input into the network.

2. Results

Table 1 shows the Dice similarity coefficient (DSC) and Hausdorff distance (HD) of our RecNet3D and RecNet4D on both individual cardiac structures and the whole-heart (WH) in the test dataset. As shown, our method achieves accurate reconstruction for most heart structures, with DSC reaching 95.24% and HD of 16.63 mm in WH, demonstrating the efficacy of our proposed model. Under the constraint of myocardial volume invariance, our RecNet4D achieves higher reconstruction accuracy on both DSC and HD. Figure 2 displays the first frame of the 4D meshes reconstructed by RecNet4D. An example of a 4D whole-heart mesh reconstructed using our RecNet4D is shown in Figure 4.

Table 1 Quantitative results of our RecNet3D and RecNet4D on both individual structures and the whole-heart (WH) on the test dynamic CTA images.

Metrics	Models	LV	Myo	RV	LA	RA	AO	PA	WH
DSC (% , \uparrow)	RecNet3D	96.37	94.17	95.19	95.51	94.52	95.00	90.97	95.15
	RecNet4D	96.45	94.20	95.35	95.95	94.04	95.64	91.62	95.24
HD (mm, \downarrow)	RecNet3D	8.30	13.39	11.99	6.41	7.56	8.37	9.26	16.62
	RecNet4D	9.10	13.21	11.53	6.59	9.04	8.93	8.75	16.63

To further evaluate the reconstruction performance of RecNet3D and RecNet4D, we compute the coefficient of variation (CV)—defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean—to assess the stability of Myo reconstruction. As shown in Figure 3, RecNet4D achieves a lower CV than RecNet3D across most dynamic CTA images, suggesting that our proposed RecNet4D produces more physiologically plausible Myo reconstructions.

Figure 2. Reconstruction results of our proposed RecNet4D on test images. All the results presented are the first frame of the reconstructed 4D whole-heart mesh models.

Figure 3. An example of a 4D patient-specific whole-heart mesh model reconstructed by our RecNet4D.

Figure 4. Comparison of the coefficient of variation (CV) in Myo reconstruction across different methods. The horizontal axis indicates the image ID in the test dataset.

D. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The quantitative and qualitative results show that our proposed 4D patient-specific whole-heart mesh reconstruction network can accurately reconstruct the models. Moreover, our reconstructed 4D models can accurately reflect cardiac behavior, providing reliable support for personalized clinical treatment of CVDs in the future. Inevitably, our work also has some limitations, as we are constrained only to the Myo volume rather than all cardiac structures. In the future, we plan to incorporate more physical rules of cardiac motion to enhance the temporal and spatial consistency throughout the cardiac cycle.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the Joint Funds of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. U24A20753), the general program of National Natural Science Fund of China (No. 81971693), the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (No. DUT22YG229), the funding of Liaoning Key Lab of IC & BME System and Dalian Engineering Research Center for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging.

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An Automated Positioning Framework for Medical Imaging Scans: Personalized Whole-Body Digital Anatomical Model Construction Based on Optical Photo

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Tomography scans are indispensable auxiliary tools in modern medical diagnostics, but radiological scans carry potential risks of ionizing radiation, and there are clear limits to the number of scans a human body can safely undergo^[1]. Therefore, accurate organ localization prior to CT/MRI scanning becomes a critical step in reducing patients' radiation exposure risks and easing physicians' workload. Precise organ localization plays a decisive role in dynamically optimizing scanning parameters, such as radiation dose modulation and field-of-view selection. However, current clinical workflows heavily rely on manual annotations by radiologists—a process that is time-consuming, labor-intensive, and subject to significant inter-observer variability.

Currently, some studies address the need for organ localization prior to re-scanning in targeted therapies by utilizing patients' prior medical scans and limited modeling approaches^{[2][3]} to predict organ positions, as an alternative to traditional plaster modeling methods. However, this approach is not applicable to patients undergoing the initial scan. Although virtual pre-scan assessments based on whole-body organ models can improve localization efficiency and accuracy, the lack of automated anatomical modeling tools remains a technical bottleneck.

This study addresses this gap by proposing a novel automated organ localization algorithm that integrates optical photo-driven digital anatomic reconstruction. Our framework builds personalized whole-body digital anatomical models from visible-light-based photo. An end-to-end convolutional neural networks (CNNs) reconstructs a patient's personalized 3D human mesh-based statistical shape model from visible-light images. Aligning the surface mesh with the image is propagated to internal organs to maintain epidermal and internal anatomical consistency. Real-time organ localization by mapping the reconstructed anatomical model to a standardized coordinate system to automatically recommend scanning protocols.

B. METHODS

We achieve organ localization by constructing a whole-body digital anatomical model that fits with images obtained prior to scanning. The construction of the whole-body digital anatomical model relies on a pre-defined human statistical shape model template. We employ convolutional neural networks to regress pose parameters and shape parameters that control the deformation of the pre-defined human model. To address the issue of missing internal anatomical structures in Skinned Multi - Person Linear (SMPL)^[4] Model, we simultaneously utilize the Statistical Deformable Human Anatomy Phantom (SDHAP) proposed by Wang^[5] et al. Figure 1 illustrates the overall framework of our proposed method. The backbone model DinoV2^[6] acts as an encoder to extract features from input images, followed by two Multi-Layer Perceptron layers to regress pose and shape parameters of the SMPL model. These parameters control the deformation of the SMPL template model to achieve personalized skinning model construction for the target human body. Subsequently, we need to build internal anatomical organs that match the personalized skin perfectly. The SDHAP includes detailed anatomical structures such as skin, skeleton, muscles, organs, and more. We register the skin model of the whole-body digital anatomical model to a personalized skin model, SMPL. By transferring the deformation field obtained during skin registration to internal organs, we achieve personalized deformation of internal organs, completing the personalized whole-body digital anatomical model.

Figure 1 Overall workflow of the proposed method.

C. RESULTS

Through aligning the models with surface renderings of pseudo-photos generated from five test CT images, we have verified the precision of organ localization. As depicted in Figure 2, the personalized whole-body digital anatomical model, post-projection rendering, directly showcases the position of each organ on the pseudo-photos. Additionally, upon aligning the predicted skin model with the skin model reconstructed from CT scans, the observed positional differences between predicted and actual organ locations are not significant. In the image, the blue point cloud represents our constructed model, while the red point cloud indicates the organ models segmented from the CT scan. Notably, the position of the heart shows almost perfect overlap.

We also computed the average surface distance between the predicted organ model and the CT-segmented organ model, and the results are summarized in Table 1. Using the segmented CT organs as the gold standards, our method yielded averaged Chamfer Distance (CD) of less than 22mm for the internal organs (heart: 12.99 ± 1.72 mm, stomach: 18.03 ± 6.73 mm, lungs: 15.60 ± 2.92 mm, livers: 16.19 ± 2.58 mm, kidney: 15.10 ± 5.76 mm, spleen: 21.49 ± 3.55 mm), achieving centimeter-level localization accuracy of internal organs. Figure 2 displays visual comparison images between the predicted organ positions by the proposed method and the CT scan. Our method can visually demonstrate organ positions to medical professionals.

Table 1 This is the caption of a table, should be left aligned above the table

Organ	CD (mm)
Heart	12.99 ± 1.72
Stomach	18.03 ± 6.73
Lungs	15.60 ± 2.92
Lives	16.19 ± 2.58
Kidney	15.10 ± 5.76
Spleen	21.49 ± 3.55

Figure 2 Visual comparison of results. (a): Project the reconstructed model onto the image. (b): 3D organ prediction (red) compared with ground trust CT organ (blue)

D. DISCUSSION

The proposed method has reconstructed relatively accurate human organ models solely based on surface images of the human body, with the surface of the heart model achieving a precision of 11.02mm. Additionally, the reconstructed internal organs not only include large organ models visible in CT scans but also encompass small organs such as the pancreas and thyroid that are challenging to identify using traditional organ localization methods. While the accuracy of this method may not match that of medical imaging-based organ segmentation methods, it fills a gap in pre-scanning organ localization in medical imaging, greatly enhancing the efficiency of radiological examinations. However, since internal organs undergo various deformations with changes in body posture, the morphology of reconstructed organs differs for the same individual in different postures. Therefore, real-time performance is essential for this method. In future research, improvements are needed to enhance the real-time performance of our method.

E. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our method, relying solely on external optical photo, has demonstrated the ability to accurately reconstruct internal organ models, including small organs traditionally difficult to identify. While there is room for improvement in real-time performance, the efficiency gains in pre-scanning organ localization are substantial. Future research should focus on enhancing real-time capabilities to further augment the utility of AI in medical imaging.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the Joint Funds of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. U24A20753), the funding of Liaoning Key Lab of IC & BME System and Dalian Engineering Research Center for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging.

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1053-Dynamic Perlin Breast Simulation Pipeline RevisitedMagnus D. ¹, Tomic H. ¹, Tingberg A. ¹, Bakic P. ¹*Lund University Translational Medicine Malmö-Sweden* ¹

Purpose: In 2024, we introduced an integrated pipeline for dynamic interactive Perlin-based simulation in breast cancer imaging. The initial pipeline configuration has shown a high level of realism and flexibility. Based upon the preliminary applications, potential areas for further development have been identified and discussed in this submission.

Methods: Three areas for further development of dynamic interactive Perlin pipeline include: (1) Systematic evaluation of simulated breast images; (2) Selection of locations to insert simulated lesions; (3) Modelling changes in breast volume and its effect on breast density. We propose methods to address these areas for development, and discuss their anticipated effects.

Results: Preliminary evaluation of the dynamic Perlin simulation pipeline has included qualitative comparison of simulated and clinical images. Comparison of breast density estimates is ongoing. Future evaluation may compare radiomic and statistical (e.g., Laplacian fractional entropy) image properties, as well as lesion detection properties, based upon human or model/AI observer tests.

Locations for the insertion of simulated lesions are currently selected manually, using heuristic rules and visual inspection. Development of an automated approach, based upon the analysis of lesion locations in clinical images is ongoing. Automated insertion would further accelerate our simulation approach.

Reports in the literature on breast volume changes with age vary, as affected by both breast involution with menopause, and potential increase in adipose tissue with obesity. We simulate temporal changes in volume by mathematical morphology operations of erosion or dilation. Analysis of breast volume changes over multiple screening rounds is ongoing based upon our clinical data. No significant effects on the breast density estimation, and lesion detection are expected.

Conclusions: Methods were proposed to address comments and suggestions for further development of the preliminary dynamic Perlin simulation pipeline. Implementation and evaluation of these methods is ongoing.

Figure 1: Lund interactive dynamic Perlin breast simulation pipeline. Shown are the major pipeline modules, with user-controlled options/parameters.

Figure 2: Simulated temporal changes in: (a) breast volume (assuming increase with age); (b) breast parenchyma and density (no change in volume); and (c) tumor size.

Whole-Body Digital Vascular Structure Phantoms with Interactive Plaque Simulation for Virtual Imaging Research

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Digital phantoms of vascular structures are valuable tools in virtual imaging trials for medical imaging device development and hemodynamics simulation^{1,2}. However, a whole-body range phantom repository of vascular structures with diverse morphological characteristics and lesion simulation capability is still lacking.

B. METHODS

Leveraging multicenter, multimodal medical imaging data including 150 cases of computed tomography angiography (CTA) and 340 cases of magnetic resonance angiography (MRA)³, we implemented an enhanced 3D U-Net⁴ architecture to segment vessels of different radius scales and from various body parts (brain, head and neck, coronary artery and abdomen vessels)⁵⁻⁷, followed by dedicated segmentation error proofreading to ensure the geometrical quality. Morphological features such as centerlines, diameters, and bifurcation points were systematically extracted from segmented vessels⁸⁻¹⁰.

Figure 1 Workflow diagrams including vascular segmentation, centerline extraction, plaque simulation, DSA synthesis, and hemodynamic simulation

An interactive plaque creation function allowing user customization of plaque location, size, and fibrous cap thickness is implemented to generate anatomically plausible plaque models with optimized morphological fidelity. The spatial

distance field of the sphere was calculated by the selected center point, and then the core layer was morphologically expanded, and the outer annular region was extracted by XOR operation to construct the fiber layer, and then the core layer and the fiber layer were intersected with the vascular labels respectively to preserve the internal area of the blood vessels. Virtual imaging simulations were conducted to generate pseudo digital subtraction angiography (DSA) images of arteria carotis, and hemodynamics simulations based on aorta ascendens phantom were conducted for different vessel shapes. The repository of this dataset will be open-sourced upon the publication of this work.

C. RESULTS

We have constructed a database of vascular models containing vascular models from different sites and their centerline diameters and bifurcation points (including 50 cases of aorta, 100 cases of carotid and 340 cases of cerebrovascular), as shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows the segmentation and topology modeling results of each part of the blood vessels, in which the first column is the aorta, the second column is the carotid vessels, the third column is the cerebra vessel. In the figure, the vascular model is rendered as semi-transparent, with the red center line and blue bifurcation points shown inside the vessel.

Figure 2 Exemplar vascular models and their corresponding centerlines of (a) the aorta, (b) carotid vessels and (c) cerebra vessel.

The range of intravascular atheroma in the Willis circle is classified as less than 0.9 mm for normal, 1 to 1.2 mm for intimal thickening, 1.2 to 1.4 mm for plaque formation, and greater than 1.5 mm for arterial stenosis. We constructed atheroma plaque simulations ranging in size from 1.3 to 1.7 mm, and constructed the lipid core and fibrous layers of the plaques at different scales. Figure 3 shows plaque simulations of three typical sites of the internal carotid artery,

middle cerebral artery, and posterior cerebral artery, with yellow color for the core layer, dark green for the fibrous layer, and translucent red for the blood vessels.

Figure 3 Intravascular atherosclerotic plaque modeling.

Based on the existing data, the Willis circle intravascular atheroma simulation modeling library can be used for post-vascular modeling research such as hemodynamic simulation. The data simulation method has the following advantages: the physical unit parameter system is adopted, which is suitable for data with different resolutions; The dual-structure modeling of the core layer and fibrous layer of plaque is more consistent with the pathological characteristics of atherosclerotic plaques. Interactive design can improve the selection and accuracy of plaque anatomical location; The database can be used to generate synthetic data for training deep learning models. Figure 4 shows the results of generate synthetic DSA images of arteria carotis and hemodynamic simulation of aortic arch. Among them, the DSA image synthesis was realized by projection algorithm, and the hemodynamic simulation was carried out by simvascular software.

Figure 4 (a) generate pseudo DSA images of arteria carotis (b) Hemodynamic simulation results of aortic arch (A change from blue to red indicates increasing pressure on the blood vessel wall).

D. DISCUSSION

In this study, a large number of vascular models of different sites were obtained by improving the vascular segmentation algorithm to segment a large number of medical image data including aorta, artery and cerebrovascular vessels, and the topological structure of these models was modeled. A system-wide digital vascular repository integrating morphological changes and quantitative geometric features was constructed. Developed interactive plaque simulation capabilities to support patient-specific lesion generation. The dual-structure modeling of the plaque core layer and the fibrous layer is consistent with the pathological characteristics of atherosclerotic plaques. The interactive

design improves the selection and accuracy of plaque anatomical locations. The database can be used to generate synthetic data for training deep learning models. Virtual DSA imaging and hemodynamic simulation were attempted. Future work will expand the data scale of the repository and integrate food image simulation modules with different imaging modalities (DSA, CTA, MRA) to enhance their utility in personalized cardiovascular medicine.

E. CONCLUSION

This study constructs a comprehensive vascular phantom repository from large population medical image dataset, encompassing different vascular morphological features, integrated with interactive plaque simulation capabilities, to advance virtual imaging trial studies related to cardiovascular disease.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the Joint Funds of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. U24A20753), the general program of National Natural Science Fund of China (No. 81971693), the funding of Liaoning Key Lab of IC & BME System and Dalian Engineering Research Center for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging.

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Comparison between simulated mechanical imaging on software breast phantoms and clinical measurements, in breasts with different density

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Breast cancer is the most common form of cancer in women globally. During their lifetime, one in ten women are expected to be affected by breast cancer firsthand. Breast cancer is also virtually non-preventable¹, which means that efficient treatment through early detection is key. Therefore, we need to continuously assess current detection methods and innovate new ones. For this purpose, virtual clinical trials (VCT) can complement clinical trials of medical imaging systems for breast cancer detection.

With the use of VCTs, one can produce an arbitrary number of unique simulated mammograms in an affordable and time-efficient manner. This is of course only feasible if the simulated material exhibits realistic properties, preferably indistinguishable from clinical data. To achieve this, our lab has pioneered the use of Perlin noise²⁻³ to create 3D structures which resemble the tissue distribution in a breast. Perlin noise is a mathematical method of creating noise without discontinuities, “noise with structure” in a manner of speaking. It is often used in computer graphics and video game development to replicate natural or organic structures. It has also been used before to create virtual breast tissue.⁴⁻⁷

The aim of the project is, using Perlin noise, to create a *deformable* software breast phantom, i.e. to evaluate how tissue is displaced by mammographic compression and derive the distribution of stress. Achieving this allows us to simulate breast Mechanical Imaging (MI), a novel approach for breast cancer detection which has been shown by Dustler et al⁸. to reduce false positives in breast cancer detection when used in conjunction with clinical mammography, MI measures the surface stress of the breast during mammographic compression, providing information about local elastic properties of the underlying tissue. The pressure distribution is visualized in patches corresponding to the size of the pressure sensors.

MI can be an aid in distinguishing between malignant and benign lesions, as malignant tumors are stiffer in comparison to benign tumors or healthy tissue. Because of this, the pressure measurements will also depend on the composition of tissue in a breast. Breast density depends on the amount of fibroglandular tissue. This is because breast density affects the breast's mechanical properties; as the ratio of fibroglandular tissue increases or decreases compared to adipose tissue, so will the overall stiffness of the breast change.

The purpose of this study is to evaluate how differences in density of the software breast phantom affect the results of simulated MI.

B. METHODS

We performed simulations of MI imaging using software breast phantoms with different density. The tissue composition of the phantom was based on an in-house developed Perlin model of breast anatomy⁹. The phantoms are used to model progressive changes in the amount, distribution and appearance of dense tissue within a certain simulated breast, as to model the diminishing of the amount of fibroglandular tissue in a breast, which is part of the natural aging process¹⁰.

Voxels in our anatomical breast model have values corresponding to the ratio of two tissues (adipose and fibroglandular). These voxel values range from 1, representing a tissue mixture with 100% adipose tissue, to 0, representing a tissue mixture of 0% adipose tissue and 100% fibroglandular tissue. The difference between the breast models is the number of voxels which have a higher ratio of adipose tissue, i.e. more voxel values closer to the value of 1.

The MI simulation was performed by finite element analysis (FEA) using FEBio, an open-source software¹¹. The shape of the deformable breast phantom is based on geometrical shapes by connecting two quarters of two different ellipsoids, forming a breast-like shape with dimensions spanning 17 x 7.5 x 3.7 cm. The software phantom was partitioned into roughly 100 000 tetrahedral elements. To replicate the hyper elastic properties of breast tissue, a neo Hookean material model was used, assigning properties obtained from literature. We assigned stiffness parameters according to the values in the range given by Krouskop et al¹². For our simulations, we used the stiffness modulus of 20 kPa for adipose tissue, and 80 kPa for fibroglandular tissue.

To assign each tetrahedral element a material value, the weighted average value of the voxels inside each tetrahedral element was calculated. The element was then assigned to completely consist of the tissue mixture value, used in the original software breast structure, which the calculated average value was closest to.

The phantoms are deformed by compression of two rigid plates down to half the original thickness (see figure 1). The total reaction force acting on the plates can be read out directly from FEBio.

Figure 1: Example of software breast phantom before compression (above), and after compression (below) using the software FEBio. The different colors of the elements of the phantom represents materials of different values of stiffness.

C. RESULTS

Five different Perlin breast models were used to assign tissue to the tetrahedral FEA phantom. When compressing the phantom with the most adipose tissue (the least dense breast phantom), the reaction forces were 70 N. When compressing the phantom with the least adipose tissue (the densest breast phantom), the reaction force on the compression plate was 128 N.

In order of low density to high density, the reaction force was measured to be 70 N, 86 N, 119 N, 136 N, 128 N on the compression plates.

D. DISCUSSION

It is unexpected that the second most dense phantom would yield a slightly higher reaction force than the densest software breast phantom. This is probably due to that even though the material distribution in the densest phantom was stiffer overall, the selection of voxels used to assign material to the deformable breast phantom happened to correspond to less stiff materials than the ones used in the second most dense phantom. Also, we are not currently simulating the presence of ligaments or the pectoral muscle, nor the presence of a chest wall. All these factors could be responsible in absorbing a substantial part of applied pressure in the clinical trials, and the absence of which could explain the lower-than-expected values of reaction force in our simulations, at least for the less dense breast phantoms.

E. CONCLUSION

Preliminary comparison has confirmed that the compression force on the simulated breast is close to the mean value of clinical observed values, which was measured to be 118 N by Zackrisson et al¹³., but also above or below that value depending on the density of the software breast phantoms.

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Intraoperative 2D/3D registration of coronary artery models guided by personalized virtual digital subtraction angiography (DSA)

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

In coronary interventions, the quality of intraoperative digital subtraction angiography (DSA) imaging critically influences the procedural outcomes. However, in cases of severe stenosis or chronic total occlusion (CTO), DSA frequently fails to visualize distal vessel morphology due to calcification, contrast dispersion, or vascular occlusion, leaving operators to navigate guidewires blindly with prolonged procedure time and increased perforation risks[1]. Although preoperative computed tomography angiography (CTA) provides complete 3D coronary artery mapping, the precise registration between static CTA models and dynamic intraoperative DSA sequences remains a significant technical challenge[2]. This study proposes an intraoperative 2D/3D registration framework guided by personalized virtual DSA, which integrates preoperative CTA-derived 3D coronary models with real-time DSA imaging to reconstruct occluded vessel pathways, thereby enhancing navigation accuracy for complex CTO procedures[3].

B. METHODS

The proposed intraoperative 2D/3D coronary artery registration framework integrates multi-stage deep learning and geometric optimization pipelines, as illustrated in Figure 1. First, a 3D coronary artery model is reconstructed from preoperative CTA scans using nnU-Net[4] for volumetric segmentation, while intraoperative DSA images are processed by an enhanced FR-UNet[5] network to extract 2D vessel centerlines. To address the extensive angular search space in conventional registration, a personalized synthetic DSA dataset generation module is developed: the 3D coronary model is orthographically projected across 200-360° azimuth and 0-60° elevation ranges, synthesizing 20,000 virtual DSA images with augmented clinical challenges including vessel occlusion and contrast dispersion. A PointNet++[6]-based projection angle prediction network is then designed to estimate optimal viewing angles by analyzing topological patterns of intraoperative DSA vessel branches, providing robust initialization for subsequent registration. Finally, an improved iterative closest point (ICP) algorithm aligns synthetic and real DSA centerlines through 2D/3D point cloud registration, estimating optimal rigid-body transformations (rotation matrix R and translation vector t) to minimize Euclidean distances between corresponding points. This workflow significantly reduces the initial pose sensitivity of conventional ICP through deep learning-guided initialization while enhancing adaptability to complex vascular pathologies via synthetic data augmentation.

Figure 1 The workflow of the registration algorithm.

Figure 2 The left figure shows the complete coronary artery centerline, and the right figure shows the orthogonal projections of the LCA at different angles.

The virtual DSA synthesis module employs orthographic projection to simulate clinical C-arm imaging dynamics. Projection geometry is parameterized by two degrees of freedom: elevation (angle between projection direction and horizontal plane) and azimuth (rotation around body axis), adhering to clinical coronary angiography conventions (LAO/RAO and Cranial/Caudal angle combinations) that comprehensively cover all potential viewing angles. Focusing on the anatomically complex left coronary artery (LCA) - a clinically challenging site for intraoperative visualization - we generate 20,000 synthetic DSA images by projecting 3D coronary models across 200-360° azimuth and 0-60° elevation ranges. Each synthetic image incorporates annotated projection angles and 2D vessel centerline coordinates (see Figure 2 for representative projections). This dataset serves dual purposes: 1) training a personalized angle prediction network through topological pattern learning; 2) providing geometrically constrained search space for subsequent ICP registration.

C. RESULTS

In this study, the accuracy of predicted projection angles was evaluated based on the virtual DSA dataset. This is because real intraoperative DSA images lack ground truth projection angles, whereas the virtual DSA data generated from preoperative CTA contains accurate angle labels, enabling quantitative evaluation of angle prediction performance. The PointNet++ model achieved a mean squared error (MSE) of $2.48 \pm 0.03^\circ$ for elevation angle prediction on the virtual test set ($n=500$ cases), indicating high precision in this parameter. However, the azimuth angle prediction exhibited significantly larger errors (MSE $36.77 \pm 0.36^\circ$), suggesting substantial uncertainty in the model's ability to resolve rotational orientation.

After the ICP registration step, the proposed method achieved 2D/3D alignment between the vessel centerlines of the preoperative CTA and the intraoperative DSA images. As demonstrated in Figure 3 the workflow effectively aligned 3D vascular models (red) with real-time DSA sequences (green), with sub-figures (a) and (b) showing the raw DSA and extracted centerlines, (c-e) showing progressive refinement of spatial alignment through angle prediction and iterative optimization. Notably, the registered 3D CTA projection (f) complemented missing vascular branches in native DSA, enhancing anatomical continuity for occluded LCA segments. These results confirm the framework's capability to bridge 3D preoperative anatomy with 2D intraoperative navigation in complex coronary interventions.

Figure 3 2D/3D registration visualization results of the LCA. (a) Raw intraoperative DSA image (The blockage locations are indicated by the red arrows). (b) DSA vascular segmentation mask. (c) Initial alignment between projected 3D CTA centerline (blue) and DSA centerline (green), revealing angular discrepancies. (d) Optimized registration via ICP algorithm, demonstrating spatial coherence of registered 3D model (red) and intraoperative data (green). (e) Fused visualization of registered 3D vascular model overlaid on original DSA. (f) 3D CTA projection (red) complementarily displaying occluded branches undetectable in native DSA, confirming anatomical continuity restoration.

D. DISCUSSION

Our framework introduces two key innovations to advance intraoperative coronary navigation: 1) deep learning-based projection angle prediction that overcomes manual initialization bias, and 2) adaptive 2D/3D registration enabled by synthetic DSA generation with pathological variations. By generating synthetic multi-angle projections with pathological variations, our method eliminates dependency on paired clinical datasets while maintaining anatomical plausibility. The virtual-to-real alignment paradigm demonstrates significant potential for enhancing surgical navigation in coronary interventions, particularly for reconstructing occluded vessel pathways invisible in conventional DSA.

Current limitations involve residual rotational mismatches in tortuous vessels and rigid-body constraints during cardiac motion.

E. CONCLUSION

This study proposes an AI-enhanced 2D/3D registration framework that effectively bridges preoperative 3D coronary models with intraoperative guidance. By integrating robust angle prediction with pathological simulation protocols, our method addresses critical challenges in CTO navigation. The technology establishes a new paradigm for intelligent surgical navigation systems that harmonize spatial precision with procedural efficiency.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the Joint Funds of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. U24A20753), the funding of Liaoning Key Lab of IC & BME System and Dalian Engineering Research Center for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging.

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CT-Based Personalized Modeling of Whole-Body Anatomy with Conditional Shape Priors

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Personalized whole-body anatomical modeling serves as a fundamental basis for supporting virtual imaging experiments, radiotherapy simulation, and digital human construction. Existing deep learning frameworks such as Moose¹ and TotalSegmentator² have achieved significant progress in segmenting large, commonly visible organs (e.g., liver, lungs, spleen). However, they still struggle with small-volume, low-contrast, or anatomically ambiguous structures (e.g., adrenal glands, thyroid, pancreas), where segmentation accuracy and consistency need further improvement. These difficult structures are often critical for disease localization, target delineation, and dose evaluation. Therefore, improving their segmentation accuracy is essential for building high-quality digital human models.

B. METHODS

We propose a two-stage anatomical modeling framework based on conditional Gaussian priors, as illustrated in Figure 1. In the first stage, visible large organs are extracted using state-of-the-art segmentation frameworks, such as TotalSegmentator, to establish reliable anatomical references, where each organ's geometric features are represented as $Y = [c_x, c_y, c_z, w, h, d] \in R^6$, comprising the 3D bounding box center coordinates and dimensions. The collective features of $K - 1$ neighboring organs form the conditioning variable $Y \in R^{6(K-1)}$ used in subsequent modeling. In the second stage, Conditional Gaussian Models (CGM)³ precisely model small structures by capturing their spatial dependencies with neighboring organs through conditional distributions.

The conditional distribution is characterized by:

$$\mu_{X|Y} = \mu_X + \Sigma_{XY}\Sigma_{YY}^{-1}(Y - \mu_Y)$$

$$\Sigma_{X|Y} = \Sigma_{XX} - \Sigma_{XY}\Sigma_{YY}^{-1}\Sigma_{YX}$$

In these formulations, $\mu_{X|Y}$ represents the expected position and size of the target small organ given neighboring structures, where μ_X denotes the target organ's mean characteristics, μ_Y represents neighboring organs' mean features, Σ_{XX} encodes their spatial covariance, and Σ_{YY}^{-1} is the inverse covariance matrix of neighbors. The conditional covariance $\Sigma_{X|Y}$ quantifies prediction uncertainty after accounting for neighbor information, with Σ_{XX} capturing the target's intrinsic variability and Σ_{YX} being the transpose of Σ_{XY} . These parameters generate probabilistic spatial priors where $\mu_{X|Y}$ provides optimal location estimates while $\Sigma_{X|Y}$ indicates prediction reliability, particularly valuable for challenging cases with poor contrast or ambiguous boundaries.

For each target small organ, spatial statistical relationships with adjacent detectable structures such as the kidneys, liver, and spine are established. The model captures the dependency between the centers of small and large organs.

Parameters learned from training data reflect the anatomical spatial coupling and are used to generate spatial heatmaps during inference.

A 3D U-Net⁴ structure is adopted for fine segmentation, with features generated by the CGM incorporated as auxiliary location guidance. In addition, a composite loss function is designed, combining a segmentation consistency term with a spatial guidance term to enhance the network's perception of anatomical structure constraints.

Figure 1 Overall framework of the proposed training and inference pipeline. (a) Flowchart of two-stage network training, a multi-organ detection network is trained using full CT images and their organ annotations to obtain the coarse localization information of each organ; the detected organ regions are then used as the basis for cropping the obtained localized images and the corresponding labels to be used for training multiple independent single-organ segmentation networks. (b) Flowchart of two-stage network inference, where the input CT images are used to obtain the initial localization frame of each organ through the trained multi-organ detection network; subsequently, based on this localization frame, the local images obtained by cropping are input into the corresponding single-organ segmentation networks, and the single-organ segmentation results are output.

C. RESULTS

Experiments were conducted on 53 whole-body contrast-enhanced CT datasets, covering 32 categories of commonly visible structures and 5 categories of low-contrast small organs. The training/validation/testing split ratio was 8:1:1.

Figure 2 illustrates the construction of a digital atlas of 32 visible organs of the human body, providing a comprehensive overview of the anatomical structures considered in the segmentation task.

Figure 2 Construction of a digital atlas of 32 visible organs of the human body.

As shown in Figure 3, the proposed method achieves better boundary continuity and geometric consistency compared to Moose for structures such as the thyroid, prostate, and pancreas. The predicted structures align closely with the ground truth annotations and outperform conventional models significantly.

Figure 3 Visualization of the results of the second stage segmentation of the gland

Table 1 presents the Dice Similarity Coefficient (Dice) comparison between the proposed method and the Moose framework for five critical glands. The results highlight the effectiveness of the proposed approach, particularly in the improvement of small and low-contrast organ segmentation.

The overall average improvement exceeds 2.3%, with the left adrenal gland showing more than a 4% gain. This indicates the significant role of the CGM mechanism in spatial localization, particularly for small and low-contrast organs.

Table 1 Quantitative comparison of segmentation accuracy (Dice) with Moose

Organ	Moose	Our Method
Prostate	88.57 \pm 4.13%	89.19 \pm 4.23%
Thyroid	86.83 \pm 2.75%	89.98 \pm 4.83%
Left Adrenal Gland	81.56 \pm 4.82%	85.87 \pm 3.39%
Right Adrenal Gland	84.33 \pm 4.59%	84.83 \pm 3.00%
Pancreas	89.64 \pm 3.18%	90.36 \pm 4.81%

D. DISCUSSION

The core innovation of this study lies in introducing contextual spatial relationships between anatomical structures. Detectable structures serve as anchors to predict the spatial distributions of hard-to-segment structures, breaking through the traditional paradigm of "independent organ modeling." This approach demonstrates particular value in prostate segmentation by leveraging its spatial coupling with the bladder and pelvic bones, ensuring anatomical plausibility even in cases with boundary ambiguity. For thyroid localization, the method benefits from consistent relationships with cervical bones and lungs, maintaining robustness across varying contrast conditions.

Compared with methods relying solely on image intensity or individual shape modeling, the CGM-based approach can more accurately construct inter-organ conditional relationships, enabling inference of "invisible structures," as evidenced by its reliable performance in small adrenal gland segmentation through spatial priors from liver and spleen.

Moreover, the method demonstrates good generalizability and scalability, suggesting potential applications in multi-modal image fusion scenarios such as PET/CT, where accurate organ localization is crucial, as well as in spatial prior generation tasks for clinical lesion localization and automatic annotation. The ability to maintain anatomical consistency across diverse imaging conditions underscores its clinical utility.

E. CONCLUSION

We proposed a two-stage whole-body anatomical modeling method integrating conditional shape priors, which combines the spatial information of detectable large organs and the conditional Gaussian modeling mechanism to achieve precise localization and segmentation of hard-to-segment small organs. Experiments demonstrate that the proposed method significantly improves small organ segmentation accuracy, structural integrity, and anatomical consistency. It holds promising potential for applications in more complex medical imaging modeling and virtual experimental tasks.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the Joint Funds of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. U24A20753), the funding of Liaoning Key Lab of IC & BME System and Dalian Engineering Research Center for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging.

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Stability of AI Lesion Detection Output in Mammography Investigated Using a Physical Version of a Virtual Breast Phantom

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Various forms of computer-assisted detection (CAD) applications powered by artificial intelligence are seeing increasing use in breast imaging, especially in alleviating the considerable workload imposed on radiologists by breast cancer screening programs¹. With AI as an increasingly integral part of the image review process – both as a reading assistant and possibly in the future for independent triaging – it is important that quality control (QC) procedures are adequate not only for human readers but also for the output of AI algorithms as the latter may considerably impact screening outcomes.

Traditional radiological QC is primarily carried out using physical phantoms. Digital phantoms, although useful in many other applications, are unsuitable for day-to-day QC as virtual imaging models cannot capture drift in the parameters of a specific imaging system. QC phantoms are neither anthropomorphic nor realistic, but intended for measuring the stability of the imaging system by standardized measurements of quantitative parameters such as contrast and line pair resolution. Although the exact effect such parameters have on readers is unknown, they are known to correlate with reader performance and measurable changes in them give an indication that there is a drift in system parameters of e.g. the detector or X-ray tube that may warrant repair or replacement. In principal, physical anthropomorphic phantoms could be used and QC procedures could be set up as a detection task for radiologists. However, this would require a large number of phantoms, a lot of radiologist time and be severely hampered by memory bias. Digital anthropomorphic phantoms could provide more variety, but would naturally instead be subject to the same limitations mentioned previously for digital phantoms.

A procedure for QC focused on AI performance can be considered to have both advantages and challenges. Though, on a general level, AI detection performance should also be affected by traditional quantitative QC measures, there is no indication of whether it is more or less sensitive than human readers to such changes. Other studies on AI image recognition suggest that changes that would be unnoticeable to a human can substantially affect AI performance, and vice versa². Additionally, as clinically used breast imaging AI does not suffer from memory bias and reads images very rapidly, it seems that there is an opportunity to create a more robust and realistic QC procedure focused on AI output using realistic physical breast phantoms with realistic lesions. Breast imaging QC can then essentially be transformed into a miniature virtual lesion detection trial, with the imaging itself carried out on a physical version of a digitally designed breast phantom and the image review performed by the AI system. By regular imaging of such a phantom, AI output can be continuously monitored for drifts in performance.

This project aims to investigate and provide a baseline for virtual quality control of AI-assisted mammographic imaging by quantifying the variation in AI lesion detection results in digital mammography (DM) and digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) using a realistic physical phantom based on a digital phantom.

Figure 1 DM image of PhantomX phantom with lesion marked

B. METHODS

DM and DBT images of a compressed 36 mm breast phantom in CC-view containing a simulated spiculated mass (59-01, PhantomX GmbH, Berlin, Germany) were collected. The PhantomX phantom is a physical breast model based on the Virtual Imaging Clinical Trial for Regulatory Evaluation (VICTRE) pipeline provided by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)³. It contains realistic anatomical structures, such as adipose and glandular tissue, and has attenuation properties similar to that of a real breast. The phantom is rigid and noncompressible. All images were acquired using a Siemens MAMMOMAT Inspiration system (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany). The phantom was positioned on the center of the detector plate. Figure 1 shows a DM image of the phantom with the lesion marked by a red circle.

Image acquisition used AEC (automatic exposure control) to allow a controllable baseline and various other settings were varied to investigate their potential effect on the AI output. These included moving the phantom on the detector (between 1-6 cm right or left of center), repeating the same image acquisition with compression plate released in between exposures (but trying to recreate the compression force each time) and moving the phantom back to exclude the highly attenuating mountings located where the chest wall would be on real woman. At each condition, 20 images were acquired using identical settings. Differences between imaging conditions and baseline (fixed compression without release of compression plate between acquisitions, centered on the detector and “chest wall” included) were investigated using the Student’s t-test.

The collected images were analyzed using Transpara (version 2.1.0, ScreenPoint Medical, Nijmegen, Netherlands), a clinically available AI-based cancer detection system. Transpara presents two relevant outputs: individual localized lesion risk scores of 1-100 and an overall image risk score of 1-10. Only lesion risk scores above 15 are shown in the algorithm output. The clinically used overall risk scores are calibrated so that 10% of cases in a screening population fall in each group and >90% of cancers go into group 10. For this project, only the lesion risk scores are reported.

For all DM images, the finding with the highest region risk score in an image was checked to see that the coordinates corresponded with the coordinates of the lesion in the phantom. If the coordinates of the finding did not correspond with the location of the lesion, the coordinates of the other findings in the image were checked. If any other finding had coordinates corresponding to the lesion location this score was assigned to the lesion. If no finding in an image corresponded to the lesion, a lesion risk score of 0 was assigned. For the DBT images the location of the findings was not available from the output file. Instead, it was assumed that the highest reported findings corresponded to the location of the lesion.

C. RESULTS

Results for DM and DBT are summarized in Tables 1 and 2 below, respectively, along with results of Student t-tests for differences in lesion scores for all included imaging conditions compared to the baseline values. Lesion risk scores were generally substantially higher for DBT, indicating that the included lesion appears more malignant on DBT than DM.

Table 1 AI lesion risk scores for DM of the included imaging conditions and results of t-tests for differences to baseline. The given values are mean, standard deviation and range of the lesion risk score values. Statistical difference test results are shown for baseline (A1, B1, C1) compared to three different variations: A, compression not-released vs compression released; B, phantom centered vs phantom moved; C, "chest wall" included vs excluded. The baseline values are for the compression not released, phantom centered and "chest wall" included.

Conditions	Mean (\pm SD)	Range	Mean difference (95% CI)	t-statistic	p-value
A1. Compression not released (baseline)	43.9 (\pm 7.40)	33 - 63	3.0 (-2.08, 8.07)	1.193	0.240
A2. Compression released	40.9 (\pm 8.59)	30 - 67			
B1. Phantom centered (baseline)	43.9 (\pm 7.40)	33 - 63	0.72 (-4.46, 5.85)	0.280	0.781
B2. Phantom moved	43.2 (\pm 9.03)	28 - 61			
C1. Including "chest wall" (baseline)	43.9 (\pm 7.40)	33 - 63	-0.80 (-5.10, 3.50)	-0.376	0.709
C2. Excluding "chest wall"	44.7 (\pm 5.97)	33 - 56			

Table 2 AI lesion risk scores for DBT of the included imaging conditions and results of *t*-tests for differences to baseline. The given values are mean, standard deviation and range of the lesion risk score values. Statistical difference test results are shown for baseline (A1, B1, C1) compared to three different variations: A, compression not-released vs compression released; B, phantom centered vs phantom moved; C, “chest wall” included vs excluded. The baseline values are for the compression not released, phantom centered and “chest wall” included.

Conditions	Mean (\pm SD)	Range	Mean difference (95% CI)	<i>t</i> -statistic	<i>p</i> -value
A1. Compression not released (baseline)	69.0 (\pm 3.54)	60 - 76	2.90 (-0.131, 5.94)	1.936	0.060
A2. Compression released	66.1 (\pm 5.75)	56 - 82			
B1. Phantom centered (baseline)	69.0 (\pm 3.54)	60 - 76	3.18* (0.064, 6.30)	2.112	0.042
B2. Phantom moved	65.8 (\pm 6.01)	55 - 81			
C1. Including “chest wall” (baseline)	69.0 (\pm 3.54)	60 - 76	-1.00 (-3.87, 1.87)	-0.705	0.485
C2. Excluding “chest wall”	70.0 (\pm 5.26)	61 - 81			

D. DISCUSSION

The results show that neither minor differences in positioning of the phantom by displacement or compression nor the inclusion or exclusion of an unrealistic “chest wall” have substantial effects on the AI lesion risk score. The only statistically significant difference was a somewhat higher, but still minor, decrease in score from not having the phantom centered on the detector during DBT imaging. All of these differences were on average much lower than the baseline variation in scores with repeated imaging at each distinct condition. The reason for these variations is unknown, though it must be stressed that the repeat images, especially for fixed compression, are visually identical and have identical exposure settings. The only thing that could realistically vary is the quantum noise. Understanding these variations is vital for designing a useful QC procedure.

For the purposes of this study, the absolute values of either overall risk scores or individual findings are unimportant and neither an increase nor decrease should necessarily be seen as positive or negative. While the lesion is visually similar to a malignant breast lesion there is no actual ground truth, i.e. no real malignant or benign lesion. The stability of the output is however important, as it shows the baseline variation that can be expected from the AI system.

In terms of virtual clinical trials, this study shows both the advantages and limitations of the VCT approach. On the one hand, this study necessitates the use of physical rather than digital phantoms, and real rather than simulated imaging in order to eliminate sources of error in the modelling of the imaging system. On the other hand, the physical phantom is based on a validated digital phantom that is part of a state-of-the-art VCT pipeline. Further, the results of this study can be used to validate a virtual version of the trial, which could then in turn be used to design further VCTs to systematically investigate the effect of various parameters on the AI output, e.g. the possible influence of quantum noise. Such investigations would be impossible or extremely resource-intensive to carry out on physical phantoms. In a wider perspective, the correspondence between AI detection performance in real and virtual imaging will likely vary between algorithms and may be sensitive to parameters that do not necessarily matter for human readers or model observers. Future work is needed to investigate these questions, especially in light of the accelerating adoption of AI in many radiological applications.

An important limitation is the realism of the phantom and whether or not it is sufficient for the task. Direct comparison with the AI output of real patients with repeated images could in principal validate the study results, but

such repeat images would not be available except if retakes were necessary due to poor image quality. So despite the potential limitation of realism, this study, to the author's knowledge, represent the first investigation of actual repeated imaging using a clinically deployed radiological breast AI lesion detection system. Other limitations include that this study used a single AI-system and a single mammography unit, limiting the generalizability of the results.

E. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study provides novel information on the robustness of breast AI output in a phantom-based QC procedure. It demonstrates the usefulness of VCT components in a hybrid digital-physical methodology capable of investigating an important research question that would not be possible to study using clinical images.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors would like to acknowledge the assistance of ScreenPoint Medical and PhantomX.

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Reconstructing brain vascular velocity and pressure field using PINN based on real 4D flow data

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Understanding the velocity and pressure fields within the cerebrovascular system holds immense significance in diagnosing and monitoring diseases^[1], executing simulation tasks^[2], and comprehending brain function^[3]. 4D flow magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provides a non-invasive approach to measure blood flow velocity. However, limited by low spatial and temporal resolution and noise interference^[4], it becomes challenging to directly acquire high-resolution velocity and pressure fields. The traditional way to get velocity and pressure field is finite element method (FEM), which costs amounts of computational resources, cannot make full use of the 4D flow MRI data, and is constrained by the mesh which is preset. In recent years, physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) have been increasingly applied to hemodynamic simulations due to their ability to incorporate physical laws. Several studies^[4-7] have demonstrated the potential of PINNs in modeling blood flow in simplified vascular geometries. Despite these efforts laying a solid foundation, most existing studies rely on synthetic or artificial data generated by FEM, which typically assume precisely known measurement points as well as initial and boundary conditions. This study aims to utilize PINN to achieve high-resolution velocity and pressure field in the cerebrovascular system using real 4D flow raw data.

B. DATA AND METHODS

1. Data

In this study, we utilized a representative 4D Flow MRI dataset acquired from a healthy adult at Beijing Chaoyang Hospital. The imaging volume covered the major intracranial arteries within and around the Circle of Willis (CoW), including the internal carotid arteries (ICA), vertebral arteries (VA), basilar artery (BA), and the proximal segments of the anterior (ACA), middle (MCA), and posterior cerebral arteries (PCA), which includes full 3D velocity vector fields over 20 cardiac timeframes. Spatial resolution was $0.85 \times 0.85 \times 2.0 \text{ mm}^3$, with a temporal resolution of 100 ms and a velocity encoding (VENC) of 100 cm/s in all directions.

2. Methods

We introduce a PINN for real 4D flow MRI data for the cerebrovascular system super-resolution. We combine the anatomy and magnitude image to manually mark the labels where the vessels locate to get the coordinates, which are the inputs of PINN. The neural network is constrained by 4D flow data and Navier-Stokes equations, which expresses as

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u \right) = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 u \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot u = 0 \quad (2)$$

where p denotes pressure, u denotes velocity. We assume $\rho = 1066\text{kg/m}^3$ and $\mu = 0.0035\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ [8]. Therefore, the loss function consists of two components: Data loss, L_{data} , which makes the prediction and the raw data alike, and Navier-Stokes equations loss, L_{NS} , which is the residual of physics equations, which are

$$L_{tot} = L_{NS} + \alpha L_{data} \quad (3)$$

$$L_{NS} = L_1 + L_2 \quad (4)$$

$$L_{data} = \sum_{\Omega} \|\overrightarrow{u}_{data} - \overrightarrow{u}_{PINN}\|_2 \quad (5)$$

where

$$L_1 = \rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u \right) + \nabla p - \mu \nabla^2 u \quad (6)$$

$$L_2 = \nabla \cdot u \quad (7)$$

where α is the coefficient that balances loss components.

To prevent the physics-informed neural network (PINN) from converging to degenerate solutions of the partial differential equations during training, a two-stage training strategy was employed. In the first stage, supervision was applied solely through the data loss, encouraging the model to fit the 4D Flow MRI measurements as a priority. Based on this initialization, the second stage incorporated both data loss and Navier–Stokes loss to enforce physical consistency while mitigating the risk of degeneration. Figure 1 shows the total procedure of PINN.

Figure 1 The workflow of the proposed PINN framework. In stage I, all the space and time coordinates are used to pretrain the model, which is supervised by 4D flow MRI data. In stage II, in order to capture the complex behaviors in vessels, RBAS is employed to sample the coordinates iteratively with the supervision of 4D flow MRI data and physics laws.

To enhance the PINN's ability to capture complex physical behaviors in anatomically challenging regions, such as vascular bifurcations and curved segments, we adopted a residual-based adaptive sampling (RBAS) strategy [9]. After a fixed number of training epochs, a subset of collocation points was resampled from regions exhibiting high residuals of the PDE, thereby focusing learning on areas with larger prediction errors.

C. RESULTS

Our PINN model is able to reconstruct the velocity and pressure field from noisy, low-resolution 4D flow MRI data. As shown in Figure 2, the predicted velocity field closely resembles the result after pre-processing obtained from the commercial software CVI42 across the entire domain. The proposed PINN model achieved a mean squared error (MSE) of $4.06 \times 10^{-2} \text{m/s}$ on the velocity field (while the raw data is $5.83 \times 10^{-2} \text{m/s}$). Besides, from the local perspective of the velocity vector graph, the output of PINN is also more consistent with the real blood flow behavior (Figure 3).

Figure 2 The velocity field comparison among 4D flow MRI data, PINN results, and gold standard.

Figure 3 The output of PINN is more in line with the laws of physics.

D. DISCUSSION

The staged training strategy effectively mitigates the emergence of degenerate solutions in the partial differential equations, while the incorporation of the RBAS technique enables the PINN to better capture flow behavior in regions with complex hemodynamics. However, several simplifying assumptions were adopted — including rigid vessel walls and the use of average density and viscosity values based on healthy populations. Future work will focus on reducing these assumptions to enhance physiological realism.

E. CONCLUSION

Our study demonstrates that PINN can effectively reconstruct the blood flow in the cerebrovascular system by noisy 4D Flow MRI data. Compared with the raw 4D flow MRI data, it shows better performance while without the limitation of mesh resolution.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the Joint Funds of the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. U24A20753), the funding of Liaoning Key Lab of IC & BME System and Dalian Engineering Research Center for Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Off-label in-silico flow diverter performance assessment in posterior communicating artery aneurysms

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Posterior communicating artery (PCoMA) aneurysms account for ~25% of intracranial aneurysms [1], yet the Pipeline Embolization Device (PED) is not FDA-approved for this location [2]. While PED is considered safe in PCoMA aneurysms, its efficacy in cases with fetal posterior circulation (FPC), where the PCoMA compensates for an absent or underdeveloped P1 segment, remains unclear [3,4]. FPC, which increases PCoMA size and flow demand, is more common in patients with PCoMA aneurysms and among individuals of black race [5]. A retrospective study reported lower PED occlusion rates in fetal-type PCoMA aneurysms, raising questions about whether increased flow or vessel size drives treatment failure [4].

Despite their prevalence, PCoMA aneurysms, especially with concomitant FPC, are underrepresented in clinical trials. Major studies like PUFs, PREMIER, ASPIRe, and IntrePED included few PCoMA cases and reported no subgroup outcomes [6-9]. In-silico trials (ISTs), which use computational modelling and simulation to investigate treatment in virtual patients, can fill such evidence gaps. Building on prior work showing ISTs can replicate clinical trial results [10], we present the FD-PCoMA IST, the largest study to date of off-label PED use in PCoMA aneurysms with and without FPC [11].

B. METHODS

In-silico trial design

The FD-PCoMA study tested two hypotheses: that maintained PCoMA flow after PED diversion reduces treatment success in patients with fetal posterior circulation (FPC), and that PCoMA radius influences treatment success more than aneurysm morphology, characterized by size, aspect ratio, neck diameter, and non-sphericity index. Given the importance of endothelialisation, we also investigated the impact of FPC on endothelialisation using wall shear stress on the device as a haemodynamic marker. Based on prior data showing PED occlusion rates of 43.7% in FPC and 81.8% in non-FPC cases, a sample size of 64 patients (32 per group) was calculated for 90% power at a 0.05 significance level. Our cohort included 59 anatomies with single aneurysms arising from the PCoMA (13 from @neurIST, 46 from AneuX), each simulated under both FPC and non-FPC flow conditions, resulting in 59 virtual patients per group, exceeding the required size. While clinical trials assess flow diverter safety via neurological outcomes and efficacy via angiographic occlusion, long-term outcomes cannot yet be simulated in-silico; thus, reductions in aneurysm velocity are used as established proxies for occlusion. We used reduction in space-and-time-averaged velocity (STAV) in the aneurysm sac as a haemodynamic endpoint and assessed space-and-time-averaged wall shear stress (STAWSS) on the device surface to evaluate its potential role in promoting neointimal growth.

In-silico trial simulation pipeline

Patient anatomies were obtained from the @neurIST and AneuX databases. Surface meshes were generated and refined by extracting centrelines to identify anatomical landmarks, defining internal carotid artery (ICA) inlets and PCoMA, middle cerebral artery (MCA), and anterior cerebral artery (ACA) outlets. A single 48-wire PED was deployed in each case using the fast virtual stent method [12]. Devices were clipped to cover only the aneurysm neck and PCoMA branch to reduce computational load. Volumetric meshes were created in ANSYS ICEM CFD v19.1, averaging one million elements without the device and fourteen million with. Patient-specific inlet flow waveforms representing normotensive rest were generated from a Multivariate Gaussian Model trained on phase-contrast MRI data [13]. Fetal and non-fetal physiological states were modelled by assigning PCoMA outflow mass flow boundary

conditions based on flow splits derived from a 1D Circle of Willis model [14], with fetal cases receiving 21.7% and non-fetal 0.34% of ICA inflow. Blood flow simulations were conducted in ANSYS CFX v19.1 solving unsteady Navier-Stokes equations under Newtonian fluid assumptions and rigid walls, over three cardiac cycles with results from the last cycle analysed. Zero pressure was applied at MCA and ACA outlets. Post-treatment haemodynamics were assessed via STAV and device wall shear stress. Statistical comparisons between fetal and non-fetal groups were performed using t-tests ($p < 0.05$), correlations with morphological features assessed by linear regression, and occlusion defined as $>35\%$ STAV reduction, with sensitivity analyses for alternative thresholds. Figure 1 shows the stages in the simulation pipeline and the details of the virtual patient cohort.

Figure 1 FD-PCoM A in-silico trial simulation pipeline (left) and virtual patient cohort details (right).

C. RESULTS

Distinct haemodynamics were observed in non-fetal and fetal patients, as shown in Figure 2. Stratifying the cohort into fetal and non-fetal groups via distinct PCoM A outflow conditions revealed significantly lower aneurysm STAV reduction in fetal patients (46.5%) compared to non-fetal patients (67.8%; $p < 10^{-11}$), indicating lower treatment success in fetal posterior circulation (FPC). Additionally, post-treatment device STAWSS was significantly higher in fetal cases (29.2 N/m² vs. 23.5 N/m²; $p < 0.05$), suggesting more inhibited endothelialisation. Using a 35% STAV reduction threshold for treatment success yielded predicted success rates of 98.4% (non-fetal) and 85.3% (fetal), both exceeding rates reported by Rinaldo et al. (81.8% and 43.7%). Threshold tuning showed best alignment with literature using 50% STAV reduction (88.5% non-fetal, 42.6% fetal, highlighting the need for tailored criteria across subgroups. Finally, linear regression between flow variables (STAV reduction, STAWSS) and morphological features (aneurysm size, shape indices, PCoM A radius) showed low R^2 and largely non-significant p values, indicating weak or no correlation across both physiologies.

D. DISCUSSION

Using computational fluid dynamics simulations for 118 virtual patients, we assessed treatment via aneurysm STAV reductions and device STAWSS. FPC patients had significantly less flow reduction and lower success rates, along with higher STAWSS on device struts, which may inhibit endothelialisation and promote PCoM A patency, explaining the low neurological complication rates reported clinically. Since the same anatomies were used for fetal and non-fetal subgroups, differences in treatment success are attributed to flow rates, not vessel size or aneurysm morphology. Our findings suggest PED alone may lead to slow or failed occlusion in fetal PCoM A aneurysms due to persistent flow, which is consistent with clinical observations. Given that endovascular coiling is relatively straightforward for PCoM A aneurysms, combining coiling with flow diversion could improve outcomes. Stent-assisted coiling is effective, but further research on flow diverter-assisted coiling is needed. FPC prevalence varies demographically, with lower rates in white (4.9%) than black (11.5%) populations. The FD-PCoM A IST thus not only addresses a gap

in evidence for FPC cases but also supports improved representation for under-studied demographic groups, demonstrating the value of ISTs in medical device evaluation and health equity.

Figure 2 Top: Systolic velocity streamlines for one patient from FD-PCoA. Bottom: Aneurysm flow reduction (left) and flow diverter wall shear stress (right) for all virtual patients with non-fetal and fetal physiology.

E. CONCLUSION

The FD-PCoA IST showed that PED flow diversion is less effective in patients with FPC, primarily due to increased PComA flow. Morphological factors including PComA diameter and aneurysm geometry did not significantly impact outcomes. Our findings support the following: (1) maintained PComA flow in FPC reduces treatment success; (2) treatment efficacy is driven by FPC status rather than anatomical features; and (3) FPC hinders endothelialisation, as indicated by elevated stent wall shear stress. We therefore recommend considering alternatives to single PED treatment for PComA aneurysms in patients with FPC.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

A.F.F. acknowledges support from the Royal Academy of Engineering under the RAEng Chair in Emerging Technologies (INSILEX CiET1919/19) and ERC Advanced Grant – UKRI Frontier Research Guarantee (INSILICO

EP/Y030494/1) schemes. A.F.F. acknowledges seminal funding from the European Commission to @neurIST (FP6-2004-IST-4-027703) and the @neurIST Consortium. A.S-F., T.L., and A.F.F. were funded by the European Commission via InSilc (H2020-SC1-2017-CNECT-2-777119). Z.A.T. was funded by a Royal Academy of Engineering/Leverhulme Trust Research Fellowship (No. LTRF2021/17115). M.M. was supported by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) Centre for Doctoral Training in Fluid Dynamics (P/L01615X/1). We acknowledge support from ANSYS through an Academic Partnership Agreement (No. 1122349). The information contained herein reflects only the authors' view, and none of the funders or the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of it.

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A Credibility Framework for Assessing Virtual Patient Populations for In-silico Clinical Trials

Zherui Zhou, Haoran Dou, Ali Sarrami Foroushani, Arezoo Zakeri*, Alejandro F. Frangi*

A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

In-silico trials use computational simulation to enhance medical device development and regulatory evaluation, potentially reducing and partially replacing conventional clinical trials [1]. Virtual patients, represented as synthetic objects generated by artificial intelligence, are fundamental to addressing ethical, economic, and fairness challenges in traditional recruitment. However, establishing their credibility through equivalence to real patients remains challenging.

Recent virtual population generation studies have been validating the performance of their models using different metrics. For instance, Qiao et al. [2–4] assessed divergence using Earth Mover’s Distance and Kullback-Leibler Divergence, while Zhang et al. [5] incorporated Jensen-Shannon Divergence to quantify distributional differences. Other works have used 1st Nearest Neighbour Accuracy to measure how closely generated samples match real ones in latent space [6,7]. Beetz et al. [8] applied Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) to evaluate the similarity of shape distributions. Specificity metrics were leveraged to quantify the realism of generated instances by evaluating their distance to real samples [9–13].

While these studies provide valuable insights, they are typically isolated evaluations rather than part of a unified or standardized framework. As such, the current landscape of fidelity assessment remains fragmented and could benefit from a more comprehensive and systematic evaluation strategy. In this study, with a focus on the virtual patient of cardiovascular anatomy, we propose an evaluation framework to assess the credibility of virtual populations. The evaluation encompasses three primary aspects: (1) fidelity that compares the distribution-level similarity between the virtual and real population, (2) diversity that investigates the rarity and coverage of the virtual population to the real one, (3) privacy to identify the potential data leakage in the generative artificial intelligence.

In this study, with a focus on the virtual patient of cardiovascular anatomy, we propose an evaluation framework to assess the credibility of virtual populations. The evaluation encompasses three primary aspects: (1) fidelity that compares the distribution-level similarity between the virtual and real population, (2) diversity that investigates the rarity and coverage of the virtual population to the real one, (3) privacy to identify the potential data leakage in the generative artificial intelligence.

B. METHODS

In the experiment, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) model and a Variational AutoEncoder (VAE) [14] model are trained on the same whole heart dataset with a size of 1000 samples. Each model is used to generate 1000 virtual hearts and evaluated by the evaluation framework. Our framework follows established principles from synthetic data validation and expands them into three primary dimensions of assessment: fidelity, diversity, and privacy.

Fidelity evaluates how accurately the virtual patient population replicates the statistical properties and inter-variable relationships present in real clinical population [15]. To quantify fidelity, we adopt the Specificity metric, which measures the realism of synthetic samples by computing, for each synthetic shape, the minimum Euclidean distance to any real sample. The final error is calculated as the average of these minimum distances across all synthetic samples. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Specificity Error} = \frac{1}{|Y|} \sum_{y \in Y} \min_{x \in X} |y - x|_2,$$

Where Y is the set of all VP, X represents the set of all samples in the real population, $|Y|$ is the number of samples in the VP, and $|y - x|_2$ is the distance between a virtual patient y and a real patient x .

Diversity assesses the extent to which the synthetic population captures the variability and rare patterns observed in real patients [16]. We use the Coverage Distance as our metric. This is computed in two parts: for each real sample, we find the closest synthetic sample and record the squared Euclidean distance, then for each synthetic sample, we find the closest real sample and record the squared distance as well. It is formulated as:

$$\text{COV}(X, Y) = \frac{|\{x \in X \mid \exists y \in Y, y = \text{NN}_d(x, Y)\}|}{|X|},$$

where X is the real set, Y is the generated set, and NN_d is the nearest neighbour function. A higher Coverage Score indicates that the generated population better spans the space of possible shape variations observed in real patients.

The privacy dimension of our evaluation framework addresses the risk that a generative model might reproduce specific data points from its training set. To evaluate this, we incorporate the Authenticity metric proposed by Alaa et al. [16], which estimates the likelihood that each synthetic sample is genuinely novel rather than a near-duplicate of training data. A high authenticity score indicates that most synthetic instances diverge meaningfully from the training data, suggesting that the model generalises well. The authenticity is formulated as:

$$A = \frac{1}{|\widetilde{X}_g|} \sum_{\widetilde{x}_g \in \widetilde{X}_g} I(d_g > d_r)$$

$$d_g = \min_{x_r \in D_{\text{real}}} |\widetilde{x}_g - x_r|_2,$$

$$d_r = \min_{x' \in D_{\text{real}} \setminus \{x_r^*\}} |x_r^* - x'|_2$$

$$x_r^* = \arg \min_{x_r \in D_{\text{real}}} |\widetilde{x}_g - x_r|_2,$$

Where A is the authenticity ranges from 0 to 1, $|\widetilde{X}_g|$ is the total number of synthetic samples, D_{real} is the set of real training samples, $I(\cdot)$ is the indicator function, which returns 1 if the condition inside is true, and 0 otherwise, d_g is the Euclidean distance from a synthetic sample \widetilde{x}_g to its nearest real sample. x_r^* is the real sample in D_{real} closest to \widetilde{x}_g . d_r is the Euclidean distance from x_r^* to its nearest neighbor in $D_{\text{real}} \setminus \{x_r^*\}$, i.e., excluding itself.

C. RESULTS

We compared virtual populations from a PCA and a VAE against real patient data as a showcase. VAE showed better fidelity with specificity error of $2.4275 \pm 0.4552 \text{mm}$ versus PCA's $3.0902 \pm 0.6483 \text{mm}$. PCA demonstrated superior coverage (47.60% versus VAE's 40.40%) and also showed better authenticity (0.591 versus VAE's 0.477), indicating better diversity and privacy in the generation of novel samples rather than reproducing training data. These quantitative metrics confirm the feasibility of our framework in comprehensively assessing virtual population credibility across multiple dimensions.

Figure 1. The bar plots of the (a) authenticity and (b) coverage score of the virtual patients generated by PCA and VAE models. (c) The violin plot of the specificity error of the virtual patients generated by PCA and VAE models.

D. DISCUSSION

It can be observed from the experiments that while the VAE can generate virtual patients with higher fidelity, the PCA model has a better performance regarding generating diverse data and keeping the privacy of the real patients. Similar patterns could also be applicable to other models and studies when trying to compare the performance of the newly designed models and the benchmarks. If not applying an evaluation framework that is comprehensive enough, the result of one model is better than the others might not be convincing enough.

E. CONCLUSION

This framework addresses the need for credibility assessment of virtual populations by providing a standardized, multi-faceted approach. The methodology enables the systematic evaluation of synthetic data quality across multiple dimensions, facilitating more reliable validation of virtual populations for in-silico clinical trials.

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1062-An automated modelling pipeline for fluid structure interaction analyses in patients with severe aortic stenosis

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Background and Purpose

Aortic stenosis (AS) is the most common valvular heart disease in the elderly and is often accompanied by coronary artery disease [1]. Beyond structural narrowing, AS can impair coronary perfusion even in healthy arteries, contributing to left ventricular hypertrophy and increased myocardial infarction risk. While TAVI is the preferred treatment, post-procedural haemodynamic changes can lead to complications such as thrombus formation, coronary obstruction, and paravalvular leakage (PVL), affecting outcomes [2,3,4]. Despite its clinical significance, the role of haemodynamics in AS progression and post-TAVI complications remains poorly understood, thus warranting further investigation.

Methods

To address these challenges, we are developing an automated computational modelling framework for patient-specific fluid-structure interaction (FSI) analysis using clinical trial data. Our workflow includes: (i) CT segmentation to reconstruct the aortic root, native leaflets, and calcifications; (ii) patient-specific boundary conditions; (iii) FSI simulations; and (iv) haemodynamic analysis of the aortic valve and surrounding regions.

Results

Preliminary results demonstrate the promise of this model in evaluating pre-TAVI haemodynamics, particularly in assessing Sinuses of Valsalva flow dynamics and thrombus formation risk.

Discussion and Conclusion

Ongoing work includes validating the model against echocardiography-derived flow measurements. Once validated, this workflow will be integrated into an in-silico trial to assess PVL post-TAVI, offering a novel approach for risk stratification and treatment optimisation.

Acknowledgements and Conflicts of Interest

We acknowledge support from the ERC Advanced Grant - UKRI Frontier Research Guarantee (INSILICO EP/Y030494/1). Yidan Xue and Arezoo Zakeri are acknowledged for their contributions in group discussions.

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An approach in evaluating the realism of computational breast lesion models

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Breast phantoms serve as indispensable tools across various applications in breast imaging. They are fundamental for quality control of devices¹, instrumental in diverse optimization tasks, crucial for the development of novel imaging techniques² and performing in-silico trials³. Furthermore, phantoms are vital for training medical personnel, including radiologists and technicians^{4,5}, and are increasingly important for testing AI-based algorithms⁶.

The creation of truly realistic phantoms hinges on accurately representing lesions in both shape and material properties⁷. However, manufacturing these complex components requires careful consideration of material selection and precise shape definition. Computational approaches offer a significant advantage here, allowing for the generation of numerous modifications and variations. This digital flexibility enables the adjustment of properties, such as x-ray imaging characteristics, before any physical production takes place. Determining the most realistic phantom modifications is achieved through either objective metrics or subjective assessment. The latter often involves evaluations by radiologists with expertise in mammography, who routinely encounter such cases. This implementation is typically facilitated by interactive and easy-to-understand software alongside the phantoms. Our study aims to create and assess a comprehensive set of computational breast phantoms, specifically designed to evaluate techniques and protocols for imaging the breast in a novel research infrastructure at Medical University of Varna, Bulgaria and provide advanced training for radiologists.

B. METHODS

The computational breast phantom was implemented by exploring the computational tool⁸ which can create compressed breast phantoms of any thickness and density. The phantom itself is composed of two primary elements: (a) a semi-cylindrical container that mimics the x-ray properties of breast skin and (b) thousands of spheres representing adipose tissue. The spheres, the second component of the phantom, were generated with six different diameters - 15.88 mm, 12.70 mm, 9.52 mm, 6.35 mm, 3.18 mm, and 1.58 mm. The total volume of spheres with the same diameter remains consistent across all volumes. The remaining space within the container is assigned as glandular tissue. The two-component phantom, the semicylindrical container with the used dimensions, is shown in Figure 1. The thickness of this container ranged from 3 cm to 8 cm, increasing in 1 cm increments.

Figure 1 (a) Two-component computational breast phantom: semicylindrical container with height of 3 cm to 8 cm, and radius of 9 cm; (b) a computational solid lesion, selected from MAXIMA database (<https://zenodo.org/record/7099532>).

Once the computational phantoms were created, an algorithm, implemented on a GPU was used to convert the free lesion phantoms into voxel-based models⁹. The voxel size was 0.2 mm x 0.2 mm x 0.2mm. Further, a solid type of mathematically modelled lesion was generated and inserted into the breast phantoms. The model was selected from the MAXIMA database (<https://zenodo.org/record/7099532>) and inserted into the breast phantom. The lesion properties were assigned to correspond those of Water ($\rho = 1.00\text{g/cm}^3$), Gland ($\rho = 1.02\text{g/cm}^3$), and Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA, $\rho = 1.19\text{ g/cm}^3$), resulting in a total of three lesions with varying x-ray properties. X-ray images were generated with *XRAYImagingSimulator*, an in-house developed simulator based on the Beer-Lambert law¹⁰, by using geometry, corresponding to mammography setup. The parameters of the simulation were the following source to detector distance equal to 900 mm, source to object distance depended from each phantom and was calculated based on the source to isocentre distance which was set to 600 mm. The size of the generated images was 2000 x 2000 pixels, each pixel with size of 100 μm .

C. RESULTS

Six computational breast phantoms, each differing in container thickness – 3 cm, 4 cm, 5 cm, 6 cm, 7 cm, 8 cm - were generated. The phantoms and the number of generated spheres are summarised in Figure 2. The lesion, shown in Figure 1b and inserted in a random position into each phantom individually, resulted in a different computational phantom; thus creating 18 breast phantoms in total.

Number of spheres in phantom with thickness of 3 cm	17800
Number of spheres in phantom with thickness of 4 cm	24016
Number of spheres in phantom with thickness of 5 cm	29546
Number of spheres in phantom with thickness of 6 cm	36087
Number of spheres in phantom with thickness of 7 cm	41717
Number of spheres in phantom with thickness of 8 cm	48029

Figure 2. Generated phantom and details about the number of spheres in the phantoms.

Eighteen mammography images were generated and three radiologists evaluated the visibility and realism of the breast models using a scale ranging from “clearly synthetic” to “extremely realistic” and from “absolutely sure there is no lesion” to “absolutely sure there is a lesion”. A dedicated website was developed to facilitate the evaluation. A screenshot is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A screenshot from the web-based assessment approach for developed computational phantoms.

The radiologists utilized a web application to assess the eighteen images, with the results summarized in Figure 4. These images were classified by lesion origin and breast phantom thickness. Specifically: (a) Images 1-6: lesions originating from water, across breast phantom thicknesses of 3cm, 4cm, 5cm, 6cm, 7cm, and 8cm; (b) Images 7-12: lesions originating from gland, corresponding to the same breast phantom thicknesses; (c) Images 13-18: lesions originating from PMMA, also at the aforementioned thicknesses.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. (a) Summarised results from the radiologists' evaluation, (b) simulated mammograms of water phantoms with varying thicknesses, inserted within a 4 cm thick phantom and a 3 cm thick phantom, both containing a water lesion.

D. DISCUSSION

The overall assessment indicated that water-represented tumors yielded the most realistic images. Radiologists awarded scores exceeding 14 to simulated mammography images 1 and 2, which featured water lesions embedded in 3 cm and 4 cm thick phantoms. In contrast, PMMA and gland lesions were not visible on any planar projection. Despite this, radiologist expressed a preference for the PMMA lesion within the 5 cm simulated phantom. Future research will focus on enhancing the visualization of spiculated lesions and integrating algorithms developed by other researchers¹¹. Furthermore, upcoming work will involve simulating tomosynthesis images and evaluating phantoms' performance in a 3D imaging mode.

E. CONCLUSION

The proposed approach offers a flexible and rapid method for radiologists to independently evaluate computational breast phantoms and related creation methods. This can accelerate the modification of these methods, leading to improved representation of the female breast. Ultimately, this approach has the potential to significantly reduce the time and resources currently required for extensive experimental studies, which often involve time-consuming phantom printing and specialized x-ray facility evaluations. Validated, mathematically generated lesions can be added to computational breast models with varying densities, aiding radiologists training.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This study is financed by the European Union-NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No BG-RRP-2.004-0009-C02. The work is performed by the ELPIDA 3.1.5 research group, which is part of the MUVE-TEAM project No BG-RRP-2.004-0009-C02.

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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An approach in improving the realism of anthropomorphic physical breast phantom

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Accurate simulation of breast anatomy is essential in advancing imaging technologies, as well as refining diagnostic workflows and quality assurance. However, traditional physical phantoms are often created with homogeneous materials and simple geometries. As such they fail to replicate the complexity and the anatomical details of the real breast¹.

The use of virtual phantoms overcomes these limitations. Usually, derived from mathematical models or clinical data these models can simulate the fine anatomical details and density characteristics². Moreover, these virtual models are being actively used as the source for 3D printed physical breast phantoms that closely replicate the anatomical textures and x-ray attenuation properties^{3,4}. However, there are still challenges in completely transferring the modeled characteristics of the virtual phantom to the physical one.

This study explores the use of virtual imaging simulations to improve a physical anthropomorphic breast phantom. This dual-domain approach capitalizes on the strengths of both virtual simulation and physical fabrication, enabling iterative refinement.

B. METHODS

A computational breast phantom without internal structures was created using a dedicated in-house developed software BreastSimulator⁵. The created model was then 3D printed via Stereolithography (SLA) 3D printer with flexible resin. The internal support structures required for the printing process were arranged to be retained within the model, with the aim to mimic the glandular tissue. Additionally, spheres with radii of 1.6 mm, 6.4 mm, 9.6 mm, 12.8 mm, and 16 mm were printed using Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) 3D printer and thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) filament, employing infill only and no outer shell. Liquid paraffin was then poured to complete the phantom. The assembled model was scanned with a mammography unit and evaluated by a radiologist.

To refine the phantom, a computational twin was developed to optimize its structures so that extracted imaging features from both the computational and physical models align with those from patient mammograms, both quantitatively and subjectively. Using the same breast shape, we implemented a subroutine to populate it with computational replicas of the internal components.

The computational breast phantom was created by using the in-house developed software BreastSimulator⁵. A screenshot of this is shown in Figure 1.

Specifically, a small sized breast was designed and created. The size of the semi-ellipsoid was 4cm x 4cm x 4cm. The external shape based on unique combination of semiellipsoid and semihyperboloid was filled with:

- (a) Glandular tree with parameters of creation as shown in Figure 1;
- (b) Cooper ligaments were represented as spheres with radii randomly sampled from a uniform distribution between 1 mm and 9 mm. The surface of each sphere was perforated with 10 to 20 holes, each having a diameter that varied from 0.2 mm to 0.4 mm.
- (c) Texture was incorporated by simulating a linear pattern using the algorithm proposed in the original publication in 2003⁶. This involved creating synthetic mammography images and then projecting each pixel as a bar into the breast matrix, resulting in a linear texture pattern.

Attenuation coefficients to each modelled structure corresponded to 20kV. The synthetic mammograms are generated by simulating mammography geometry for source to detector distance equal to 650mm and source to isocenter image equal to 600 mm. The resolution of the images was 10 pixels/mm.

Figure 1. A screenshot from the approach used to generate computational breast with the BreastSimulator.

C. RESULTS

Two phantoms were created: (a) a physical breast phantom and (b) a computational replica. An image of the physical phantom is shown in Figure 2, while the mammographic image of the phantom is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Image of the 3D printed breast phantom (left) and the 3D printed spheres inserted into the phantom (right).

Figure 3. A mammography image of the created physical breast phantom.

The created computational breast phantom and its mammography simulated image is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Screenshots from the created computational phantom, resembling the physical one (left) and the resulting mammography simulated image (right).

D. DISCUSSION

The mammography image of the physical phantom was subjectively rated as realistic by a radiologist, resembling a very dense breast. Simulated mammograms of the computational twin resembled the physical phantom's images. However, further adjustments of the spheres of the virtual model will be needed to match the physical 3D printed ones. Similarly, work to reproduce the internal support structures representing the glandular tree are under development.

Extracted imaging features will be analyzed to refine the computational model, aligning it completely with the physical phantom. This iterative process will guide improvements to the physical phantom by modifying the virtual model, implementing these adjustments in the physical prototype, and subsequently comparing the extracted features and conducting visual evaluations of the resulting mammography images.

E. CONCLUSION

The proposed approach of leveraging a computational twin to refine physical phantom structures and materials could prove highly effective. This method enables the development of a highly anthropomorphic breast phantom for validating prototype breast imaging systems. Additionally, the computational phantom serves as a powerful tool for virtual imaging validation and optimization.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This study is financed by the European Union-NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No BG-RRP-2.004-0009-C02. The work is performed by the ELPIDA 3.1.5 research group, which is part of the MUVE-TEAM project No BG-RRP-2.004-0009-C02.

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1065-Modelling Transcatheter Aortic Valve Implantation for Predicting Pacemaker Dependency in In Silico Trials

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A. Background and Purpose. Transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI) is a minimally invasive procedure for treating severe aortic stenosis. A major complication is conduction abnormalities (CAs), caused by injury to the heart's conduction system, sometimes requiring permanent pacemaker implantation (PPI) [1]. Computational models [2,3] have examined TAVI-induced stress on the aortic root and its role in CAs. However, they neglect balloon aortic valvuloplasty and fail to assess the risk of conduction system injury during deployment, focusing only on the final implanted state. The lack of a comprehensive workflow for TAVI deployment, stress analysis, and PPI prediction limits in-silico trials for TAVI devices.

B. Methods. We developed explicit finite-element models of the balloon aortic valvuloplasty and the deployment of a mechanically expanded TAVI device in ANSYS LS-DYNA. An automatic workflow was constructed to deploy the TAVI in patient-specific aortic anatomies reconstructed from the computed tomography angiography [4].

C. Results. We present the comprehensive TAVI deployment workflow in patient-specific aortic roots, where the stress distribution on the vessel wall was analysed during the entire TAVI procedure, including both valvuloplasty and deployment.

D. Discussion and Conclusion. The model underpins the development of a stress-based PPI prediction model after TAVI. The PPI prediction could contribute the development of in-silico trials of TAVI devices and procedures.

E. Acknowledgements and Conflict of Interest. We acknowledge support from the ERC Advanced Grant - UKRI Frontier Research Guarantee (INSILICO EP/Y030494/1), and helpful discussions with Michael MacRaid and Arezoo Zakeri.

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A PET Simulation Pipeline Using XCAT and ASIM

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Signal and noise properties in PET images are affected by many factors in the imaging chain that include biological, physical, and algorithmic effects. Because the overall impact of these effects on lesion detection in reconstructed images impractical to predict *a priori*, the simulation of PET signal and noise is an option in Virtual Imaging Clinical Trials is a useful method, if fast and accurate virtual image generation with realistically distributed model parameters is feasible.

We have developed a virtual imaging pipeline that uses the XCAT phantom[1] as an input, which allows for anatomical variability and high-resolution modeling in the spatial domain by using non-uniform rational B-splines (NURBS). This is used as input to ASIM[2], a fast PET simulator that performs the forward projection via raytracing to create noise-free emission signal that can be used to create ensembles of data realizations with independent noise. Images are reconstructed with the Duetto package from GE Healthcare.

A guiding principle of ASIM is to first analytically calculate projections based on the analytically described surfaces that define the emission and attenuation objects, e.g. the NURBS surfaces. This avoids the potential 'inverse-crime' of non-physical interactions with discrete system matrices used in iterative reconstruction methods. In other words, we want to avoid the use of projectors in the forward model that are similar to the numerical integration for forward- and back-projection in the image reconstruction process. The result is a fast and flexible simulation package that can quickly create stochastically accurate image replicates for the analysis of detectability in PET images.

B. METHODS

Figure 1: Simulation pipeline. The XCAT program creates a modified NURBS file which contains the anatomical boundaries to be simulated. PET activity levels can be manually adjusted.

Figure 1 shows how we have combined the XCAT, ASIM and Duetto software and created utilities to accept modifications in the XCAT NURBS file to make the activities appropriate for clinical PET imaging. These include a NURBS Parser that sorts through the roughly 3,000 NURBS objects for the assignment of PET activity values. A

second utility is the Activity Table Writer, which creates activity tables for both the XCAT and ASIM, which use different formats. Not shown in Figure 1 is the lesion insertion feature, which is described below.

1. XCAT Phantom and Modifications

To generate ensembles of anatomic variations, our simulations used two sets of XCAT phantoms. The first set started with a 'base' XCAT NURBS file and modified the global parameters *transaxial scaling* and *adipose tissue scaling* (Table 1). For the scaled phantoms, the patient sizes were chosen to approximately represent the 10th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 90th percentiles of habitus [4] based on waist circumference.

Table 1: Scaling factors applied to a baseline XCAT phantom, whose waist circumference was determined to be in the 25th percentile of adult males [4]. The transaxial scale factors scaled all organs in the phantom. The adipose tissue scaling only added adipose to the outline of the chest and abdomen.

XCAT Set 1 variation	waist circumference percentile	transaxial scaling	adipose tissue scaling
1	10	0.91	1.00
2	25	1.00	1.00
3	50	1.00	1.10
4	75	1.00	1.21
5	90	1.00	1.32

The second set of XCAT phantoms drew from a library of 56 pre-defined male and female phantoms that were matched to clinical CT images [3]. For the patient-based phantoms, the patient sizes were chosen to approximately represent the 10th, 25th, 50th, 75th, and 90th percentiles of habitus based on body-mass-index (BMI) (Table 2).

Table 2: A set of 5 XCAT phantoms drawn from the library described in [3]. BMI: body mass index.

XCAT Set 2 number	BMI percentile
M2	10
M7	26
M21	51
M27	74
M28	92

The first approach allows a precise level of control over the patient and organ sizes. However, organs are scaled together and for phantoms of the same size there is no inter-phantom variation of internal structures, unlike patients of the same size. The second set provides inter-phantom variation of internal structures and external shape but is limited to the 56 variations.

The PET uptake values in the XCAT activity table were specified by a table whose row labels exactly matched the surface names in the NURBS file. The NURBS Parser reads the NURBS file line by line and inserted a user specified SUV if the organ name matched a user-defined string.

2. ASIM

ASIM computes emission domain signal using line integrals, whose values depend on the intersection of line segments with analytical surfaces. New features in this iteration of our pipeline include improved detector modeling and lesion insertion.

Detector Modeling

The detection geometry is block-based Figure 2 (left) shows a clinical scanner geometry in which detector locations are rendered as black boxes. The blue lines represent line segments used in the signal computation, and the depicted oversampling shows how a "tube of response" can be modeled by multiple rays originating on the detector face.

Figure 2: (left) A clinical scanner ring geometry constructed from planar detector blocks. The blue lines show the sampling “tube of response” achieved by oversampling the line of response with six evenly spaced line segments. A zoomed in view of the sampling lines at the detector faces and lines. Right: Spherical and lobular lesions that were forward projected by ASIM and inserted into XCAT phantom emission data.

Lesion Insertion

Lesions were simulated separately from the phantoms and added to the emission data. Lesion geometry was specified by providing the center and axes of ellipsoids. To make lobular lesions with constant value (Figure 2, right), ASIM sorted intersections for all lobes in a lesion and recursively removed overlapping contributions to the signal. Lesions were attenuated with the attenuation map.

Phantoms corresponding to Tables 1 and 2 were generated with noise levels corresponding to 110M, 50M and 11M prompt coincidences. A lobular lesion of 7.5 mm was inserted with a target:background ratio of 4.5:1. Scattered and random coincidence effects were modeled. The scanner model was based on a 3-ring GE Discovery MI PET scanner with time-of-flight imaging. Image reconstruction was done using OSEM via the Duetto program, which replicated the scanner-based reconstruction code

C. RESULTS

Figure 3 shows noise-free emission images for the scaled XCAT phantoms parameterized in Table 1. both the voxelized XCAT output image and the NURBS-based reconstructed images are shown.

Figure 3: Voxelized XCAT output emission (top) and attenuation images (bottom) for scaled XCAT variations listed in Table 1. A lesion location in one of the images is indicated with a red circle.

Figure 4 shows equivalent images to those in Figure 3, but from the 5 XCAT phantoms drawn from the library based on patient CT images. The patient-based variability compared to Figure 3 is evident.

D. DISCUSSION

Figures 5 and 6 demonstrate the how the XCAT-ASIM pipeline enables PET simulations in which more user-defined modifications are possible, including organ-specific SUVs, patient habitus, and lesion geometry. The reduced computation time versus photon-tracking packages, as well as the precise non-discretized inputs, provides advantages for simulation studies on the effects of such factors on PET-based tasks.

Figure 4: Voxelized XCAT output emission (top) and attenuation images (bottom) corresponding to the 5 XCAT phantoms drawn from the library based on patient CT images. A lesion location in one of the images is indicated with a red circle.

Figure 5: Reconstructed PET images corresponding to Figure 3 with noise levels from top to bottom of: 110M, 50M and 11M prompt coincidences.

Figure 6: Reconstructed PET images corresponding to Figure 4 with noise levels from top to bottom of: 110M, 50M and 11M prompt coincidences.

E. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported in part by the following NIH grants: R01CA258298-01A1, P41EB028744, R01EB001838

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A Digital Twin Construction Workflow for Patient-Specific Aortic Stenosis Modelling

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Constructing digital twins from medical images is crucial for patient-specific modelling and in-silico trials [1]. Yet, the accurate segmentation and reconstruction of complex anatomical structures remains a significant challenge, requiring advanced algorithms to capture fine details and variations [2]. In this study, we focus on the cardiovascular structures implicated in aortic stenosis disease, particularly the aortic valve, calcium, and surrounding vasculature, to enhance in-silico trials for transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI).

B. METHODS

This study presents a digital twin construction workflow for cardiovascular structures of aortic stenosis disease. The methodology consists of two primary stages: anatomical segmentation from CT images and template-based mesh registration. Anatomical segmentation encompasses three parallel processes: (1) aorta and left ventricle extraction using Synopsys software (version Medical T-2022.03-SP2), (2) valve leaflet segmentation using a custom deep neural network trained on a public CT dataset with 27 subjects annotated with the structure of aortic valves [3], and (3) calcification segmentation using adaptive intensity thresholding calibrated to Hounsfield units. Template meshes with predefined topology are aligned with the segmented anatomical structures using coherent point drift registration, enabling consistent point correspondence across patient-specific geometries.

C. RESULTS

We processed 217 cases with multi-phase CTs retrospectively collected from a real clinical trial. Figures 1 and 2 visualise examples of the constructed twin mesh models. Quantitative analysis was performed by measuring the chamfer distance between the segmentations and registered meshes, which was 0.81 ± 0.07 mm, 0.69 ± 0.05 mm and 0.39 ± 0.07 mm (mean \pm standard deviation) for the aorta, left ventricle and valve structures, respectively. We further evaluated the average absolute error of calcification volume between our method's segmentation and the CoreLab measurements, which was 13.89, 15.13 and 7.73 mm³ for calcification in the left, right, and non-coronary cusps, respectively. These results demonstrate the accuracy of our approach in constructing clinically viable digital twin models of aortic stenosis, with sub-millimetre precision for anatomical structures and calcification volume errors well within the clinically acceptable range for TAVI planning

D. CONCLUSION

This workflow demonstrates the feasibility of creating detailed, patient-specific digital twins for aortic stenosis cases, potentially enabling more accurate TAVI-related in-silico trials. The proposed digital twin construction approach ensures reproducibility while maintaining individual anatomical variations, addressing a critical balance that has challenged previous methodologies. By combining the multi-anatomy segmentation method with coherent point drift registration, our framework efficiently creates a large-scale digital twin cohort (217 cases) in which each twin model retains unique anatomical characteristics with varying degrees of valvular calcification. The developed methodology

provides tools to advance the TAVI-related in-silico trials and thus accelerate the verification and validation of TAVI devices.

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Figure 1 Visual example of the digital twins of the cardiovascular structure of aortic stenosis (aorta and left ventricle).

Figure 2 Visual example of the digital twins of the cardiovascular structure of aortic stenosis (valve and calcification).

FREDem: a multi-GPU Monte Carlo simulation code for virtual imaging trials in radiology

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Monte Carlo (MC) simulations represent a widespread tool for virtual imaging trials (VITs) in medicine; however, many (CPU-based) full-MC codes entail long computational times and are not suitable for implementation in real-time. Thus, several GPU-based MC codes have been recently developed to allow for real-time performance. This study aimed at developing and validating a new multi-GPU based MC simulation code (called FREDem) for *photon and electron* transport with kilovoltage photons, to carry out VITs in diagnostic radiology. FREDem’s key purpose is to comply with reasonable simulation times while maintaining the needed accuracy and precision. FREDem is a GPU-accelerated MC simulation code based on the previously validated FRED (Fast parTicle thErapy Dose evaluator) code¹, designed for treatment planning in ion beam, proton, electron and photon radiotherapy. FREDem makes use of the ray tracing methods adopted in full-MC codes to achieve high accuracy, possibly at the expense of a reduced efficiency with respect to other GPU-based codes. On the other hand, FREDem is designed to run on multi-GPUs, to reduce computational times. In this work, we validated FREDem in the diagnostic energy range through several tests, including tests from the AAPM TG-195 report².

B. METHODS

1. FREDem – code structure

FREDem transports photons and electrons between 1 keV and 1 GeV, extending FRED¹’s range to the diagnostic energies. The code structure separates the initialization stage (fully operated on CPU to set phantom dimensions, source and detector directions) and the tracking stage (entirely performed by GPU). The latter adopts a history-based approach, with a GPU thread tracking a single primary particle, for high parallel computing on GPUs with tens of thousands of cores. The interaction processes are described by a series of continuous models that simulate the mean energy loss, the mean scattering angle and the energy fluctuation as particle’s condensed-history and discrete events of interactions with matter, described as point-like processes. Particles are followed as they cross a three-dimensional voxel grid by generating their tracks step-by-step, with the end of each step determined by the occurrence of an interaction or by a voxel boundary cross. For interactions resulting in the production of secondary particles, if the secondary particles’ energy exceeds the threshold (set during the initialization stage) they are stored for tracking, otherwise they are locally extinguished. To combine time reduction and high accuracy, FREDem adopts look-up tables as storage for most of the parameters needed to carry out the transport steps. In this work, the code runs on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 graphics card.

2. Percentage Depth Dose

The first validation test was the simulation of the Percentage Depth Dose (PDD) deposition in water of an 80 kV x-ray beam (W target, HVL = 2.3 mm Al), compared to the CPU-based code TOPAS, to the validated GPU-based code gCTD³ and with a laboratory measure with a PTW31010 ion chamber and an x-ray tube. In the simulations, the x-ray source was an isotropic point source with a 50 μm focal spot, collimated to a cone beam with 1.75 deg half cone angle and positioned at source-to-axis distance of 60.6 cm. The phantom was a (14.3 cm)³ box with 6.5-mm thick PMMA walls filled with (13 cm)³ water; the phantom voxel size was (0.5 mm)³. We scored the dose deposited in a circular region of interest (ROI) of

10 mm diameter along the beam axis, only in the water volume; the PDD curve was obtained normalizing each dose value with respect to the maximum dose value recorded.

3. Half Value Layer

The second test performed is the Case 1 of TG-195², evaluating the x-ray beam attenuation after crossing aluminium filters with thicknesses to attenuate the beam intensity to a half (Half Value Layer, HVL) and to a quarter (Quarter Value Layer, QVL) of its incident value. The simulation setup consisted of an isotropic x-ray point source, collimated to a circular projection of 1 mm diameter and centred on the entrance surface of the filter fixed at a source-to-surface distance of 10 cm. The ambient was filled with air and the scoring plane was at a source-to-image distance of 1 m. The nominal HVL and QVL values were given in the TG-195. The test was performed for monoenergetic photons with 30 keV and 100 keV and for x-ray tube spectra at 30 kV and 100 kV. Spectra definitions were available in the electronic resources of the report. The scoring was binned in 0.5 keV intervals up to the peak energy, for primary and scatter photons in polyenergetic spectra, and up to the incident photon energy, for the scatter component in monoenergetic simulations. The quantity scored was the energy fluence $\psi = \frac{\sum_i E_i}{A}$ per x-ray in a circular ROI of 10 mm diameter, then converted to incident air kerma $AK = \psi \left(\frac{\mu_{en}}{\rho} \right)$ to compute the ratios $R_{1,2} = \frac{\sum_E AK_{primary}(t=t_{1,2})}{\sum_E AK_{primary}(t=0)}$, and $R_{3,4} = \frac{\sum_E AK_{primary}(t=t_{3,4}) + \sum_E AK_{scatter}(t=t_{3,4})}{\sum_E AK_{primary}(t=0) + \sum_E AK_{scatter}(t=0)}$, with thicknesses $t_{1,3} = \text{HVL}$ and $t_{2,4} = \text{QVL}$.

C. RESULTS

1. Percentage Depth Dose

Figure 1a shows the PDD curves simulated with the codes gCTD, TOPAS and FREDem, and the measured PDD, indicating a good agreement between the four datasets, as evaluated by the relative difference between FREDem and TOPAS, and between FREDem and gCTD (fig. 1c). Using TOPAS as a reference, from fig.1d we can note that FREDem's in better agreement with TOPAS than gCTD. Figure 1b shows the dose distribution inside the phantom (water volume and PMMA walls) along the beam direction.

Figure 1: a) Percentage depth dose curve in water (PMMA walls box) for an 80 kV X-ray beam measured with an ion chamber and simulated with FREDem, TOPAS and gCTD MC codes; b) 2D dose distribution along the central slice of the phantom; c) percentage relative difference between FREDem and TOPAS, between FREDem and gCTD, and between FREDem and experimental measurements in the PDD simulation; d) percentage relative difference between FREDem and TOPAS and between gCTD and TOPAS.

2. HVL and QVL

Figure 2 shows the comparison between the HVL (fig. 2a,c) and QVL (fig. 2b,d) for the monochromatic and polychromatic beams, calculated with FREDem (green), vs. the reference MC codes (EGSnrc, Geant4, MCNP, Penelope) reported in TG-195.

Figure 2: a) AK ratio R_1 , b) R_2 , c) R_3 and d) R_4 for two monochromatic (30 keV and 100 keV) and two polychromatic beams (30 kV and 100 kV) obtained with FREDem and EGSnrc, Geant4, MCNP and Penelope (data taken from TG-195²).

D. DISCUSSION

In the field of VITs, the need for fast MC simulation codes is an important requirement. This can be achieved by using GPU-based MC codes without sacrificing the accuracy of the physical model implemented in the code. From our preliminary PDD tests with FREDem code running on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 graphics card we measured a maximum tracking rate of 1.18×10^6 primary photons/s, against gCTD performance (without electron tracking capability) of 6.23×10^8 primary photons/s. However, FREDem is in better agreement with TOPAS than gCTD (maximum difference of $\pm 2.7\%$, vs. $\pm 3.9\%$ for gCTD), and shows a maximum relative deviation of $\pm 10\%$ with respect to the measured PDD and $\pm 4.1\%$ with respect to gCTD. The validations following the TG-195 protocol indicated very good agreement with the mean of the results reported by other MC codes (0.38%) and with the expected values (0.29%), and 1.10×10^8 photons/s maximum computing speed.

E. CONCLUSION

We reported first tests of the GPU-based MC code, FREDem, developed for photon and electron transport for VITs in the diagnostic energy range. These tests, against reference MC codes and measurements, validate FREDem in VIT simulation platforms for radiologic imaging, with fast computation times permitted by the GPU acceleration. Further tests are underway to investigate the validity of the physical model implemented in FREDem. The combined set of the parent MC code FRED for particle and photon therapy¹ & FREDem represents a fast simulation platform for both diagnostic imaging and radiotherapy investigations.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work was supported by Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN), via the research project VITA.

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XCAT+ for Tracer Specific Numerical Simulation

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A. BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

Traditional cardiac imaging protocols evaluate perfusion-related heart conditions through comparative analysis of stress and rest physiological states. However, the statistical characterization of tracer distribution patterns across heterogeneous tissue types represents an underexplored research domain. The eXtended CArdiac-Torso (XCAT) phantom software¹⁻³ provides a hybrid computational framework combining voxelized and mathematical phantoms, offering an optimal balance between anatomical realism and experimental flexibility for medical imaging research, particularly in Single Photon Emission Computed Tomography (SPECT) applications.

The purpose of this investigation was to conduct a comprehensive statistical analysis of ^{99m}Tc-tetrofosmin tracer distributions across cardiac tissue regions, utilizing reconstructed patient imaging data to establish distribution patterns and integrate these empirical findings into enhanced XCAT computational phantoms called XCAT+ phantoms.

B. METHODS

The study analyzed tracer concentrations in cardiac tissues and liver from 40 reconstructed SPECT images stratified into four equal cohorts: Control Stress (n=10), Control Rest (n=10), Disease Stress (n=10), and Disease Rest (n=10).

Retrospective data acquisition was conducted using a dual-headed SPECT camera (Infinia Hawkeye 4, GE HealthCare) with ^{99m}Tc-sestamibi tracer doses of 10 mCi for rest conditions and 25 mCi for stress conditions⁴. Images were reconstructed via maximum likelihood expectation maximization (MLEM) incorporating a realistic system matrix for a low-energy high-resolution (LEHR) parallel hole collimator with point-spread function modeling.

Statistical distribution patterns were identified through comparative analysis of pixel intensity histograms generated for each region of interest⁵. Combined histograms were created for respective cohorts through normalization procedures based on mean pixel values within each group. These histograms were then fitted to normal, lognormal, gamma, or laplacian statistical distributions using maximum likelihood estimates^{6,7}, which were compared via the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test⁸. The empirical statistical functions derived from patient data were integrated into the extended cardiac-torso (XCAT) computational phantom architecture to generate enhanced phantoms.

C. RESULTS

The statistical analysis revealed distribution patterns that demonstrate partial concordance with established medical knowledge and empirical parameters in tracer distribution behavior, as shown in Table 1. The fitted statistical functions (an example of which can be seen in Figure 1) successfully characterized tracer kinetics and uptake variability across different tissue states. The resulting XCAT+ phantoms demonstrated enhanced accuracy in modeling tracer distribution patterns compared to conventional computational phantoms, providing more realistic simulations as shown in Figure 2. To further augment clinical realism, myocardial infarctions were computationally incorporated into the cardiac tissue, enabling accurate representation of infarcted regions within the simulated phantom environment, as demonstrated in Figure 3.

Mean Intensity Values by Organ and Condition

Organ	Control-Rest	Control-Stress	Diseased-Rest	Diseased-Stress
Myocardium	0.2137	0.8300	0.1359	0.4974
Liver	0.3864	1.516	0.2346	1.042
Left Blood Pool	0.1089	0.4779	0.0736	0.3083
Right Blood Pool	0.1423	0.6080	0.0923	0.3407

Table 1: Mean Intensity Values by Organ (Region of Interest) and Condition. Each mean is calculated from voxel intensity data from 10 SPECT images of the given condition. Although these values lack a meaningful unit, they theoretically represent the relative amount tracer concentration in the given Region of Interest.

Figure 1: Histogram of normalized myocardium distribution across 10 control-rest SPECT images, generated using python's matplotlib library. 'loc' represents the mean value and 'scale' represents the standard deviation. The x-axis is the voxel intensity value, and the y-axis is the normalized PDF. This is a sample from the 16 normalized histograms we created (one for each Region of Interest, for each condition).

Figure 2: Comparison of anatomical and patient-derived cardiac phantoms. From left to right: *XCAT*, a computational phantom with simplified anatomical structures; *XCAT+*, an enhanced *XCAT* phantom with added tracer distribution; and a clinical *SPECT image* reconstructed with MLEM algorithm.

Figure 3: Axial view comparison of *XCAT* and *XCAT+* along with a *XCAT+* with myocardial infarction. The infarction can be seen as some pixel intensities appear to be very low on the left and right ventricles.

D. DISCUSSION

The statistical insights derived from this investigation enhance the understanding of tracer behavior across various tissue types, representing a novel contribution to the field of cardiac imaging research. The integration of empirically-derived statistical functions into *XCAT* computational phantoms bridges a critical gap between computational modeling frameworks and clinical reality. The incorporation of statistical patterns observed in actual patient data results in more clinically relevant phantom simulations, offering a possibility of advancing cardiac imaging techniques. Additionally, the inclusion of myocardial infarctions in the *XCAT+* phantoms allows us to realistically simulate images from patients with pathological conditions. The creation of realistic *SPECT* images in a traceable manner (i.e. without generative AI) is a novel development in the field of medical imaging, and will continue to be improved upon in future iterations.

E. CONCLUSION

This work enabled us to look at reconstructed SPECT images from a novel, empirical perspective, providing new insights into the tracer distributions captured by these images. By combining full-body XCAT phantoms with real patient statistics, we have created realistic synthetic SPECT images which show statistically sound distributions of tracer in the heart and liver. Future improvements to these XCAT+ phantoms will improve the visual similarity to real SPECT images and further enhance the accuracy of our statistics.

F. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND CONFLICT OF INTEREST

This work is supported by the NIH funding R15EB030807. We acknowledge data provided by Dr. Youngho Seo's lab at the Univ. of California, San Francisco.

Conflict of Interest: There is no conflict of interest to declare by any author.

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Statistical shape modelling of the adult mitral valve using CCTA

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Introduction

The mitral valve (MV), a bi-leaflet atrioventricular heart valve, is essential for ensuring unidirectional blood flow from the left atrium to the left ventricle¹. Structural or functional abnormalities of the mitral valve can disrupt this flow, leading to various cardiovascular pathologies². Understanding the anatomical variations of the MV is crucial for comprehending the complexities of these conditions. However, previous studies have primarily relied on linear measurements to describe variation in valvular shape, often neglecting the intricate three-dimensional (3D) elements of the valve².

Methods

This study employs statistical shape modelling (SSM) to quantify the principal axes of shape variation and clinically relevant metrics in a population of patient specific 3D MV reconstructions. Geometries were reconstructed from 43 publicly available cardiac computed tomography angiography (CCTA) scans³ in Synopsys' Simpleware⁴, using a combination of automatic and semi-automatic methods. SSM was conducted using Synopsys' Simpleware SSM Toolkit.

Preliminary Results

Results show that the largest mode of shape variation correlated closest with valve size, with the second largest correlating (inversely) closest with valvular height. The generated SSM can be used to generate a mean MV and can be used to generate numerous representative sample shapes that encompass the range of shape variation (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: (A) mean shape of the mitral valve generated from SSM of 43 patients. (B-D) Population modes of shape variation plotted against key geometric features: valvular height (A) intercommisural distance (C) and anterior-posterior distance (D).

Discussion

The SSM generated in this study enables the creation of a population of physiologically realistic, virtual 3D reconstructions of the MV. This dataset demonstrates the anatomical variations in the MV's healthy features and further analysis may elucidate deviations linked to pathological conditions. Future work could use this virtual MV patient population to conduct *in silico* clinical trials of interventional technologies like mitral valve replacement devices, by employing computational biomechanical testing methods like finite element analysis⁵. This knowledge can enhance diagnosis, inform treatment planning, and support the development of personalized interventions for mitral valve diseases.

References

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